

UNIVERSITY OF NORTHWEST

**THE MEANING OF MANIPULATION, EQUIVALENTS IN DAILY LIFE AND ITS
USAGE IN TECHNOLOGY**

MASTER THESIS

Mete ÖZKÖK

Thesis Advisor: Prof. Dr. Bilal Semih BOZDEMİR

2017

TERM PROJECT APPROVAL

The study titled “THE MEANING OF MANIPULATION, ITS CORRECTIVES IN DAILY LIFE AND ITS USE IN TECHNOLOGY” prepared by Mete ÖZKÖK was published in 2017, in accordance with the relevant articles of the “ University of Northwest Education and Examination Regulations, a graduation project in the Psychological Science Undergraduate Program”. evaluated and accepted .

	<u>Title - Name Surname</u>	<u>Signature</u>
Project consultant	: Prof. Dr. Bilal Semih BOZDEMIR	
Head of department	:	

Director of the institution

Contents

TERM PROJECT APPROVAL	2
Summary.....	4
DECLARATION OF COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL PRINCIPLES AND RULES.....	6
Introduction.....	7
So why do people still use the word " manipulation "?	8
A Comprehensive Definition.....	15
An Integrative Manipulation Explained.....	17
Manipulation as Sneaky and Sneaky Deception.....	18
Especially in Liberal Societies	24
A New Concept That Takes An Integrated Approach To Characterize Manipulation	24
A Revised Definition of Manipulation.....	26
Sneaky and Sneaky and/or Deceptive Ways	27
What Makes Us Not to Realize Our Capacity to Influence People Through Our Emotional States?	29
An Example of a Persistent Phenomenon	29
Same Research Method.....	33
Responsibility.....	33
Moral Responsibility	34
Prevention Policy	37
Deceptive Manipulation	39
Difference Between Manipulative Effect and Non-Manipulative Effect.....	43
Choosing Between Alternative Policies, Practices and/or Technologies	52
Focusing on Alleviating Symptoms.....	55
Behavioral Advertising.....	66
Harms of Online Manipulation	68
Technology and Autonomy.....	75
Manipulation in Online Spaces.....	78
Two Different Workflows	79
Muscular Preferences in a Western Population.....	87
Conclusion	92
References.....	94

Summary

We are continually and in a variety of ways each other's primary sources of influence in the world. There are other forms of influence, on the other hand, which do not give rise to any ethical considerations all. This form of influence may be utilized, for instance, when we wish to convince someone of something by arguing with a rational and well-founded argument to win them over to our point of view. On the other hand, there are pressures that force us to behave in a certain way, and we often find such influences disturbing because they restrict our freedom to act in a free and independent manner. On the other hand, it seems that there are other kinds of effects that lie somewhere along a continuum of impacts and that, for the most part, do not affect us in a reasonable manner while at the same time not imposing any kind of coercion on us. They do this by utilizing our internal processes, which are frequently unconscious, and by utilizing environmental decision-making channels to exert influence over us by changing our emotional states, or more specifically our feelings, emotions, and moods. One of the most common ways that they do this is using social engineering. . This is intricately connected to a pattern of conduct that we refer to as "manipulation," which has been persistently associated with a negative connotation. We hear the term "manipulation" used in many different situations, such as in the realms of business, politics, and even our own personal relationships. Although throughout history, manipulation has been seen in a very negative light, often as a dishonest kind of coercive approach, the truth is that it is a more nuanced problem. In this research, we give a viewpoint on the phenomena that is wider and, hopefully, more unique than those presented in earlier studies. This perspective has the potential to explain more benign and maybe even positive manifestations of the phenomena. Because of this, manipulation provides the manipulator with at least some degree of freedom to choose whether or not to pursue a goal (an action, a product, etc.) that is viewed as either enjoyable or unpleasant. In conclusion, we will argue that manipulative strategies that target emotional registration are not necessarily in conflict with rationality and autonomy, but rather are a constitutive part of a complex decision-making process that is based on both emotional states and logic, and that this is not always the case. In other words, we will argue that manipulative strategies that target emotional registration are not necessarily in conflict with rationality and autonomy. To put it another way, we shall argue that manipulative methods that target the emotional register do not inevitably pit logic and autonomy against one another. Although while

the subject's rational freedom can be limited or changed because of the manipulation, this does not necessarily imply that the subject does not have any freedom, as we shall demonstrate in the following paragraphs.

Keywords: *Manipulation, Manipulation in Daily Life, Technology and Manipulation*

Mete ÖZKÖK

Department of Psychology

University of Northwest

Thesis Advisor: Prof. Dr. Bilal Semih BOZDEMİR

DECLARATION OF COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL PRINCIPLES AND RULES

I declare that I have acted in accordance with scientific ethical principles and rules in the preparation of this term project, that I have referred to the sources used within the scope of the study in accordance with scientific norms and that I have included them in the bibliography . I declare that I accept all moral and legal consequences that will arise in the event of a situation contrary to this statement I made regarding my work.

Mete ÖZKÖK

Introduction

We will try to conceptualize manipulation in accordance with Aristotle's understanding of rhetoric, which is to say, as a neutral instrument that employs both problematic and unproblematic tactics, which morally upright or immoral individuals can use to achieve either positive or negative results. In other words, we will attempt to conceptualize manipulation in accordance with Aristotle's understanding of rhetoric. The same may be said regarding the act of participating in the practice of exerting influence on other people. Given that a significant percentage of people are going to think that this is irrational, it seems to reason that this is something that must be clarified in some way. The process of conceptualizing manipulation is a challenging one since it requires making a significant number of intuitive leaps. The question of how manipulation may (and should not be considered as) a kind of influence can often be challenging. This is because there are many different motives for manipulating others. Most of these explanations are not very in-depth, even though some of them are more in-depth than others.

Theun A., and so forth. More than 20 years ago, van Dijk posed the question of why there was not a comprehensive definition of manipulation at the time. This was in response to the widespread misunderstanding that prevailed in society at the time. Even though it is used rather often, he maintains that the concept of manipulation "... has never been specified in a theory" (van Dijk Citation 1998, 340). Given the prevalence of manipulation as a tactic for gaining influence, the lack of an agreed-upon definition is more surprising when considered in this context. For example, in 1978, novelist Joel Rudinow expressed his dissatisfaction of this practice by voicing his opinion publicly. (Rudinow Citation: 1978, page 338). Because of this, having a dialogue about the techniques and applications of manipulation is not only very difficult but also really necessary. This is because, when seen as a strategy, it is not quite clear what it consists of or which techniques it integrates. This is because it is not entirely clear what it consists of.

Because of the ambiguity of ideas that already exist, the term "manipulation" may be used accurately as a pejorative to describe an attempt to make an impression, even if there is no further discussion of the subject matter. This is due of the ambiguity of the word "manipulation." According to this interpretation of the text, manipulators who act only in their own self-interest, just as Iago does in Shakespeare's Othello, carry out their plans in a dishonest and covert manner with the intention of bringing about undesirable and harmful outcomes for the person who is being manipulated. This is the same behavior that Iago displays in the play. In addition to this,

manipulation disregards or even subverts the reasoning of the person who is being influenced; this is something that seems to be something that all types of manipulation have in common, at least to some degree. As a direct result of this, an attorney's autonomy is infringed upon, and he is treated in a dishonorable way (although the veracity of this assertion varies widely depending on the specifics of each case) (Fischer Citation2017, 16). This is in no way equivalent to what it implied in the past for "manipulate," which is a term that originates from the Latin word *manipulus* and originally meant "a handful" for soldiers serving in the legion. This is in no way equivalent to what it implied in the past for "manipulate." While it was originally used to mean "to hold someone's hand" (sometimes in a good manner!), over the course of time it has evolved into a specialized phrase that indicates that something has been "handled." This is even though initially it was intended to represent "to hold someone's hand" (for example, a machine; we are getting closer to our job). meaning within the context of the present).

The notion of "results-oriented treatment of a person" is making its debut in the sphere of scientific discourse, and it may be found positioned near the theories of behaviorism and psychoanalysis. Given the eventful history of dictatorships using propaganda to create public opinion with fear, anger, distrust of others, and admiration for authoritarian evil, it is understandable that the term "manipulation" has become commonplace. This history also provides context for why the term has become so commonplace. In light of this background, it is easy to see how the implications connected with the word "manipulation" contributed to the spread of its use in everyday language. It is easy to see how these meanings may have found their way into our everyday usage of the word given such a background.

The claim that a wicked manipulator reprehensibly affected an agent in a reprehensible manner by misleading and subverting logic is what prompted the term "manipulation" to acquire negative moral overtones. This charge has its roots in the Neo-Marxist tradition, and it received further support from a widespread shock to the past (Fischer Citation2017, p . 36–40).

[So why do people still use the word " manipulation "?](#)

Arguments in favor of maintaining the phrase, along with some suggestions for improving the way it is interpreted by listeners. To begin, the suggestion that we should stop making use of the word "manipulation" raises the question of whether or not it is even possible to have a conversation about events that are analogous to those in question without making use of that phrase. The

assertion that we should cease using the term "manipulation" has brought up this dilemma. The idea of "effect" may be viewed of as both a broad umbrella category and fairly ambiguous when considered on its own. It's possible that "emotional influence" and "irrational influence" are neutral alternatives that are less negative than the word "manipulation," but these phrases certainly aren't used in everyday speech. Manipulation can be defined as the act of intentionally trying to persuade another person to do something against their will. The word "manipulation," which has the connotation of turning a dial with one's hand while focusing on the result, continues to seem to be the best choice. On the other hand, the negative connotation may be more directly linked to the fact that the conversation placed an excessive amount of emphasis on the dual nature of reason and emotional experiences. This may be the case because the conversation placed an excessive amount of emphasis on the dual nature of reason and emotional experiences.

As a direct result of this, the idea that calling into question our logic and "contaminating" it with emotion is seen as a threat to our autonomy and dignity has acquired momentum in the awareness of the public. Since we are all finite and somewhat rational animals, it is essential that manipulation as a kind of influence that targets our emotional states be identified as a regular method of communication. This is because it is necessary that manipulation can be recognized as a regular way of communication. The individual circumstances should determine the extent to which one should adjust their understanding of this. Even if we are all finite animals with a restricted ability to think logically, we are all capable of acknowledging this fact. Since it depicts an influence that is beyond the capabilities of our realistic radar, the word "manipulation" is a great option for characterizing this situation. This is because it shows an impact that is beyond the capabilities of our reality radar. Actually, the idiom obtains a higher degree of specificity after having some distinctions added to it; nonetheless, it does not wander unduly from its main significance in doing so. It is interesting to note that the findings of a recent poll that a colleague of mine in marketing and I carried out together found that a representative sample of respondents saw the word "manipulation" as neither inherently unethical nor problematic, nor as inevitably deceitful and damaging. This finding was reached after we polled a total of a hundred and fifty people. It was usually regarded to be a kind of influence that makes use of our emotional states, and since it does make use of this channel, it is essential that we stay aware to avoid it from being harmful at any point in time in the future (Feurer and Fischer Citation2022). Not only does it make sense to separate in a way that is as clear and precise as is practically possible, but there also seems to be

real evidence that supports the idea behind this differentiation. As a consequence of this, the question of whether or not manipulation demands a negative moral value and the question of whether or not it is fair to offer an unbiased account of the event are considerably more important. This holds true not only due to the fact that it is logical to differentiate as clearly and accurately as possible, but also due to the fact that there appears to be actual data that supports this theory. This holds true not only because it is logical to differentiate as clearly and accurately as possible, but also because of this. In conclusion, manipulation may appear to be a poor attempt to impress with specific problematic tactics; however, when we examine it further, we discover that it is not as obvious as it may appear to be in certain circumstances. This is because manipulation is not as obvious as it may appear to be in certain circumstances. Influence may take the form of manipulation when it is utilized with the intention of acquiring a competitive advantage. It is crucial to discern between objectionable and unobjectionable efforts at manipulation rather than making the assumption that manipulation is necessarily unethical, problematic, dishonest, damaging, and sneaky. The following examples will clarify some of these sorts of unacceptable efforts at manipulation, if not all of them entirely.

So, let's begin by thinking about some examples of how to influence an agent in a way that is not only illogical but also not aggressive, which I would want to say is truly a type of manipulation. It is essential to emphasize the fact that at the core of what we refer to as "manipulation," there seems to be an effort to alter our emotional states by drawing a conclusion that is either enjoyable or disagreeable. This is the case in spite of the fact that there are a great deal of other traits, such as being stealthy and engaging in devious techniques, as well as being dishonest.

Othello gives fire to his envy by focusing on the love bond that exists between Cassio and Desdemona. Its purpose is to stoke the flames of envy, and to do so, it quotes a line from the song that has the potential to make us feel particularly helpless, as well as a verse from the Bible that suggests even insignificant things like the air we breathe may be powerful sources of approval for those who are envious. It is clear that the purpose of this passage is to stoke the fires of envy, and it does so by citing these two sources.

Because of his convoluted and deceptive attitude, as well as the various techniques he uses, he allows himself to become consumed by feelings of jealousy, hatred, and insecurity. This is a direct result of the many strategies he employs. Second, take into mind this legendary example from the

annals of German history: Even though potatoes should have been the answer to a catastrophic food crisis, it was a tough task to make the potato into a popular meal across Europe. Although potatoes ought to have been the solution to the issue, this came to pass instead. In the year 1746, a momentous event took place in Prussia, and it is of utmost significance that this took place. The fact that inedible species were provided alongside edible ones and that no one knew how to properly prepare the new product for eating did not sit well with the farmers who bought it. In addition, no one knew how to properly prepare the inedible species for consumption. When the attempts of the Prussian government to establish control over the planting of potatoes were fruitless, the King of Prussia turned to other techniques in an effort to persuade his citizens to begin consuming the novel cuisine. The significance of the potato had to be conveyed by priests, and King Frederick the Great of Prussia made an effort to portray potatoes as something delicate and important by ordering his army to keep watch over a field in which potatoes were being grown. This strategy was really one of the ones that were put to the test. At a time when France was experiencing an abundance of food shortages, Antoine Augustin Parmentin was a citizen of that country and worked hard to find a solution to the problem. The potato became one of the most well-liked dishes as a direct result of the popularity of these recipes, which contributed to its prominence. It is even reported that he is hosting a great number of large banquets, at which dignitaries dine in front of massive audiences while praising potatoes.

Those whose intelligence levels were similar to their own were lured to the 'great' product, and relatively rapidly, their desire for it increased. As a direct consequence of this, they were far better able to control the amount of food that they consumed. One additional item to think about is the passage that can be found in Tom Sawyer written by Mark Twain. In this piece of writing, Tom is persuaded into painting a fence, and the thought of having to carry out the responsibility fills him with dread. It doesn't take long for it to become abundantly evident that Jim's efforts to persuade Jim to replace him in a fair way would not be successful, despite the fact that Jim puts out his best efforts in this regard. This was because utilizing force was not a choice that could be made in this situation.

We can interpret what he is saying as follows: Not by saying that this or that is wrong and that you should do the opposite, he tries to invoke guilt (perhaps not even consciously; he is able to express his needs that way) (that's why he argues), but using a certain style and non-causal words By

suggesting something, making him admit that his life isn't easy, it's important to make you believe that you can at least do something to ease the pain he's been through. It is irrelevant as to whether or not you understand what he is doing in order to get you to feel what he is causing you to feel since it will still have the impact that was intended.

You begin to have feelings of guilt, and as a result, you check your schedule to see when you may be able to carve out some time for yourself. Let's take a look at the example that Joel Rudinow, who wrote one of the first studies on manipulation as a covert approach for influencing an agent, provided for us. He did this so that we could better understand his findings. "Jones complains of being the regular victim of his wife's manipulative tactics," Rudinow said. "Jones complains of being the victim of his wife's frequent attempts." "Jones complains of being the victim of his wife's manipulative tactics," and he demonstrates this point with a situation that is quite typical. He is getting ready to leave the house in order to go to the weekly poker game that he very much looks forward to attending, and he is really excited about it. Jones has been maintaining an unusually packed schedule as of late; in the last two weeks, he has not spent a single evening at home with his wife. In all, he has not had a single evening off in that time period. Throughout the whole of their time together, he has not spent a single evening at home with either of his kids. He asserts that she is seeking to wield some kind of power over him in order to further her own agenda. This is something that his wife immediately confirms, and she goes on to say that, in the same way that Jones is aware of it, she is aware of how frequently the two of them have been having sexual encounters as of late, and that she is aware of it in the same way that Jones is aware of it. This is something that his wife is aware of in the same way that Jones is aware of it (Rudinow Citation1978 , 341). We look at the notion that Jones' wife is seeking to exercise some form of control over her husband, which is a frequent charge that has been leveled against her. Our article investigates this issue. To put it another way, he believes that the most successful approach to try to change someone's behavior is to exert control over the many phases of that person's emotional life, or, to put it another way, to create desire in that person (although he is disgusted at this point, so he may have overestimated his effort). Despite this, not a single one of them is in the dark about what is going on, and there is not even an attempt to cover anything up in any way. Let's consider this as a last resort, but it's certainly not the least important step: let's look at a situation in which persuading someone is not just irrational, but also not compelling. Let's examine this scenario. It would seem that humans often use techniques including both pleasure and punishment in their

dealings with one another. It's possible that we conceive of punishment as something that occurs as a response to a particular action that was taken on purpose and has the effect of lowering the likelihood that the behavior will be repeated in the future. This is one way that we may comprehend the concept of being punished. Its purpose is to discourage a certain behavior and, depending on the circumstances of the interaction, it might present itself in a number of different ways. Its goal is to achieve this aim.

In addition to this, he does not hide his hurt feelings and makes no secret of the fact that he is using them as a weapon to pressure him into feeling guilty. On the other hand, enjoyment is what motivates people to do particular behaviors, such as increasing the likelihood that a person would eat in a way that is beneficial to their health or participate in some kind of physically active pursuit that includes a degree of excitement. Both the provision of gratification and the infliction of punishment are neither very effective strategies for cognitively persuading an agent to conduct in a certain manner, nor are they particularly effective strategies for coercing an agent to behave in a particular manner. Neither approach is especially fruitful in this regard. There is a possibility that, at first glance, the story of the potato, Tom Sawyer's escape from washing the fence, George's lack of love, Nana's guilt, and Jones' wife's seduction may not seem to be typical examples of manipulation. On the other hand, Iago's approach to Othello is virtually unanimously recognized as the prototypical example due to their interactions with one another. Iago's intention to win Othello's favor is accompanied by self-serving and even demonic urges, as well as blatant dishonesty and underhandedness on his part. Iago employs a strategy that is not just deceitful but also manipulative. Because of this, Othello is unaware of the events that have taken place, and because of this, Othello has very little room for free movement and is on the verge of a horrible death (but he does have some middleman; otherwise, the game wouldn't be a tragedy).

And this is how people commonly image manipulation, as well as how the phrase is frequently accused of being used in our day-to-day discussions and interactions. He is shouting at you and labeling everything you do "ethically problematic." And this is how people frequently picture manipulation. It would seem that many instances exhibit "problematic" behavior, although to varying degrees. By portraying an event in terms of whether it would be joyful or painful, the underlying purpose of each of these instances is to produce a change in the emotional state of a person, with the eventual goal of influencing the target to modify their behavior. In any of these

scenarios, neither rational argument nor physical force is used; rather, the focus is placed on the regulation of emotional states through the presentation of alternative outcomes. This is done so as to prevent the individual from becoming overly invested in one particular course of action.

It is immediately apparent that we are able to uncover varying degrees of intent (and effort), and that even while certain attempts are not just manipulative but rather manipulative, they combine with other sorts of influence, such as trying to intellectually persuade someone of anything. This is something that can't be missed. When one takes into consideration the reality that varying degrees of purpose (and effort) may be found, it is easy to see that this is the case (for example, Tom confuses rational persuasion and manipulation). It is also abundantly clear that a variety of strategies, such as cheating, deceit, and other repercussions (possibly even negative ones), are utilized in order to assist in the manipulation of the individual who is the target of the manipulation. This is in order to facilitate the manipulation of the individual.

In other instances, the implications are not quite as catastrophic, and in fact, it's possible that they won't even have any negative effects at all. On the other hand, the fate that was destined for Othello was a particularly awful one. It is vital to choose a representation of continuity because of the regularity with which our separate efforts to have an impact on one another tend to combine into a coherent whole. This is why it is important to pick a representation of continuity. As a consequence of this, we decide to go with a picture that is a continuum, in which no component is absolutely clearly distinguishable from the parts that surround it, with the exception of a division that is entirely arbitrary. In this image, we go with a picture that is a continuum. It is still a good idea to use ideal differentiations to generate a clear image of the many distinct types of consequences; however, it is vital to keep in mind that real life is sometimes more difficult than philosophical categories, so this should be done with caution. Since the universe is "a gigantic flowering, buzzing mess," as William James once described it (Citation 1890, 488), it is not only challenging but also impossible to comprehend how one of us has an impact on the other in a way that is well-organized and clear. Because human decision making is analogous to a very complicated black box that is influenced by particular events, unique settings, habits, and individual characteristics of the person making the choice, the world can be described as "a great blooming, buzzing confusion." This is because the world is "a great blooming, buzzing confusion" (Fischer Citation2017, 63, 85). The technique of operant conditioning, which applies both negative

and positive reward in equal quantity, serves as the most conspicuous instance of this concept since it mixes the two types of reinforcement in equal measure. Yet, conditioning is merely one of the many ways that our emotional states may be exploited in the field of study that it covers. This research area encompasses a wide variety of methods.

Examples such as those shown above demonstrate that there are, in fact, a great lot more methods. It is conceivable that the ordinary, daily usage of the word "manipulation," together with the features that are typically associated with it, may not always emerge as a necessary and sufficient prelude for the act of manipulation. This is something that should be considered a possibility. On the other hand, we shouldn't just give in to our natural tendencies or adapt to the standards that have been established. Both of these things are unacceptable. My opinion is that it is reasonable to take a step back in order to acquire a more in-depth grasp of the subject at hand by exploring the phenomena in issue on a descriptive level. This is what I mean when I say that taking a step back is logical. This has the ability to startle our intuition and call into question an understanding that is clouded by some really severe and well-known examples of manipulation (in addition to Othello, George Orwell's Nineteen Eighty-Four may come to mind at this point). It is vital to take into account alternate outcomes that are not as catastrophic, or even more humane, in which the individual who is harmed does not suffer any damage, or even takes into mind their present state of health. The negative connotation may not even be dependent on the act of manipulation itself; rather, it is dependent on the manner in which a manipulative enterprise is run, in addition to the question of whether or not it involves cheating, deception, and self-interested manipulators in a particular circumstance. This is because the negative connotation is dependent on the manner in which a manipulative enterprise is run.

A Comprehensive Definition

Manipulation may be thought of as a wide and pervasive sort of influence exerted by human action in general. This can serve as a beginning point for our attempts to construct a complete definition of the term "manipulation," which we can begin by thinking of as a starting point for our efforts. When we speak about manipulation, this will assist us in getting a clearer picture of what it is that we are attempting to express. In spite of the numerous guises that it might assume, the goal of manipulation is to shape our mental and emotional states, and as a result, our behaviors and our thoughts. To name just one of the many ways in which we, as active participants, have the power

to have an effect on our own capacities, manipulation on a vast scale is one of them. While looking at a map of influence on a more macro level, a lot of emphasis was paid to the categories of rational persuasion and compulsion. On the other hand, manipulation seems to be a kind of influence that may perhaps be located anywhere in the middle of these two extremes (Beauchamp Citation2001, 477; Fischer Citation2017, 53). When it comes to the capacity of individuals to make choices, there are a variety of various ways in which they may be influenced. Rational persuasion and coercion can be thought of as poles since they represent opposite extremes of a continuum that demonstrates these kinds of influence. These two polar opposites, rather from being recognized as significant distinctions between them, should be seen as two sides of the same coin, analogous to how light and dark are both aspects of the same whole. As a consequence of this, there are a significant number of ratings that fall somewhere in the region of the middle ground between how likely an influence is and how implausible it is. When there is coercion present, there are less and fewer choices that are practical, which eventually leads to the use of coercion as a solution. In the event of coercion, which may be carried out in a variety of different ways, an agent is often unable to make a choice freely, and sometimes even rationally, since he is not given any information that would allow him to make that decision (or at least one that is preferred). Because of this, he is unable to make a choice that is in his own best interests.

Almost. The illustration of rational persuasion demonstrates the opposite: in this scenario, an agent is given the ability to freely decide on the basis of the good reasons presented to him so that he can make his decision based on all of the information that is available to him. This enables the agent to make his decision based on all of the information that is available to him. Because of this, the agent is able to arrive at a conclusion after carefully considering all of the facts at his disposal. It would seem that none of the situations that have been offered up to this point constitute a crystal clear example of logical persuasion; rather, they only reflect some degree of attempts at debating the topic at hand.

When we are in danger or when our ideas are being influenced by other elements that may be difficult to control, such as our emotions, rational persuasion might be deemed a maximal and optimum option. Under these kinds of circumstances, the extent to which people are free to make their own decisions is constrained by the use of force, whereas the use of logical persuasion might be seen as the highest and most perfect option. This is because the use of physical force imposes

limitations on the process of freely deciding what to do with one's life. People discover that they are at least partially free to act on feelings like jealousy, guilt, hunger, insecurity, and curiosity when such emotions first begin to arise inside them.

In conclusion, it appears that anything that does not absolutely compel or logically persuade an agent in order to accomplish the intended outcome might be considered to be a kind of manipulation. Affect plays a role in the dispute surrounding the nature of free decision-making and action that is notable for its ambiguity. This role may range from being a substantial component of free decision-making and action to being a grave threat to it, or it can simply be indifferent to it. The discussion is significant for the presence of ambivalence on both sides. Everyone is aware that it will be difficult to arrive at a decision about this topic throughout the course of the conversation. This may be, at the very least in part, owing to the fact that we have a tendency to assume that our sensuality and our intellect are on opposite sides of a perfect dualism that is unlikely to exist. This, however, is unlikely to be the case. An emotionally meaningful worldview, the capacity to analyze, the ability to recognize values, and the ability to be led are all impacted by our emotionality, and it is precisely this emotionally meaningful worldview that plays a vital role in the process of generating logical judgements.

[An Integrative Manipulation Explained](#)

Before we get into that, let's take a quick look at the bigger conversation that surrounds manipulation and the many different ways that it may be described. This will help us better understand the new and more thorough approach of discussing manipulation. This explanation not only aims to avoid some of the challenges experienced by previous ideas of manipulation and our day-to-day usage of the word, but it also takes inspiration from prior philosophical explanations of the concept. These concepts were conceived using the theory of action and research in psychology as their primary sources of motivation. In addition, past philosophical definitions served as a source of motivation for developing this interpretation. As a result of this, manipulation will be construed as the intentional alteration of an agent's emotional states through the presentation of a particular objective (an activity, a product, etc.) as either enjoyable or unpleasant, which implies a recommendation regarding whether or not to favor it. This interpretation will have the effect of limiting the scope of manipulation. Nonetheless, this is crucial in circumstances in which the person who is the subject of the influence has some degree of freedom to choose whether

or not to act in the way that is expected of them. Some options become more desirable (even spectacularly, while others are not appealing at all), which, as a result, increases the likelihood that those options will be selected. This intentional (and sometimes not entirely conscious) curation of the emotional appeal of certain goals or the achievement of those goals makes some choices more desirable (while others are not appealing at all) (Fischer and Illies Citation2018, 27). The appraisal of a certain conclusion is subject to change as a consequence of the intentional manipulation of our mental states, which include our emotions, sentiments, and feelings. This results in very nuanced emotional experiences, the bulk of which can be simplified down to a desire or reluctance, yes or no, that drives us to act in a way that is compatible (or not consistent) with the goal of the manipulator.

This definition of manipulation may strike some of us as odd since it deviates significantly from the common understanding that the vast majority of us have about the idea of manipulation. Let's have a look at the many processes that were carried out in order to arrive at this proposed definition of the term, shall we?

Manipulation as Sneaky and Sneaky Deception

Since the act of misleading someone typically takes place below their level of awareness, covert manipulation and covert deception go hand in hand. If this weren't the case, it would be incredibly difficult to remove the deception after it has been introduced. Because of this, the concepts of manipulation as subtle and deceit as sly go hand in hand with one other. Nevertheless, these are two distinct characteristics that are frequently associated with the act of manipulation, despite the fact that it may at times be difficult to differentiate between the two. Manipulation can be defined as the process of influencing another person in order to achieve one's goals. It's possible to look at being clumsy as a helpful strategy that's utilized to conceal something (more or less craftily) and prevent it from being discovered. On the other side, deception is an attempt to produce an error in the perception of reality that a person has of a given situation without the subject being aware that the mistake has been created. It's possible to look at being clumsy as a helpful strategy that's utilized to conceal something (more or less craftily) and prevent it from being discovered. There are numerous different ways that one might cheat, including cheating.

As we can see, manipulation has a well-deserved reputation for the sneaky and dishonest qualities that many say it has. The evidence suggests that this view is correct. It is said to take place

surreptitiously, below the level of consciousness of the one who is being manipulated, misled into acting in a specific manner, without the subject being aware that they are being influenced in any way. Because of this, manipulation may sometimes be characterized as "recipients of which they are oblivious or inadequately aware, or unable to effectively manage their repercussions" (van Dijk Citation1998, 275; see also Goodin Citation1980, 9; fairly similar views e.g. Ware Citation1981, 165; Baron Citation2003, 37). On the other hand, this is not very helpful in providing an adequate description of the idea of manipulation. This is not only due to the fact that the word "manipulation" may be used to nearly any situation.

hiding a manipulation, such is what happened with Jones's wife in this instance. Ultimately, it seems that romantic relationships are a field for overt and obvious manipulation, which is something that should be avoided. This is something that should be avoided.

Any kind of dishonesty, including lying and selective sharing of information, has the potential to be an efficient strategy for influencing the opinion of another individual. Someone who deceives another individual in an effort to influence their thoughts and actions is engaging in manipulative conduct. But, it is not quite apparent what type of values are being addressed within the context of this sentence.

a person by telling them lies, using audiovisual illusions, or even providing them with just half of the information on a broader plan in order to deceive them. In spite of this, it is still feasible to discriminate between these two facets: In the case of manipulation, it may be constructed on a falsehood, which is then utilized to enhance a manipulation. Yet, in order to manipulate someone, it is not necessary for any falsehoods to be in play. While all of the propositions in the game may be true, they may still be utilized in a manner that is manipulative.

In other words, some agents strive to attain their self-serving aims (with bad repercussions for others who are influenced) by influencing other individuals. This understanding of the term "manipulation" is supported by the majority of definitions of the term "manipulation." This may take the shape of a single individual or a whole institution.

Neo-Marxist thinkers who were linked with the Frankfurt School put out the following statement in regard to capitalism:

Manipulation to deter people from rebelling against the unfair consequences of capitalism . This is accomplished by constantly manipulating the desire to buy and own property, for example, through advertisements (Marcuse Citation1969, 13).

Green and Pawlak (Citation 1983), Marcuse points to another direction already implied in his argument :

Manipulation is used by someone who is more skilled (or so we can say: has more resources) than the target, to exploit the weak and undermine their well-being. (35; see also Sunstein Citation2015, 433)

Without a shadow of a doubt, the behavior that defines manipulation is one that is planned with the intention of being destructive or selfish (as such, Marcia Baron Citation2003). The aforementioned occurrences demonstrate that it is an oversimplification to assert that all forms of manipulation are destructive and may only result in negative outcomes for the individual who participates in manipulative behavior for the purpose of furthering their own personal interests. The events demonstrate that it is possible for manipulative behavior to result in positive outcomes for the individual who engages in it in order to further their own personal interests. In the same line, one should not instantly presume that a manipulator is dishonest simply because they are manipulative. This is because being manipulative is not the same thing as being dishonest. Despite the fact that Tom is obviously a bit of a bully, it is made abundantly clear in the episode that is titled "Tom Sawyer" that Tom is not someone who participates in dishonest behavior in any way. This is despite the fact that Tom is named after Tom Sawyer.

The effects that may be achieved by manipulation are quite varied according to the amount of work that is put into it. It's possible that the same process that pushes individuals to participate in activities that are not in their best interests also leads them to engage in acts that are useful to them and even highly pleasurable for them to do. Consider the potato example once again; in some instances, manipulation may bring significant benefits to their goals and make it easier for individuals to maintain healthy lives. Consider the potato example once more. Consider the tale about the potato once again. On the other hand, it does not seem that the manipulator will

unquestionably profit from the current situation. Consider, as well, romantic relationships, in which one person strives to boost the well-being of the other in a manipulative way while offering no benefit to themselves in the process. This may be seen as a kind of codependent behavior. This viewpoint maintains that manipulation is not always a zero-sum game in which the one who emerges victorious keeps everything. As a result of this, a more detailed explanation could potentially engage both sides as follows: A manipulator who takes action that is presumed to be primarily praiseworthy, without the use of rational persuasion or coercion, is an example of a possible egoistic manipulator with selfish and possibly negative ends (which points us to possible ethical illegitimacy!). It's possible that a manipulator of this sort might engage in unethical activities. Because of the "paternalistic" impact that this argument is attempting to have on us, it is of utmost importance.

Dishonesty, deception, hostile purpose, or damage are not prerequisites for manipulation, as long as the manipulator is skilled enough. Those who are just concerned in themselves as a manipulator are not necessary either. The overwhelming bulk of criticism comes from a different point of view:

“ The claim that manipulation weakens our logic and therefore our autonomy ”

The part that lying to and manipulating others play in the process of making a person's thinking more corrupt. The concept of manipulation may be defined as "a sort of influence that disturbs or subverts the thinking abilities of the target," which is a widely accepted definition. On the other hand, this idea of manipulating others does not have universal appeal (Coons and Weber Citation2014, 11; Fischer Citation2017, 41). Since manipulation is in no way analogous to logical persuasion, the idea that it can circumvent logic, at least to some degree, appears to have a justification that may be accepted. This is because manipulation is in no way comparable to logical persuasion. It would seem that the primary means by which it communicates with us are those that are associated with the formation of our attitudes toward the natural world, or, to put it another way, our emotional states. In each and every one of these situations, the application of logical thinking is, at the very least, partially neglected. Yet, the more complete example of influencing the human mind seems to be something else, and it can be found in both *Othello* and *1984* by George Orwell. Both of these works were written in 1984.

Manipulation is essentially a kind of influence that does not need the intellectual talents of an actor, and this is something that can be asserted with the utmost certainty. This is only one of the numerous factors that contribute to the truth of this statement. This is a comment that needn't be made out of fear since it can be uttered. However, the foundation of many older ideas, which we are going to take a brief look at today, is the notion that our mind and affect are antagonistic to one another and are joined in a manner that is adversely related to one another. We are going to examine this notion in more detail in the following paragraphs. It is of the utmost importance, as was just said, that the manner in which we collaborate should be made more egalitarian. For instance, according to the definition provided by Noggle, manipulation is an activity in which the manipulator exerts influence on a target by manipulating the target's "psychological levers" in any one of the following three ways:

- (a) Deception to change beliefs;*
- (b) Changing conditioning or situational factors to change desires (Richard Thaler and Cass Sunstein suggested for poking); or*
- (c) The use of guilt or other emotions to alter the emotions of the person being manipulated.*

Although it is not entirely clear why education alone and ever-changing environmental factors influence our desires (for a critique of Noggle's explanation, see Manipulation, how an individual acquires beliefs, desires, and emotions—although these ideals are initially false—ideals Therefore, it can be called a non-ideal response due to the use of psychological leverage instead of rational negotiation. Manipulation causes the individual to lag ideals on how they should respond. Manipulation causes the individual

The concept that manipulation impairs our capacity for logical negotiation is still widely held, and there is much more that can be said about it. There is much more that can be said about idealized views of rational ideals and the absence of an adequate theory (rather than a simple binary view) of our emotional states, both of which have the potential to lead to a cartoonish view of manipulation. There is a great lot to be said about romanticized interpretations of logical goals and the lack of an appropriate account of our emotional states. Both topics need a great deal of discussion. It forces us to disregard the ways in which we use our own psychological strategies in attempt to sway the opinions of other individuals. Because of this, these explanations frequently

include a component that is descriptive (the affected individual does not eventually act on sound grounds because his rationality is somehow circumvented or even subverted), but there is also an inherent normative judgment embedded within them. This is a consequence of the fact that this.

From an ethical point of view, this article defends the position that manipulation "does not successfully engage or appeal to [agents'] capacity to make meaningful and deliberate decisions" (Sunstein Citation2015, 443; emphasis mine). The concept of "competence," which acts as a background for the conversation, is taken into consideration in order to arrive at this conclusion. Joseph Raz even goes so far as to claim that manipulation "distorts the way one makes judgments, creates preferences, or adopts objectives" (Raz Citation1988, 377; emphasis added); this not only identifies manipulation as being derogatory, but it also identifies manipulation as being unethically questionable.

It is very clear that manipulation is not the same thing as an argument that is logical, and it does not seem to work with the rationality of humans on a basic level. So, there is a potential that not only our independence, but also the sense of dignity that we have, might be put in jeopardy. To state the matter even another way,

To claim that any manipulation undermines logic seems a bit of an exaggeration. As Gorin (Citation2014a) explains, manipulation often seems to even depend on the reasoning abilities of the manipulated actor.

Even if there is at least some element of irrationality introduced through manipulation, this is still a valid point of view. But does this inevitably jeopardize our autonomy, that is, our ability to control how we behave and conduct ourselves?

Illies Citation2018 for any other information that you may want). On the other hand, we may say that a pre-rational impulse is tried to be activated by an actor when an agent is impacted in such a way that it causes the actor to try to activate the pre-rational impulse. This results in the actor finding a certain objective attractive, which, in turn, results in the agent basing their actions, rather than on logical reasoning, on their emotional responses to the target they are pursuing. It is not

essential, however, to reduce this fact to the level of an inanimate object that is unable to make its own judgments as a result of the circumstance. This is because the scenario is not like that at all. Even when experiencing these effects, an agent has the ability to make a decision that is both rational and free, and one of those options may be to deviate from the path that has been mapped out for them by an emotionally controlled state. As a direct consequence of this, the free agent is able to keep their strength.

[Especially in Liberal Societies](#)

By the way, this may be why using manipulation is particularly interesting in liberal societies:

“We still act on our own emotionality, typically being able to decide for or against it – which is an easy thing to do, though not always.”

As a direct result of this, the power of free agency is not diminished. The act of operating outside of our "rational radar" could push us in a certain direction, but it does not constitute a decision-making process that operates in a linear fashion. The act of manipulation might make it more difficult to form judgements that are rational. It's probable that each and every one of the characters in the cases approached the situation in a different manner than the other ones did. While there is a vast variety of methods in which influence might affect the logical reasoning of another person, it will virtually never completely corrupt that person's thinking. Instead of calling it manipulation, we should have referred to it as coercion in the event that this turned out to be the situation.

[A New Concept That Takes An Integrated Approach To Characterize Manipulation](#)

What is it that drives us to get things done? As a consequence of this, we are unable to simply assert that manipulation is a subversion of our rationality, our independence, or our autonomy. When we are in the role of the manipulator, however, we cannot simply characterize manipulation as lying or the use of damaging strategies in order to accomplish negative and self-serving goals. To do so would be an oversimplification. Instead, we need to come to terms with the fact that manipulation entails a great deal more. When an agent is influenced, the agent may give the appearance of making a choice that is (relatively) free; nevertheless, the broker does not make this decision based, for the most part, on a reasonable basis.

In a broader sense, we could argue that the introduction of a pre-rational influence into the decision-making process directly alters the emotional states that arise naturally with the evaluation of certain goals in the target. This is because the introduction of a pre-rational influence directly alters the emotional states that arise naturally with the evaluation of certain goals in the target. This is due to the fact that incorporating a pre-rational influence into the process of decision-making directly modifies the emotional states of the target. By carefully determining the emotional relevance of a goal, one may be able to elicit a response to manipulative effort from another. This might result in a desire or a reluctance to engage in or avoid a certain action, depending on the emotional value of the goal. This can also result in a want or a reluctance to avoid the activity. The sheer act of wishing something or actively hating something has as its purpose the alteration of reality so that it more closely fits those desires or aversions. This is true whether the desire or dislike is directed toward an internal or external object. A crucial component of a motivator is the individual's self, which may be manifested in a number of different ways (expectation, relaxation, impulses, libido, desires, goals, needs, etc.). It is not unheard of for our feelings to play a significant part in the formation of our thinking; hence, it is not unthinkable for us to realize that, as time passes, we have adopted other views. One of the three desired outcomes that drives us to take some type of action is the sense that accomplishing a goal would be joyful. This perception is one of the reasons why we take action. According to a contemporary interpretation of Aristotle and Aquinas, anything is considered an end when it is selected for the purpose of the item itself. These are the "ultimate" and "proper" objectives that affect an agent's life, such as the end of being vegan since nature and particularly animals are ends in themselves. One example of this is the end of being vegan (these goals have been the focus of the majority of ethical debates about autonomy). Another goal was selected because we believe it would be beneficial to our health and assist us in pursuing some of our other interests, including being vegan. As a consequence of this, we may present an aim (such as to acquire something or to gain control of the government) as being deserving of favor for the sake of favor itself. This is often accomplished by providing explanations as to why something is desirable; in doing so, we rationally convince another person that it is beneficial. reasons; rather, we could propose a conclusion that is just as helpful because it helps you achieve other goals that you already have. When it does occur, a vendor will offer a thing at a specific price, and we will have to decide whether or not to acquire the item at that price. Unfortunately,

this situation occurs all too often in the realm of economics (for example, better sound system or leather seats).

And last, we have the potential to create a pleasant and joyous finish, in addition to the ability to add new pleasures or to make specific goals that have already been defined more enticing, and as a consequence, more likely to be chosen. As we approach this stage, it becomes more interesting to find out how the process of manipulation really works. On the other hand, one might argue that any one of these tools is not only inappropriate but also unproductive and unpleasant to use. This would be a counterargument. As a result of this, there is the potential for both direct and indirect manipulation, as well as sporadic manipulation and systematic manipulation, respectively. Moreover, there is also the opportunity for occasional manipulation. Direct manipulation, for example, may be performed by directly producing guilt, obtaining an understanding of the vulnerable spots of the target, and so on. Other methods of direct manipulation include. This may be seen in the interpersonal interactions that we are able to manipulate via the use of It is helpful for the manipulator to be aware of what is being impacted in these situations. Indirect manipulation can take place, for instance, through advertising that slowly seeps into our subconscious mind by presenting a product in an appealing light and in a consistent manner over the course of time, or through specific choice architectures that exploit our tendency toward laziness, as an example. Indirect manipulation can also take place, for instance, through social engineering, which involves the use of social cues to influence behavior. Hypnosis is another kind of indirect manipulation that may be used in certain situations. This is quite important given that the majority of the online payment methods may be done with a single click of the mouse.

All of these efforts are made with the intention of convincing us to reevaluate a goal (an action, a product), motivating us to act in a certain way (for example, to go someplace or reject something), and finally changing the environment around us.

[A Revised Definition of Manipulation](#)

My working hypothesis for defining the process of manipulation is that a manipulative act is one that purposefully modifies the emotional states of an agent by presenting a certain result (an action, a product, etc.) in such a way that it is either gratifying or unpleasant to the agent. This is because a manipulative act is one that purposefully modifies the emotional states of an agent by presenting a certain result in such a way that it is either gratifying or unpleasant to the agent. To get the most

realistic picture possible of the process of modification, we believe that discussing it in this way is the best way to go about it. This involves instruction to select or not choose that objective, but it is vital when the person being controlled is free to act or not act in that way, at least in a fundamental sense. This is because the person being controlled has the ability to choose whether or not to behave in that manner. Those who are being controlled will find that some options become more tempting (even excessively so), but others will not be appealing at all; as a consequence, such options will have a greater chance of being selected. This is due to the fact that the deliberate (but often not entirely conscious) curation of the emotional attractiveness of certain aims or the accomplishment of those goals makes some possibilities more enticing than others.

The evaluation of a particular objective shifts in accordance with the degree to which our emotional states (emotions, feelings, and moods) are actively regulated. This frequently—though not always—leads to emotionally complicated experiences, which, in turn, often result in emotionally complicated consequences. This provides the individual who is being influenced with the incentive to act in a way that is congruent with the objectives of the person who is influencing them. We are able to arrive at a neutral and integrative explanation of manipulation if we define it in this manner because it makes room for many of the components that have been identified and, as a result, the usage of the word manipulation in common language. If we define it in this manner, we are able to get to an explanation of manipulation that is neutral and integrative (Wood also begs for an unbiased explanation, 2014, 19).

Sneaky and Sneaky and/or Deceptive Ways

While it is not essential to do this calculation, methods that are deceptive, underhanded, or dishonest have the potential to cause chaos, develop manipulators who are self-centered, and damage reasoning. By adopting this more specific definition of manipulation, we have positioned manipulation on the map of influence. We have differentiated it from other forms of persuasion, such as logical argument and compulsion, by carrying out this action instead. In addition, this definition prevents us from falling into an unduly simplistic and romanticized mind-sentimental dichotomy. Moreover, it maintains a clear distinction between the concepts of manipulation and demonology. By building on the concepts introduced by Baron's (Citation2014) predecessors, this explanation of manipulation makes the instances of Noggle and Barnhill more difficult to grasp. These concepts include the beliefs that manipulation is based on playing on people's emotions,

using coercion to get others to submit (which is not yet coercion), or taking advantage of character flaws.

In addition to Marcuse's use of his discovery that manipulation is successful because it works by meticulously stimulating libidinal urges, guilt is also a factor in the theory that Marcuse developed. This was made clear by the explanation that came before it, each of these scenarios is, in point of fact, a substantial kind of manipulation. This was made clear by the explanation that came before it. When an offender is exposed to manipulation, this concept may explain why he is not robbed of his right to choose:

“Making the ending pleasant can make a decision against it unpleasant and troublesome, but no one is forced into a particular decision.”

When an offender is exposed to manipulation, this concept may explain why he or she does not lose their freedom of choice in such situation. Take, for example, advertising that are created with the intention of appealing to a large number of people. It's conceivable that certain agents are more prone to being hurt, and as a result, they have a higher chance of delivering on the promise of happiness and pleasure. On the other hand, some agents could not be receptive to anything at all, and they might pay no attention at all to the manipulative power that an advertising has. There is also the possibility that Tom's efforts to convince someone else resulted in a response from Ben that was different from what was expected. Here is yet another alternative. The previous point is applicable in the same way to the circumstances that are discussed further below. A selection may be influenced by a manipulation, but it does not mean that the manipulation is the only factor behind the selection itself. In addition, by adopting this strategy, it turns out to be extremely clear why one cannot simply equate manipulating others with being dishonest. This is owing to the fact that a person is able to modify the emotional attractiveness of goals in a variety of different ways without being dishonest (although dishonesty is there, and in some situations it even benefits the manipulator's purpose). It is also incredibly important to point out that manipulation is not the only kind of dishonesty; rational arguments may also be deceitful. This is an extremely important point to make since it is extremely crucial. This is something that need to be stressed with a great deal of force.

With the production of this body of work, we have made progress toward our goal of describing what happens when we try to impose our will on one another by making use of the concepts of action and emotion. In the end, it's not a matter of better grasping an idiom or reality that we've been exposed to on such a regular basis. Instead, the problem that has to be addressed is one that is more systemic in nature. By clinging to a pessimistic and even caricatured perspective of manipulation (that is, viewing it as fundamentally dishonest, undetectable, coercive, damaging, and executed by bad minds), we are probably making it easier for ourselves to miss the manner in which we participate in the larger phenomenon. To phrase it another way, we are "complicit" in the crime that was committed.

What Makes Us Not to Realize Our Capacity to Influence People Through Our Emotional States? Are we too attached to a rigid dichotomy between rationality and affect, and perhaps reluctant to consider the complex and dynamic ways in which they interact and interact with each other – because this can be confusing (and difficult to conceptualize)?

If so, this raises the question of whether we are overly invested in a rigid dichotomy between rationality and affect.

A broader and more nuanced perspective of manipulation be an indication of our interest in outdated and exaggerated ideas of reason and autonomy?

And/or an attempt to avoid addressing the significant part that dishonesty plays in the current political system, our personal relationships, and our professional environments? Not only in terms of how exactly it works, but also in terms of the role that it plays in our lives, this fascinating phenomenon raises a great deal of questions that have not yet been satisfactorily answered. This is true both in terms of how exactly it works, as well as the role that it plays in our lives.

[An Example of a Persistent Phenomenon](#)

The phenomenon of manipulation is prevalent, and it poses substantial problems not just during the ad bellum phase of conflict, but also throughout the bello phase. This problem is inherent to conflict and is one of the distinguishing features associated with it. Let's start out by thinking about the ad bellum phase of the conflict. If these wars are going to have any chance of success at all,

there needs to be sufficient support from the people who will have to bear the many costs that are associated with them, as well as from the soldiers who will be fighting in the battles themselves. Only then will these conflicts have any chance of being successful. Because of this, governments will sometimes do whatever in their power to keep the true objectives of a war a secret. This is especially the case if those objectives are made public and it becomes hard to garner support for the conflict being fought. For instance, wars that are actually aimed at gaining financial or strategic advantages can be justified by the need to neutralize existential threats or protect values such as freedom, democracy, or human rights. This is because the need to protect these values or neutralize existential threats is a fundamental human motivation. All of these are instances of ideals that may be put in jeopardy if existential dangers are not eliminated. These conflicts are displayed in a way that justifies their validity since they are shown in a way that explains the requirement to acquire financial or strategic advantages. Because this is the case, the depiction of these conflicts is legitimate. In addition, regardless of the goals that have been publicly stated, governments throughout history have used a wide variety of distinct types of propaganda in an effort to sway the opinions, sentiments, and allegiances of their populations in an effort to garner support for their military operations. This has been done in an effort to garner support for their military endeavors.

During the covert phase of the fight, strategies like as espionage, the deliberate insertion of false information, fake assaults or retreats, the transmission of misleading radio signals, and counterfeit installations were employed to panic the other side and incite reckless attacks. Yet, the capacity to resort to manipulative strategies is limited to activities that do not cross the line into wholly dishonest conduct. This restricts the scope of possible manipulative tactics. It is against the laws of war to behave as if one is about to surrender or make inappropriate use of the protections that are allowed to medical experts in order to gain an advantage over the enemy. This includes acting as if one is ready to give up when one is not, for example. It is not always clear what exactly constitutes treason, but it is generally accepted that there is a boundary, and it is imperative that this line be respected. One possible definition of treason is an act of shameful conduct committed against one's nation (Ripstein 2020). Remarkably little consideration, however, has been given to the problem of manipulation by philosophers exploring the ethics of war and, more generally, of harm. This lack of attention has been surprising.

Even though it is common knowledge that being a victim of manipulation can serve as an alibi for fabricating an unwarranted threat and, as a result, evading one's responsibilities, there is no in-depth discussion in the research literature about exactly why and how manipulation is justified, nor is there any discussion at all about the distinction between the two. In addition, there is no discussion at all about the difference between the two. In addition, there is no mention of the differences between the two in the conversation.

By investigating the topic of how the manipulation of the wrongful threat (or a component to the wrongful threat) influences culpability for defensive harm, this research will help fill a gap in the existing body of knowledge. This research will also help fill a gap in the existing body of knowledge. In the following paragraphs, we are going to take a direct approach to addressing this problem.

In contrast to the substantial body of work that philosophers have produced on the subject of compulsion, the field of philosophical writing has paid very little attention to the topic of manipulation. This lack of attention can be contrasted with the substantial body of work that philosophers have produced on the subject of manipulation. Because of this, our understanding of what manipulation is and the reasons why it is unethical to influence other people (in circumstances in which it is immoral to do so) is rather limited. This is a direct result of the scenario. The fact that philosophers have written extensively on the issue of compulsion despite the fact that the topic of manipulation has gained relatively little attention in the philosophical literature is one of the obstacles that comes when seeking to find a solution to this subject's problem. It would seem that the ethical ramifications of manipulation cannot be summed up in a single point, which adds another layer of complexity to the situation. Instead, as the examples that came before it helped to indicate, manipulation may take on a variety of forms. This can be seen in the instances that came before them. Take into account the three options listed below:

Use of human shields; brainwashing and conscription of young soldiers ; and the use of misleading methods, such as deliberately giving false information, to induce the enemy to react in certain ways. These two scenarios cannot be more different from a structural point of view.

The first strategy is to exert influence on the surroundings around the person being manipulated in such a way that they discover new reasons for behaving in the ways that the manipulator wants them to perform. For instance, placing individuals in front of troops that are shooting at their enemies might provide the opponent with new explanations for why they should not reply to the fire. This is because the adversary is aware that responding to the fire could result in damage to the civilians (Fabre 2012, 256–267; Haque 2017, chapter 9). In the second scenario, the manipulator, rather than acting in accordance with the circumstances, acts in accordance with the goals and values of the person who is being manipulated. This is in contrast to the first scenario, in which the manipulator acts in accordance with the circumstances. The first scenario, in which the manipulator behaved in a way that was appropriate given the circumstances, stands in stark contrast to this one. The second scenario is differentiated from the first in this specific respect about the circumstance. When a child soldier is brainwashed into believing that members of a particular minority lack the kind of moral worth that creates deontological restraints against harm, he is encouraged to act as the manipulator wishes because he has somehow been instilled in him with certain values or goals. For example, when a child soldier is brainwashed into believing that members of a particular minority lack the kind of moral worth that creates deontological restraints against harm. This is due to the fact that the manipulator has, in some fashion or another, inculcated these principles or aims into him.

The last kind of situation is one in which the manipulator does not interfere with either the setting in which the child soldier is being influenced or the child soldier himself. These kinds of situations fall under the category of "no intervention." This sort of situation belongs in the third group of possible outcomes. This objective may be accomplished by one of two different strategies. To begin, the person who is influencing the other individual may be able to persuade the one who is being influenced to believe something that isn't true. For instance, the manipulator may convince the target that a certain location does not have a high population density, or that a specific building is more of a military factory than a hospital. These are just two examples of how the manipulator might mislead the target. Conversely, the manipulator may be the one who leads the individual who is being misled to act in a way that violates ethical standards. For instance, the person who is manipulating another may be led to believe, by the manipulator, that punitive torture is compatible with the moral goals and values that should guide the behavior of the person who is being manipulated. This is a false belief that the person being manipulated should have.

Same Research Method

Since that there seems to be a substantial difference between them, we shouldn't automatically assume that we'll be able to solve each of them by using the same kind of studying approach. In the sake of our study, we will focus our attention just on the cases that can be categorized into the third category.

When trying to give an explanation of how manipulation influences the defensive obligation to inflict injury, the following creates a conundrum:

So why do you think his legal liability will be different in each of these cases?

Naturally, the level to which we know the components that make up the idea of responsibility for defensive injuries will determine the way in which we respond to this topic. This is because our reactions will be determined by how well we understand these components. For the rest of this discussion, we are going to focus our attention on the concept that the basis of a criminal offense is the moral duty of creating an unjustified threat to another individual. I do this not because I believe that this idea provides a comprehensive response to the question of justification for responsibility - it is reasonable that responsibility is determined by other considerations - but rather because it is recognized as a central component of justification for responsibility, and it is important even by those who deny that it is the only component. Those who deny that it is the only component acknowledge that it is important. We do this not because I think that this idea provides a comprehensive solution to the question of why individuals should be accountable for the activities that they choose, but rather because it is chosen by other reasons (McMahan 2009; Otsuka 1994; Tadros 2020b).

Responsibility

While doing research on the topic, it seems only logical to start here given the general acceptance of his point of view. Now, at least some of those who acknowledge that responsibility is dependent on responsibility would be inclined to conclude that guilt, complicity, or attempting to pose a threat and failing to do so are all influenced by manipulation. This is the case even if they acknowledge that responsibility is dependent on responsibility. This is the case regardless of whether or not they accept the premise that accountability is contingent upon responsibility. However, in order to

provide a complete explanation of how manipulation affects responsibility, it will be necessary to take into account the ways in which these and other possible bases for liability (such as the attempt to establish a threat but its failure) are impacted by manipulation. This will be necessary in order to provide a comprehensive explanation of how manipulation affects responsibility. Ethical responsibility and causal responsibility are not the same thing; we are only ethically liable for anything if it is the direct outcome of how we exercise our free will and take autonomous action. Ethical responsibility is not the same thing as causal responsibility. On the other hand, we often see manipulation as something that prevents us from functioning as autonomous agents and, as a result, decreases the degree of responsibility that we are able to assume for ourselves. When we are created into who we are as a result of being influenced, there is a substantial sensation that our existence cannot be correctly assigned to us. This is because when we are made into who we are as a result of being influenced, we are made into someone else. Because of this emotion, we are unable to accept responsibility for our own existence. This is because "we" are the ones engaging in the manipulative behavior here. In addition to this, if it is unable to be shown that we are responsible for it, then it is permissible to make the conclusion that we do not have any ethical responsibility for it. This is because it cannot be established that we are accountable for it.

Moral Responsibility

If we accept the premise that moral responsibility is the foundation on which it is formed, then we may infer that guilt is lessened when responsibility is compromised. This is because moral responsibility is the basis on which it is constructed. This is since moral responsibility serves as the basis upon which it is constructed. This tactic seems to have some potential for success in the real world when seen from the outset, which is a very positive sign. One such example is the fact that a significant proportion of people can think deeply and give careful consideration to the question of what the next logical step should be. But, if he keeps using the "psychological levers" (Noggle 1996), he will not be able to come to his own conclusion on what to do, and as a consequence, he will not be able to act "for himself" (Herman 1993). If we were to follow Korsgaard's line of reasoning, we would reach the conclusion that Bianca "cannot 'incorporate' the consequence of the same action since she is not in her circumstance." This would be the case if we adopted Korsgaard's way of thinking. If we were to adopt Korsgaard's way of thinking, we would reach this conclusion.

He cannot make the claim that the action is his because he does not know what the true purpose of the action is; more specifically, he cannot freely choose to contribute to the accomplishment of his goals because he does not know what the true purpose of the action is. Because he does not know what the true purpose of the action is, he cannot claim ownership of the action. Korsgard 1996). The difficulty with this method is that it is not clear in what sense Bianca's causes are not "her own," or in what sense they are not "wholly" the source of them. This makes it difficult to determine whether Bianca is responsible for these causes. Because of this, it is hard to say for certain whether this procedure should be used. Determining whether this approach is effective is a difficult endeavor as a result of the aforementioned reasons. We are never "completely" in the center of the forces that are the driving force behind the actions that we decide to do. This is correct to a certain extent.

When we are presented with the components of the world in their natural condition, we have a response to those components. It's not often that life throws us a curveball and forces us to make a snap decision on what to do next. The reasons why we should do so are dependent, not only on the circumstances in which we find ourselves at this time, but also on our comprehension of the situations that we find ourselves in. When we decide to act as a result of being manipulated, we are not "acting for our own reasons" in the sense that acting is not what we would do if we had a better understanding of the circumstances we were in when we made the decision to act. This is because acting is not what we would do if we had a better understanding of the circumstances we were in when we made the decision to act. Instead, when we decide to act, it is because we have been persuaded into doing so by someone or something else. There is, of course, a second meaning that we may give to the term "we do not act for our own purposes." This is the problem that keeps replaying in our thoughts whenever we examine the numerous different courses of action that we may choose. Even in circumstances in which we were not influenced in any way, our conduct would have often departed from what it is now if the evidence that we had been presented with had been of a greater quality. (For instance, if he had more information that Bianca was innocent, we may conclude that he would avoid murdering Clint in Bombay. Yet, it is plausible that the same assumption applies to Bomb II and Bomb III.) Sarah Buss (2005) offers a very compelling argument for this line of reasoning. It is an error, according to Buss's line of reasoning, to suppose that our free will and autonomous agency are in jeopardy when we are exposed to some type of manipulation simply due to the fact that our actions cannot be traced back to us. This assumption

is based on the mistaken assumption that our actions cannot be attributed to us. This is due to the fact that no one can attribute our acts to ourselves. After all, we would respond in the same way to the data that was provided to us, even if natural events were the initial trigger for our response. This is because our responses are conditioned by our experiences. (For more reading, see out Yaffe 2003). In light of these observations, it appears reasonable to draw the conclusion that the concept that manipulation reduces guilt needs to be rejected. This seems like a reasonable conclusion to reach since it seems realistic. In the event that the manipulation does not prevent us from acting in the way of a free actor, then our actions may be ascribed to us. In the alternative, our actions may not be attributed to us. And if responsibility is what gives birth to responsibility, it would appear that we are forced to come to the conclusion that even if we are tempted to behave in this manner, we are accountable for incurring the accompanying consequences. This would appear to be the conclusion that we are forced to come to because it would appear that we are forced to come to it because responsibility is what gives birth to responsibility. If it is true that responsibility is what gives birth to responsibility, then this would be the case. On the other hand, it is difficult to make peace with the fact that this conclusion occurred. We suggest that this is not a need of the utmost importance. However, we will acknowledge that both our responsibility and our ability to use our autonomous agency is unaffected by manipulation, and that our ability to use our autonomous agency is what determines whether or not manipulation has an effect on our responsibility. I will defend the view that manipulation does, in fact, have an effect on responsibility; however, we will acknowledge that both our responsibility and our ability to use our autonomous agency is unaffected by manipulation. I will argue that manipulation does have an impact on responsibility, but we will also acknowledge that our obligation is based on our ability to make use of our own agency. I will argue that manipulation does have an effect on accountability. In addition, while we develop this argument, we are not going to abandon the assumption that the responsibility to issue unjustified threats (among other things) is the basis of defensive injury liability.

On the other side, there will be circumstances in which just the manipulator will suffer defensive damage, while the manipulators themselves will remain unscathed. There are going to be situations in which the only person who can suffer defensive injury is the manipulator, but the degree to which an individual may avoid blame will alter depending on a wide range of various elements.

Prevention Policy

Manipulating someone is interfering with their ability to respond logically and appropriately to arguments, which is an example of manipulating that individual. Since we are rational agents, we have the potential to recognize some aspects of the world as substantial reasons for taking action, and we are able to do so because of this capacity. As a result of possessing this ability, we are able to invest the world that we inhabit with significance. The psychological mechanisms that enable us to react to the variables that are creating these effects are disturbed whenever any of these two ways in which we might be affected have an impact on us. Either we are strongly encouraged to abstain from doing something that we should have done, or we are instructed to do the exact opposite of what we should have done (for example, you can use my insecurity to encourage me to do so). Either we are unconsciously forced to do what we have reason to do for the wrong reasons, in which case we actively fight against anti-discrimination legislation in the workplace, or we are deliberately pushed to do what we have cause to do for the right reasons. One of two psychological processes, both of which enable us to respond correctly to a variety of stimuli, may be hindered when we are exposed to manipulation:

What about us (you can persuade me to support anti-discrimination policies, but only because my boss will be positively impacted).

It is crucial to note that the reasons we have for conceiving specific ideas and holding certain opinions frequently function as a mediator between the reasons we have for participating in particular activities. This is something that we must take into consideration. In most cases, we form our intention because we feel we have reasons to do so or because we think it is vital to do so in light of certain attitudes that we have, such as certain wants or emotions that we have. To put it another way, we establish our intentions on the basis of our perception that we have good grounds to carry them out. On the other hand, we can decide to carry through with our goal because we are under the assumption that we have sufficient justification for doing so. Manipulation is the process of interfering with our capacity to react to the reasons for action that we have chosen, thereby weakening our ability to respond differently to our ideas and attitudes. This process is referred to as "interfering with our capacity to react to the reasons for action that we have chosen."

After all, we can guarantee that you will not act on the reasons for action that are relevant to you by completely removing the capacity for you to use your judgment in decision-making. Because of this, we are able to ensure that you will not act on the many motives for action that are relevant to you. They could become drunk or hit you in the head. You shouldn't risk it. The manipulation includes this process as one of its steps. None of these samples include even a single example of any kind of alteration whatsoever. Learning how to distinguish between the things that should inspire you and the ones that really do thrill you by utilizing your own logical capacity is an essential component of manipulation. The practice of social engineering has been compared as a kind of manipulation.

It is ultimately up to you to decide whether or not you should oppose the anti-discrimination measures, despite the fact that you have been led to adopt this choice through deceptive innuendo and justification (which I have produced specifically to guide you), despite the fact that you have been led to adopt this choice. Despite the fact that you have been led to adopt this choice, it is ultimately up to you to decide whether or not you should oppose the anti-discrimination measures.

When the manipulator makes use of the manipulated person's own logical faculties, that person's capacity to undermine the manipulator's ability to undermine the manipulated person's ability to employ their own practical mediation is undermined. The manipulator's ability to undermine the manipulated person's ability to employ their own practical mediation is undermined. When we use our practical tool, our goal should be to act in ways that make sense to us, and ideally, we should act for reasons that make the most sense. This should be our standard for how we conduct ourselves while using our practical tool. When we utilize this tool, this should always be the major focus of our attention. The manipulator will purposely mislead us as to what these reasons are, making it so that the more we strive to respond to the things we have reason to do, the more ineffective we will be in doing so. This idea can be explained in a variety of different ways, one of which is by having the manipulator purposefully present to his victim reasons for action that appear to be incompatible with the real reasons. Another way to explain this concept is by having the manipulator present to his victim reasons for action that appear to be incompatible with the real reasons (Parfit 2011, 111). This leads one to the idea that the victim is doing it on purpose in order to establish an apparent belief or viewpoint. To misalign one's incentives for action with their real reasons is yet another way to explain this dilemma. Another way to put it is that. As a consequence

of this, Bianca engages in behavior that is incongruent with the goals she has consciously set for herself.

Deceptive Manipulation

Deceptive manipulation of B happens when A uses deception to purposefully interfere with B's ability to bargain (as described above), and in this scenario, A is the manipulator. Deception is used to purposefully interfere with B's capacity to negotiate. Because of this interference, B is unable to act on his motivations for action in any of the following ways, depending on the context:

When A uses dishonesty with the intention of purposefully hindering B's ability for negotiation, B is subjected to A's deceptive manipulation, which is a kind of deceptive manipulation known as "deceptive manipulation." B has a legitimate motive for doing something, but since A is involved, B is forced into doing it for the wrong reasons on purpose and is thus pressured into doing it. Two different explanations are required, namely:

I would assume that the mismatch between the victim's real motives for action and their apparent motives is the result of manipulation only if the intervention was deliberate . When this is not the case, we are not victims of manipulation , even if we are led astray, even if another's actions lead us astray . For our purposes, we can focus here on cases of manipulation that involve deliberately causing someone to do something they have reasons not to do (item a) (item b).

This is due to the fact that defensive injury responsibility often comes into play whenever a person engages in behavior for which they have valid reasons not to, such as making an unlawful threat in this particular instance. In other words, when a person engages in behavior for which they have valid reasons not to, defensive injury responsibility often comes into play.

Even if A had done nothing else wrong to B, the fact that he was prevented from giving a meaningful response to the grounds for his behavior would be enough to constitute a breach of B's rights. This is because B's rights include the ability to give a meaningful response to the grounds for his behavior. On the other hand, the fact that B breaks a key commitment by not doing so makes the mistake much more severe than it otherwise would have been. Given the presence of this fact, the question of who should be responsible for paying the expenses involved in avoiding a violation of this commitment or, at the very least, mitigating the consequences of such a breach, is raised.

There is a participation on A's part in B's failure, and because A is morally liable for acting in that way, A accepts a secondary responsibility to pay the expenditures of B's failure. The rationale for this is that there is a participation on A's part in B's failure. This is because interference from A was the primary factor that led to the failure of B. (Raz 2011; Gardner 2018; Tadros 2020a). This is because the Preventative Principle is linked to the obligation of engaging in acts of self-defense, which explains why it has this effect.

It is A's obligation, in accordance with the Pre-Purchase Principle, to bear the eligible expenditures associated with A's manipulation. It is not A's responsibility to cover any charges that may be related with A's manipulation. The costs that are relevant are those for which it would be absurd to impose on him any method that would raise these costs considering B's reaction to perceived motives for action. The costs that are relevant are those for which it would be absurd to impose on him any method that would raise these costs. In other words, the expenses that matter are those for which it would be illogical to raise these prices in any manner. Increasing these costs in any way would be unjustifiable. Expenses that are connected to how B decides to react to these reasons are costs that are incurred by B and that are not unreasonable to be expended. These are the costs involved. The extreme view that emotional manipulation destroys our moral responsibility by preventing us from acting as autonomous agents is therefore incompatible with the Priority Principle, as it removes the option to act as an independent agent; On the other hand, emotional manipulation is self-serving and potentially harmful, reflecting the use of emotional intelligence for purposes other than those that are beneficial to society. (Berkovich & Eyal , 2017) (e.g., Austin, Saklofske , Smith & Tohver , 2014). In a study that was conducted out by O'Boyle, Humphrey, Pollack, and Story, the researchers concluded that emotional intelligence is a valid predictor of increased job performance (2011). Individuals who have a higher emotional intelligence, for example, have a better ability to cope with the strains and tensions that are associated with their respective jobs (Gooty , Gavin , Ashkanasy , & Thomas, 2014). On the other hand, there is a dearth of research that investigates whether people who are more emotionally intelligent make use of their talents in a manner that is detrimental to the well-being of others while they are working, such as by provoking or vexing other people. This is a gaping hole in our knowledge. humiliated The value of pondering this less desirable characteristic cannot be stressed, and it cannot be ignored either. One of every three workers in Australia reports that high levels of stress are brought on by issues that occur at their place of employment (Australian Psychological Society , 2015).

One in three people working in the United States report having to deal with chronic stress on the job, and one in four of those people believe that the conduct of their superiors and coworkers are to blame for this stress (American Psychological Association and Harris Interactive, 2016). Research on harmful behaviors in the workplace has received a large amount of attention in recent years (see Schilpzand , De Pater & Erez, 2014 for an overview). Throughout the course of our study, we came across many examples of behavioral patterns that have the potential to be categorized as emotional disturbances (EM). "making derogatory comments" and "insulting people" are two examples of items that may be found on the Workplace Rudeness Scale, which is used rather often. For instance, "making derogatory comments" and "insulting people" (Cortina , Magley , Williams, & Langhout , 2001). These two factors are drawn from a scale that determines how rude an employee is in the workplace.

Hence, doing study on the nature of EM in the workplace may be helpful in the development of sensitive methods for conflict management that may take into account people who have characteristics of dishonest personality. It has recently come to light that the preliminary empirical evidence provides support for the employees' perspectives about the frequency of manipulative tactics in the workplace. This has been shown to be the case via several studies (Berkovich and Eyal , 2017). A questionnaire was sent to the teaching staff as part of this research project in order to ascertain the extent to which their school administrators were susceptible to being influenced. The idea that instructors are negatively influenced is held by those teachers who also report having larger degrees of negative effect. This perspective is shared by those teachers who have experienced greater degrees of negative effect.

Individuals who can exert influence over others genuinely engage in emotional manipulation (Hyde & Grieve, 2014), which may be the result of their conformity (O'Connor & Athota, 2013) or their ethical values (Grieve & Mahar, 2010). This is only one of the factors that goes towards creating the overall impression that the outcome of this situation is impossible to forecast. Because of this, Hyde and Grieve (2014) enhanced the factors that Austin et al. (2007) provided in order to discern between an individual's desire to manipulate and their actual capability to do so. They were able to distinguish between a person's capability of exerting influence and their desire to do so because of this. The willingness paradigm, which consists of asking individuals for their own self-reports on a certain ability, is one way that these limitations might be sidestepped (Hyde & Grieve

, 2014). On the other hand, the existing willingness variables do not take the conditions into mind in any way.

This test makes use of medications that already exist, and its goal is to evaluate whether a person has a predisposition to exercise influence over the individuals in their personal and professional lives by using such substances (Hyde & Grieve , 2014). One way to acquire an insight of the degree to which a behavior is maintained across a range of situations is to do a component analysis on the items. This may be done in several different ways. If everything can be traced back to a single cause, then we may assume that a person's purpose to manipulate is unaffected by the conditions that are surrounding the event. If everything can be traced back to a single cause, then everything can be traced back to a single cause. This is the kind of behavior that will be seen when many things are subjected to the same factor. On the other hand, if the items are divided into two categories, such as work and life in general, one might come to the conclusion that the subject's behavior is influenced by the environment in which they are placed. This could be the case if the categories are divided into work and life in general. Since the nature of our goal was to investigate uncharted territory, we were not tasked with developing any precise theories or making any predictions. After the completion of an exploratory factor analysis to discover the factor structure of the Featured EM General and Job Willingness scale, a confirmatory factor analysis was carried out in order to investigate the factor structure of that scale (EFA). This was the second goal that the research attempted to achieve via its findings (DFA). As it has been shown in the past that EM may vary depending on the gender of the patient (for example, Grieve and Panebianco, 2013), separate DFAs were run on men and women. This was done since it has been proven that EM may fluctuate depending on the gender of the patient. This was done because to the fact that it has been shown that EM might differ from patient to patient depending on their gender. Since this is an exploratory research project, a hypothesis was never developed at any point throughout the process because there was no need for one. It is possible to acquire a judgment about the character of a person based just on the fact that they have been accused of being manipulative. When you allege that you have been manipulated in some way, you are basically saying the same thing as when you complain that you have been mistreated in some way. To manipulate other people is unethical at the very least, and completely immoral at the greatest possible level of severity. *So what exactly triggers it? Where precisely does the difficulty come from when it comes to manipulation? People impact one another and are influenced by one another at all times and in a variety of contexts and*

ways. What distinguishes manipulation from other methods of persuasion, and what are the characteristics of manipulation that make it an immoral practice? We are continuously the focus of a variety of different attempts to manipulate us. The following are only a few illustrations:.

When someone is being manipulated, the goal is to convince them to care so much about the manipulator's approval that they will do anything the manipulator wants them to do in order to get that acceptance. This may be accomplished by employing techniques such as seductive assaults and peer pressure. People who are induced to experience guilt trips are those who are made to feel exceedingly guilty for not complying with the demands that the manipulator has set. Convincing a person that they should not trust their own judgment and instead depend on the advice offered by the manipulator is an example of the manipulative technique known as gaslighting. gaslighting is a sort of manipulation.

Phishing and other scams can mislead their victims by employing a combination of deception (which can range from outright lying to fake phone numbers or Websites) and playing on the victims' emotions, such as greed, fear, or pity. For example, a phisher may pose as a charity organization and ask for donations in exchange for a chance to win a prize. Then there is the more direct manipulation, of which Iago's manipulation of Othello to build suspicion about Desdemona's adultery, manipulation of Othello's vulnerabilities to make Desdemona jealous, and turning Othello into a jealous man is arguably the most famous example.

It is likely that influencing other people is unethical due to the fact that it often entails the adoption of strategies that are essentially dishonest in the way they treat other people. It is possible that people who are particularly interested in Immanuel Kant's theory that morality requires that we respect each other as rational beings rather than objects will find this way of thinking to be particularly appealing. This is because Kant believed that morality required that we respect each other as rational beings rather than as objects.

[Difference Between Manipulative Effect and Non-Manipulative Effect](#)

The question of whether or not the person exerting influence is attempting to convince the person they are attempting to influence to make some kind of error in what they believe, feel, doubt, or pay for is what differentiates manipulative influence from non-manipulative influence. Non-manipulative influence does not involve the person attempting to convince the person they are attempting to influence to believe, feel, doubt, or pay for something that is false. It is a

characteristic of the human condition that, in addition to the use of logical reasoning, people have the capacity to influence one another in a number of different ways. This ability is a trait of the human condition. Sometimes the other person's decision-making is improved by these influences because they lead him to believe, doubt, feel, or pay attention to appropriate things; other times, his decision-making is made worse because it leads him to believe, doubt, feel, or pay attention to inappropriate things. This is because these influences lead him to believe, doubt, feel, or pay attention to inappropriate things. Depending on the circumstances, the influence of these factors may either have a favorable or bad effect on the decisions that are made. Yet, manipulation requires the deliberate application of such elements in a way that impedes the capacity of a person to make the optimal option for themselves. This is the essence of the immorality that lies at the core of the idea that manipulation may be used to achieve one's ends. The way in which we conceive about manipulation might perhaps give some insight into how to spot its existence in a situation. The fallacy that manipulation is only an additional kind of persuasion is very simple to fall victim to since it is so prevalent. On the other hand, as we have seen, the effects that may be used to control something can also be utilized in a way that does not entail manipulation. This is something that can be done with the same kinds of effects.

It does not matter what kind of influence is utilized to exert control over another person; what matters is whether the effect is used to put the other person in a stronger or weaker position to make a choice. To recognizing manipulation, having this knowledge is very necessary. So, before we can define manipulation, we need to focus not on the method of action but rather on the motivations of the person who is deploying it. This is because the method of action is not the primary focus of manipulation. This is since the action alone is insufficient to define manipulation on its own. As the major objective of influencing another person is to lessen that person's ability to make decisions, which is also the fundamental unethical act of manipulation, we may argue that the primary objective of manipulation is immorality. Because of this, we can make the argument that the core of manipulation is immorality. Machiavellianism is a personality trait that is characterized by emotional disconnection, cynicism, and a manipulative interpersonal style (Christie & Geis, 1970). According to Ináncsi, Láng, and Bereczkei (2015), men and women who have high levels of Machiavellianism seek closeness from other people. This is true for both men and women. An emotional separation, cynicism, and a manipulative interpersonal approach are the defining characteristics of Machiavellianism. The Machiavellian worldview is distinguished by

several characteristics, one of which is a gloomy outlook on life. These persons exhibit poor levels of empathy, are not connected with either their own feelings or the emotions of other people and portray other people in a bad light (Black, Woodworth, & Porter, 2013; Ináncsi et al., 2015; Wai & Tiliopoulos), 2012; Wastell & Booth, 2003). Any of these traits may make it simpler for some individuals to control the behavior of others. As Machiavellianism has an impact on a variety of adult relationships, and since friendship is the most common kind of social connection (Blieszter & Adams, 1992), it is crucial to explore Machiavellianism in the context of friendship. Friendship is something that Machiavellian people do, but the quality of their friendships is often quite low because of their Machiavellian inclinations. This is true of both men and women who are Machiavellian (Abell , Lyons & Brewer , 2014; Aitken & Lyons , 2010).

This should not come as a surprise since Machiavellianism is characterized by a high degree of skepticism, cynicism, and emotional detachment; thus, this should be expected. According to the findings of other studies, those who have considerable Machiavellian tendencies also prefer interacting with those of the opposite gender (Jonason & Schmitt, 2012). It is possible that this is a sign that you have a penchant to surround yourself with people who are easily influenced, since this is something that you do often. Machiavellianism has also been linked to the self-reported manipulation of a person of the opposite or same sex employing strategies such as the "silent treatment" and coercion. [Citation needed] [Citation needed] [Citation needed] (Jonason & Webster, 2012). Possibilities for exploitation and manipulation may present themselves in several contexts, one of which is the friendships that women develop with one another. Nevertheless, this is not the only place in which these kinds of situations might arise. According to research conducted by Su, Rounds, and Armstrong (2009), female respondents indicate that they place a higher value on personal relationships. When presented with adjustment obstacles such as finding a mate, this may be partially ascribed to a stronger dependence on female companions as a coping mechanism (Jonason & Schmitt, 2012; Silverman & Choi , 2005).

Women spend more time talking about their feelings and sharing personal information, and their friendships tend to be more dual in character, which makes it more difficult for them to find backup partners should their current relationship fail. Men spend less time talking about their feelings and sharing personal information. Males tend to spend less time discussing their own experiences and more time discussing a variety of other topics (Benenson & Christakos, 2003; David-Barrett et al

, 2015 ; Vigil , 2007). The cultivation of close, one-on-one friendships that are characterized by open communication has the potential to provide a setting that is conducive to the practice of manipulation in one form or another. This possibility exists because of the open communication that characterizes these friendships.

Despite the widespread belief that women can only be manipulated through the use of more covert techniques, it is not uncommon for women to use relational aggression as a manipulative strategy. This is despite the fact that many people believe that women can only be manipulated through the use of covert techniques (Wilson, Near , & Miller, 1996). It's possible that this has something to do with the dangers of engaging in physical aggression (Campbell, 1999), but it's also possible that this is seen as a socially acceptable way for women to speak with one another and form bonds with one another. [More citation is required] (Miller- Ott & Kelly, 2013).

The expression "relational aggression" refers to actions that cause harm to other people by causing them to be excluded from relationships, speak about them, or spread rumors about such connections (Archer and Coyne, 2005; Xie , Cairns , and Cairns , 2005). Relational aggression involves the support of peers and/or friends since it requires them to listen to gossip, help spread tales, exclude the target person(s), and offer their own opinion on the target. Moreover, it requires them to contribute their own perspective on the target. In addition to that, it demands students to provide their own personal viewpoint on the aim. This is because it is necessary for them to take part in spreading rumors, listen to discussion, and avoid the individual or individuals who are the subjects of the gossip (Miller- Ott & Kelley , 2013). As a direct result of this, it is essential for those taking part to have trust in one another. This trust must extend both to the participants' desire to take part in the activity as well as their conviction that other people would not betray them.

A method that involves the participation of women who exhibit a high level of Machiavellism may be fraught with complications. Even though direct aggression is more visible, relational violence is more covert than overt antagonism. The most obvious kind of violence is direct aggression directed at another individual. This form may take many forms. To participate in relational aggression, a person has to have a certain quantity of trust and connection with other people, in addition to the participation of peers and friends. Relational violence and Machiavellianism are incompatible with one another since Machiavellianism is characterized by suspicion, skepticism, and cynicism. Relational aggression is characterized by a desire to control people as well as their

behavior toward them (Christie & Geis , 1970). Individuals, especially those who have a high degree of Machiavellianism, have a great desire to avoid being caught, and the vast number of people engaged in interpersonal violence may also boost the risk of being found out about the violence they are doing. According to Abell and Brewer (2014), the term "Machiavellianism" describes the conduct in which women engage in relational animosity towards the online relationships they have. In spite of this, it is possible that this is a reflection of the lack of face-to-face contact and the decreased confidence in others that occurs while engaging in relational violence in a setting such as this one. It's possible that this is the case because relational aggressiveness in this environment leads to a decrease in confidence in other people.

Alternatively, you may practice your skills of manipulation on a close friend of yours. Emotional manipulation is one of the strategies that may be used (Austin, Farrelly, Black, and Moore, 2007; Austin and O'Donnell, 2013; Austin and O'Donnell, 2014; Austin & O'Donnell, 2013). Using various methods to affect the emotions of other people is at the heart of this tactic. Machiavellianism is about the use of emotional manipulation and involves methods such as purposefully complimenting the other person and soothing individuals to persuade them to do what the individual wants, according to Austin et al. Machiavellianism is about the use of emotional manipulation. [Citation needed] Machiavellianism is about the use of emotional manipulation (2007). The concept of Machiavellianism centers on the manipulation of people's emotions. Despite this, there has been little study done on the ways in which people who are high in Machiavellianism use emotional manipulation in the context of friendship. Machiavellianism is also tied to two unique strategies of emotional manipulation that are applied when manipulating the emotions of other people. These strategies are utilized while controlling the emotions of other people. These techniques are sometimes grouped together under the umbrella term of "dishonest approaches" or "defamation strategies." Criticizing someone or trying to undermine their trustworthiness are two examples of tactics that might be used in defamation cases. Both of these strategies are used with the intention of manipulating the sentiments of other individuals (for instance, begging for sympathy or seeming weak in order to find one's own way). Emotional manipulation, on the other hand, requires just one target person and the aggressor, in contrast to relational aggression, which is dependent on the trust and connection of other people. All that is required for emotional manipulation is a single person. Also, emotional manipulation is covert, reducing the possibility that the target or other others would identify it for what it is.

Manipulation of emotions may make it simpler to end a relationship, ruin one's reputation, and afterwards find new friends who have the same sexual orientation at a later time. It is possible that there is a link between women's self-reports of engaging in emotional manipulation and their views that their friends have engaged in emotional manipulation against them. Machiavellian women are more likely to engage in emotional manipulation. In addition to this, Machiavellian women have admitted to engaging in emotional manipulation on their own. Machiavellianism, in other words, may have something to do with the manner in which women perceive the emotional manipulation that is being committed by their female friends. This perception may have something to do with the way in which women see Machiavelli. To provide one example, Machiavellianism is connected to the idea that other people are powerless (e.g. Black et al., 2013). As a consequence of this, women who have greater levels of Machiavellianism may have the misconception that other people, particularly their acquaintances of the same gender, are unable to influence them in any manner. When it comes to friendships, this is particularly important to keep in mind. Yet Machiavellianism is also connected to a lack of faith in other people and the assumption that other people would seek to exploit them for their own profit. This is because Machiavelli believed that others would try to use them for their own advantage (Christie & Geis, 1970). It is probable that this suggests that women who score higher on Machiavellianism are more likely to believe that their friends are seeking to take advantage of them by manipulating their emotions in some fashion in order to get something for themselves. Previous research indicates that women who score higher on the Machiavellian trait are more likely to engage in emotional manipulation in their close relationships with other women, even if those friendships are with other women. This is the case regardless of whether the relationships are platonic or romantic. It makes no difference whether such friendships are with men or women; this is always the case. It is possible for these women to assert that the female companions in their lives whom they trust the most are the ones that abuse them in this way. The subject of whether or not emotional manipulation and Machiavellian thinking are connected in the context of friendship is one that has not been investigated by anybody.

Machiavellianism is associated to the practice of emotionally influencing a buddy in order to acquire what one wants for oneself, as well as the usage of two unique techniques of emotionally manipulating another person (harming and unrealistic strategies). We hypothesize that higher levels of Machiavellianism would be associated with the use of emotional manipulation (including

the use of unrealistic and mood-enhancing strategies) towards a close female friend. Specifically, we believe that this would be the case if the manipulative behavior was directed at the close friend. In particular, we are of the opinion that this is the case if the manipulative conduct was intended against the buddy. This estimate was obtained from an earlier research that was undertaken by Austin and colleagues (Austin et al., 2007; Austin & O'Donnell, 2013). It takes into consideration the potential benefits of using emotional manipulation and was based on the findings of that investigation (e.g., less trust in others, less chance of getting caught). In addition, the research analyzes the potential of a link between Machiavellianism and the many methods by which persons might be controlled. Machiavellianism has been shown to be connected to poor relationship quality in earlier study. [Citation needed] [Citation needed] (Abell et al., 2014; Aitken & Lyons, 2010). Despite this, these research did not look at how individuals with strong Machiavellian tendencies saw the functions of friendship. The goal of this investigation was to discover the answer to the aforementioned query.

In this last segment, we will analyze the connection between Machiavellianism and the six different roles that friendship plays in our lives. Companionship, help, intimacy, the development of a trustworthy connection, self-affirmation, and emotional stability are the six distinct advantages that may result from having a large number of close friends. Machiavellianism is a personality trait that is predictive with lower scores on all six functions of friendship. Even though individuals with higher Machiavellian scores may reap a variety of benefits from friendships, such as assistance in achieving their own goals, our findings suggest that Machiavellianism predicts lower scores on all six friendship functions. This is the case despite the fact that individuals with higher Machiavellian scores may reap a variety of benefits from friendships, such as assistance in achieving their own goals. This is the case despite the fact that those with higher Machiavellian scores may get a number of advantages from friendships. It is probable that those women who scored higher on the Machiavellianism characteristic reported lower levels of the functions that were previously described. This is due to the fact that women who scored higher on this characteristic tend to have a more generally pessimistic view of other people as a result of the emotional neutrality and cynicism that are characteristic of Machiavellianism. This was found to be the case because women who scored higher on this trait tended to have a more positive view of themselves. Consider the following situation as an example of extreme manipulation (Phillips and Shaw, 2015; Sripada, 2012; Woolfolk, Doris, and Darley, 2006):

Neuroscientists implant a device in your brain that gives it the ability to change your mental states (and therefore your behavior). Neuroscientists use this technology to persuade you to kill someone else by having the desire and intent to commit the murderous act. Have you demonstrated that you act of your own free will? Do you feel morally responsible for the person's death? Intuitively, manipulating another person reduces the causal and moral responsibility you have for an action, even if it's something you want to do and plan to do.

You'll be able to reproduce the studies that neuroscientists have conducted if you make these modifications. Now let's imagine that they do this in a deterministic manner, which means that, given the current state of the world and the laws of nature, there is no other way for events to transpire than the way that they already have. This is because there is no other way for events to transpire given the current state of the world and the laws of nature. Have you shown that you are capable of making your own decisions and that you have free will? When it comes to matters of ethics, are you accountable? If your responses to these situations are different, this suggests that something about the nature of the first causal factor (F1), and perhaps more specifically the existence or nature of that factor's mental states, may influence attributing responsibility to a second factor. If your responses to these situations are the same, this suggests that something about the nature of the first causal factor (F1) may influence attributing responsibility to the second factor. If your answers are the same, this shows that assigning blame to the second factor may be influenced by something about the nature of the first causal factor (F1) (F2). This offers a vital question:

Why might factors external to a particular person influence attributing responsibility to that person?

philosophers have considered these questions considering the debate between incompatibilists and compatibilists on the possibility of moral responsibility and free choice living in a deterministic universe. The question at the heart of the controversy is whether free will and moral responsibility can coexist. Incompatibilists believe that moral responsibility and free will cannot coexist in a deterministic reality, while compatibilists argue that moral responsibility and free will can coexist

in a deterministic universe. Compatibilists believe that moral responsibility and free will can coexist in a deterministic universe (Mele, 2006; Pereboom, 2001).

Incompatibilists are those who hold the view that compatibilism is vulnerable to manipulation arguments. These arguments begin with the perception that being controlled by another component (such as neuroscientists) weakens moral responsibility and free choice. Incompatibilists are those who contend that compatibilism is open to being manipulated by other people's arguments. Compatibilists and compatibilism They argue that it is readily susceptible to being influenced by arguments that are presented in opposition to it. If the circumstances of manipulation and the related conditions of deterministic causality (like the regular causal conditions in your mind), do not vary from one another by a substantial amount, then determinism should undermine not only moral responsibility but also free choice. A fallacy might be regarded to be shown by syncretism on a more comprehensive level. Arguments that are built on manipulation have a unique and alluring kind of intuitive appeal. When it comes down to it, why should it make a difference whether the same limits on action are driven by purposeful actors or by natural laws and occurrences? On the other hand, in circumstances involving entrapment, the law permits the enforcement of less severe sanctions (Carlson, 2007), and actual data imply that manipulation is conceptually distinct as well. Even though most people give manipulated agents lower marks for moral responsibility and free will than they do non-manipulated agents (Phillips & Shaw, 2015; Sripada, 2012; Woolfolk et al., 2006), at least in certain circumstances, the majority of people agree: Manipulated agents should be held to a higher standard of moral responsibility and free will than non-manipulated agents.

Agents in a deterministic universe may have moral responsibility and free will (Woolfolk et al., 2006; Phillips & Shaw, 2015; Sripada, 2012; Woolfolk (Murray & Nahmias, 2014; Nahmias & Murray, 2010; Nichols, 2011; Nichols & Knobe, 2007).

The concept that evil neuroscientists with the ability to manipulate people's minds exists primarily in works of science fiction; nonetheless, this just serves to make more ordinary issues seem more serious. Sunstein and Thaler (2008), for instance, argue that the government "pokes" people in the ribs in order to get them to do what it wants. Using research on heuristics and biases (for example, increasing the number of organ donors by asking people to check their driver's license to

deactivate), and Freedman (2012), it is important to note how smartphone apps inspired by BF Skinner can be used. One example of this would be increasing the number of organ donors by asking people to check their driver's license to deactivate. A good illustration of this would be encouraging more individuals to become organ donors by having them tick the box on their driver's license that says "do not activate."

[Choosing Between Alternative Policies, Practices and/or Technologies](#)

People are given the opportunity to choose from a wide range of alternative policies, practices, and/or technologies (such as air conditioning, desalination, insurance, relocation, etc.), and one of those possibilities is the construction of sea walls. This interpretation of adaptation is the one that is used the most often since it is also the one that is the most common. In this article, we suggest that there is a mismatch between the early and Darwinian usage of the term "adaptation" and more recent undertones, and that this divergence presents a chance for an entirely new focus on adaptation because of the potential it presents. In addition, we suggest that there is a mismatch between the early and Darwinian usage of the term "adaptation" and more recent undertones. We assert, with the use of the analytic frameworks developed by Smit et al. (1999, 2000) and Adger et al. (2005, 2009), that the objective of adaptation and the focus of adaptation are the two primary characteristics that differentiate one adaptation strategy from another. As the various adaptation techniques are compared, these distinctions become clear.

The Darwinian perspective of adaptation implies that it is a process of self-directed change (i.e., "adaptation") with the intention of creating internal adjustments so that they are more appropriate to external surroundings. This view is referred to as the "adaptation hypothesis." Adaptation is the process of organisms undergoing change to enhance their chances of surviving in their individual surroundings. This process is referred to as the process of change. On the other hand, adaptation ideas that are often articulated in the modern literature on adaptation to climate change also allow for alternatives that affect external environments. This is because adaptation is about dealing with the effects of climate change. Because of this, adjustments that are directed externally to better fit the present predispositions of certain people or social groupings are now achievable. This is because adaptation is often thought to be a process that takes place apart from an entity, which is the reason why this result occurred. As a result, contemporary ideas that result in "adaptation" might perhaps be described more accurately as manipulation. In addition to this, there is the chance that people or social groups won't have a need for "adaptation" any more (in the short term). The

contemporary definitions are, in many ways, a depiction of Darwin's idea in the other direction, which is why he was so surprised by the results. We believe that it is essential to move the conversations away from "how should life be" (Duit et al. 2010) talks and toward more inwardly oriented discussions of "how to act." This has a higher probability of being sustainable and of taking into consideration broader social and ecological circumstances. In order to increase the chance of negative repercussions for adaptation attempts, we believe that it is essential to move the conversations away from "how should life be." It is vital, in order to make progress toward this objective, to move dialogues away from a concentration on the outside world and "what life ought to be like."

Oxford University According to definitions published by Press (2011), the primary mechanism that lies at the heart of "manipulation" strategies is control of external system elements (i.e., other people or contexts), and the implicit intention of the manipulator to achieve desired results is reflected in this control. This control can be seen as a means by which the manipulator can achieve desired results. When seen from the vantage point of the manipulator, there is a good chance that this strategy will be effective, at the very least on the short term, and this is a very strong probability. On the other hand, the act of manipulation may lead to a lack of understanding of the interdependencies that are inherent in complex social-ecological systems. This may result in a future failure to achieve the intended results due to a reduction in the number of possibilities for genuine learning experiences. This is as a result of the fact that, whenever alteration is carried out, there is often just one outcome that is sought for. Our understanding of complex systems has not advanced very far in recent years (for example, Underdal 2010), and it seems probable that this will continue to be the case for the foreseeable future as well (Owens 2010).

It is difficult to determine the actual direct and indirect repercussions (also known as predictability) of attempts at adaptation and manipulation over the extensive time periods that are required for sustainability. This is because such durations are required to ensure long-term viability. Analyzing the activities with the goal of finding their intended purpose is the first step in gaining a better knowledge of the potential for both good and negative consequences of the system. This may be accomplished by first studying the activities (i.e., who or what is adapting). When it comes to finding solutions to the many issues that are connected to sustainability, complexity is inevitably present. The reductionist philosophy is reflected in manipulation that is carried out through

interventions that are directed from outside the system. This practice separates the components of the system from one another and disengages those who initiate interventions from the systems they are attempting to influence, which is consistent with the philosophy of reductionism. As a consequence of this, defensive management strategies are used instead of reflective ones (Senge 2006, Smith 2009). According to Senge (2006), reductionist cognitive processes are acquired at an early age among children who attend educational institutions in western societies. Due of these processes, it is challenging to understand the nature and breadth of the interventions and the repercussions, as well as the linkages that exist between the two categories of effects. Aside from the predictability of outcomes, the primary mechanism by which manipulative strategies undermine sustainable futures is that they limit opportunities for adaptive learning by avoiding authentic experiences of system dynamics. This is the primary mechanism by which manipulative strategies undermine sustainable futures. One of the ways in which manipulative methods destroy the possibility of sustainable futures is as follows: (see Smith and Smith 2006, Smith et al. 2009). One of the most important ways in which dishonest practices make sustainable futures less likely to materialize is as follows: (ie social- ecological change). Also, the assumption of implicit control over a system, or at least a piece of it, may not be defined in such decision-making processes, which has the potential to constrain one's capacity to innovate. This may be a problem since one's ability to innovate may be hindered as a result. When a person's capacity for creativity is limited, this might be an issue since it makes it more difficult for that person to innovate (Senge 2006). Both the negative impact that it has on adaptation and the potential for adaptation that it possesses are revealed by a recent study that investigated how ancient civilizations adapted to their environments and discovered that the availability of creative resources was a significant factor in determining whether or not those civilizations were successful (Bussey et al. 2011). This study reveals both the potential for adaptation that it possesses and the negative impact that it has on adaptation.

Methods of adaptation and steering are often quite dynamic and continuing. This takes the form of being moulded over the course of time by a sequence of activities that are either adaptive or manipulative. When examined from the point of view of a system, manipulation trajectory leads to an increase in the amount of social and ecological stress, in addition to a decline in the ability to adapt over the course of time. This reduced capacity for flexibility presents a substantial threat to the overall stability of the system. These effects on the system that is being managed and its

adaptability may also give birth to route dependencies in the process that is being manipulated. This is a condition in which every manipulative action raises social and ecological stress, decreases the ability to adapt, and necessitates further manipulative activities to prevent a shift in the predominant social paradigm. This is a condition in which every manipulative action raises social and ecological stress, decreases the ability to adapt, and increases social and ecological stress. The need for ongoing responsiveness is often motivated by the desire to keep the system in the state it is currently in rather than by the requirement to adapt to the dynamics of the system. When it comes to "adapting to the dynamics of the system," this is the exact reverse of what is intended.

A course of action that includes manipulation also increases the likelihood of the emergence of new negative feedback loops. These are cycles in which the level of manipulation increases at the expense of the ability to learn and adjust to new conditions. Individuals are unable to acquire the talents associated with transformational learning as a result of this, which further lowers their potential for flexibility. It would appear that the combination of change that is pushed from the outside, experienced actors, system coverage that is designed narrowly, and limited adaptive learning is a powerful combination that has a high potential for unsustainable processes and results that increase vulnerability and decrease resilience.

Focusing on Alleviating Symptoms

may be referred to as "short-term therapies" due to the fact that their primary focus is on alleviating symptoms rather than resolving the conditions that are driving such symptoms. This indicates that they do not tackle the fundamental causes of the problem (Senge 2006). As a direct result of this, many problems either continue in their existing iteration or take on a far more severe manifestation. When attempting to evaluate the efficacy of adaptation strategies, it is very helpful to have a solid understanding of both the intended function of the suggested changes and the scope of the impacts those changes will have. This is because having a solid understanding of both of these factors allows for a more accurate assessment of the efficacy of adaptation strategies (Adger et al. 2005). In addition, having this level of understanding is necessary in order to be able to distinguish between manipulation and disagreement. It is possible for the outcomes of adaptation to become less relevant, less effective, or even inappropriate when they transcend the geographical and temporal constraints of their initial context. This is something that may happen when the original context is taken out of its original setting (Adger et al. 2005). The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) refers to incorrect results like these as "non-compliance" in the third

assessment report that it has released. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) offered the following explanation of what it means to be non-compliant with their recommendations:

"Any change in natural or human systems that inadvertently increases susceptibility to climatic stimuli; an adaptation that does not succeed in reducing vulnerability but instead increases it" (McCarthy et al. 2001:990). According to Barnett and O'Neill (2010), references to mismatch first appeared in the scientific literature in the early 1990s. These formations in the literature cover a wide range of industries as well as different geographical and temporal scales. In the context of climate change, this information is important. (Barnett and O'Neill , 2010).

At first glance, incompatibilities of this sort may seem to be the same thing as manipulation. On the other hand, every mismatch starts out as a harmless adaptation and is believed to "accidentally" boost sensitivity since it is a change that is not planned. This is because it is a change that occurs when there is a mismatch between two things. This is due to the fact that the modification is an unwelcome kind of adaptation. In conclusion, one of the most essential features that separates disharmony from manipulation is the motive that is behind the conduct. This is one of the most crucial characteristics that distinguishes disharmony from manipulation. The scenario that is referred to as "nonconformity" is one in which an endeavor to comply leads to the manifestation of consequences that are not desired. On the other hand, one school of thinking claims that the term "manipulation" is the one that should be used when there is no intention of adhering to the norm. This school of thought contends that the word "manipulation" is the one that should be used (ie, entering into internal regulation).

It is necessary that we narrow in on the exact nature of our intervention even further before we get started. This is because the word "manipulation" is frequently used in a slang sense to refer to a varied variety of actions, so it is important that we do so. At its most basic level, having an impact on something and being able to direct or control that something are essentially the same thing. When we talk of pilots flying planes, we are referring to the manipulation of cockpit controls, and when we speak of surgeons doing surgeries, we are referring to the use of precision equipment. The term "manipulation" may be used interchangeably with "influence" and "control" when referring to efforts made to exert an effect on or seize control of institutions and processes. For

instance, in recent times there has been a lot of writing about assertions (as well as the proof that has been presented) that internet trolls working for the Russian government sought to influence the media in the United States during the presidential election in 2016. This took place in 2016. The actual election was the focus of these efforts, which eventually intended to influence the outcome of the election (by influencing voters). Fear that individuals are manipulated, that individual decision-making is directed or controlled, and that, as a result, individuals' capacity to make autonomous choices is compromised is, however, at the center of this story and at the heart of the tales. Fear that individuals are manipulated, that individual decision-making is directed or controlled, and that this will compromise individuals' capacity to make autonomous choices. They are analogous to this in the same way as well. The following discussion will emphasize on manipulation in this sense, which refers to the act of seeking to influence the decision-making and behavior of another person. This definition of manipulation will be used throughout the discussion. Political theorists and philosophers have been at conflict with one another for a significant amount of time about the topic of what constitutes manipulation. According to Robert Noggle, there are essentially three different schools of thought that may be distinguished (Noggle , 2018b).

Some people believe that the phrases "irrational influence" and "manipulation" may be used interchangeably (Wood , 2014). To put this another way, the act of manipulating someone entails exercising control over them in such a way that stops them from making decisions that are rational and thought out. In other words, they are unable to use this capacity of theirs since it has been blocked. The use of subliminal messaging is a well-known example of manipulation that may be thought of in this fashion. It is reasonable to infer that some types of emotional attraction, such as the use of guilt, are also a part of this image; however, the concept of what constitutes reason may be interpreted quite differently from one person to the next. The second definition of manipulation describes it as a kind of compulsion that is analogous to that which is seen in situations involving blackmail (Kligman & Culver , 1992, qtd . in Noggle , 2018b). This line of reasoning is predicated on the guiding premise that even though manipulation does include a certain amount of power — that is, the imposition of a penalty for disobedience — this level of power is insufficient to be regarded as coercion. This premise is based on the idea that manipulation does include some amount of power, but it is not enough power to be considered coercion.

The next piece of advice is that dishonesty should be considered a kind of manipulation. To persuade someone to behave in a manner that conforms to the desires of the manipulator is what it means to manipulate somebody, precisely as Iago did in Shakespeare's Othello by wooing the characters in the play. Even if there are a lot of different theories that fit under this tent, the primary concept that should be kept in mind is that manipulation, at its heart, is to control another person. provoking envy, giving clues, and so forth are all examples.

It keeps a very tight-lipped approach to the cheating technique, but it does make the concept of cheating work more concretely, which, in the long run, leads in the supply of more precise tools for recognizing instances of manipulation. To put it another way, manipulating someone includes exerting conscious and covert control over their decision-making processes in order to find and exploit any faults in those processes. Our point of view is that the phrase "covert effect" may be used interchangeably with "manipulation." To put it another way, influencing someone implies taking advantage of the decision-making processes that they already have in place. When you covertly influence someone, also known as imposing a covert influence, you are influencing them in a way that they are not consciously aware of and have a difficult time noticing even if they try to understand it. When you do this, you are influencing them in a way that is also known as imposing a covert influence. Even if a someone makes a concerted attempt to grasp this kind of influence, it is difficult to recognize its presence. The term "latent effect" may also be used interchangeably with "latent effect," which is yet another synonym for "latent effect." If we consider manipulation to be a kind of covert influence and approach it as such, we will be better able to distinguish it from other types of influence. In the following, we shall separate it from the concepts of persuasion and coercion first, and then from the concepts of nudging and dishonesty after that. When we speak about persuasion in the sense of rational persuasion, what we mean is the act of attempting to persuade someone's perspective by giving them with reasons that they can analyze and assess for themselves. This is what we mean when we talk about rational persuasion. When you compel someone, you are trying to win their favor by limiting their options to the point where it is no longer rational for them to do so. They have the option of doing the action that the person who is coercing them wants them to take (Wood , 2014).

It would seem that the conventional definitions of persuasion and compulsion are significantly different from one another, and perhaps practically diametrically opposed to one another. For

instance, it is acceptable to persuade someone to do something almost all of the time, yet it violates ethical standards virtually never to force someone to do something. One way in which these two tactics are similar to one another is the fact that both persuasion and coercion are direct means to exert influence. This is only one of the ways in which these two tactics are parallel to one another. When another person is making an effort to persuade or compel us into doing anything, the vast majority of the time, we are able to notice their actions. On the other hand, manipulation is covert, which means that we aren't aware that someone is attempting to influence our decision until we learn the facts about the situation. This is because we aren't aware that someone is trying to influence our decision until we learn the facts about the situation. The realization that we have been manipulated leaves us with the impression that we are being used in a clear manner. When we examine the circumstances that led to a certain decision, we often discover that we did not immediately put that decision into action after we had made it, despite the fact that we had made it. This component of the discipline is what differentiates manipulation from other forms of social influence, such as persuasion and lobbying.

is hindered since it requires selecting for us how and why we ought to spend our life, which, as a result of manipulation, makes it impossible to do. As a result of this, a specific group of issues develop, all of which will be explored in the paragraphs that follow. At this point, it is really necessary to have a complete understanding of the sort of influence that is playing a role in this scenario. In contrast to persuasion and coercion, which both make overt appeals to their respective ends, manipulation acts in a covert way to achieve its objectives. Although though the conditions that are forced on us are the cause of our anger, it is usually always OK for us to feel angry when we are required to carry out an activity that we do not want to carry out. Nonetheless, the circumstances that are imposed on us are the source of our anger. On the other hand, we are not subject to any limits when we are affected in any manner. Instead, we are instructed to carry out actions that are beyond the scope of our conscious knowledge, for reasons that we are unable to identify, and with repercussions that we may or may not choose to avoid. These reasons and repercussions are all a result of the fact that we are directed to carry out these actions. This takes place independently of whether or not our conscious awareness is drawn to this specific feature of the scenario. Nonetheless, looking at this photo might give them the idea that they are being misguided. According to our point of view, manipulation can be broken down into its component

parts, one of which is deception. Deceit may be defined as the intentional act of causing another person to believe something that is not true.

If a manipulator wanted his wife to clean the house, for example, he may tell her that his mother was coming to visit and then use that as an excuse to lie to her about it. He might also use it as an opportunity to manipulate her. This would encourage the partner of the manipulator to make a reasonable decision based on erroneous assumptions, which would ultimately result in the manipulator receiving what he wanted out of the scenario. When this occurred, the person who was manipulating the situation would get what he wanted. But, manipulation may take many forms, and deception is only one of them; there are a number of other methods to exercise covert control. The term "manipulation" may refer to a wide variety of activities. To begin, those who influence others are under no responsibility to concentrate on the perspectives of the people they are manipulating. They may instead exercise covert influence by quietly charming the target, making them feel guilty, seducing them, or playing on a variety of other the target's instincts and emotions in a variety of different ways. There are several approaches that may be used to accomplish this goal.

A strategy is regarded as "secret" in the sense that it is significant only if the target of the manipulation is uninformed of the approach adopted by the manipulator while they are making use of the manipulator. This is the only condition under which a strategy may be considered significant. As soon as the target is aware of the approach, the strategy is deemed meaningless and is no longer relevant. There are many people who believe that even overt seduction, guilt, and other similar approaches are examples of manipulative behavior. This is despite the fact that proponents of the concept of manipulation known as "irrational impact" almost universally agree that the methods in question are at their most successful when they are kept hidden. We have a sneaky feeling that the manipulator has sought to conceal their tracks by employing covert methods such as seduction, guilt, and other strategies of a similar nature, but they have been unsuccessful in doing so in the majority of the situations involving this one. When a person has been made aware that they are the target of another person's influence, that awareness will become a regular component of the decision-making process for that individual. Because of this, we have to draw the conclusion that the work that is put into protecting one's anonymity is of more significance than any one specific tactic for manipulation. We are all constantly being influenced by a wide variety of factors;

however, the reason why we do not always feel as though we are being manipulated is because we are frequently able to consider, comprehend, and take these factors into account when we are deliberating over our own choices regarding how to behave. This is the reason why we do not always feel as though we are being manipulated (Raz , 1986). , p.204).

The manner in which we were impacted is one of the aspects that go into the formation of the internal motives that are a factor in our conduct. On the other hand, the effectiveness of this technique suffers when the influence is hidden, which is why it is important to avoid doing so. Therefore, while we can call a person who frequently engages in overt acts of seduction or seduction a manipulative — that is, someone who frequently tries to manipulate — we can literally say that they only succeed in manipulating their goals when they are unaware of their goals. This is because the person who frequently engages in overt acts of seduction or seduction frequently engages in overt acts of seduction. This is due to the fact that when people are unclear about their objectives, they are more open to being influenced by the actions of others. Because of this, we are quick to label a person as manipulative if they engage in overt acts of seduction or seduction. This is because it is natural for us to refer to a person as manipulating. This suggests that they often try to exert their will on other people. Second, behavioral economists have compiled a comprehensive list of "cognitive biases." These cognitive biases are ineffective mental shortcuts that we make use of on a regular basis while we are in the process of making choices. These cognitive biases may be controlled by so-called manipulators to cause our choices to go in a different direction.

It is possible for the information that is supplied to us to be framed in such a way that we are persuaded to believe a certain interpretation of the facts; manipulators have the capacity to strategically "anchor" our frame of reference while we are doing data analysis. Deception, in addition to the manipulation of people's wants and emotions, was probably the most prevalent kind of manipulation in the past; that is, the most popular method for influencing others. In other words, manipulation was the most common approach. But, there is an explanation for why this transpired to be the case, and we will discuss it in further depth in the paragraphs that follow.

“ believing that exploiting cognitive biases and weaknesses is the most worrisome problem we face today.”

The research conducted by Sunstein served as the foundation for the game "Poke," which was created by Richard Thaler and Cass Sunstein. It is possible to define a "nudge" as any modification that is made on purpose in the decision-making environment ("choice architecture") of another person in order to influence the decision-making outcome of that individual (Thaler & Sunstein , 2008, p. 6). Because our decision-making processes are inherently and inevitably sensitive to even the tiniest cues from the contexts in which they are located, Thaler and Sunstein believe that the fact that we suffer from so much vulnerability to decision-making demonstrates this when we contemplate other people's choices. This is because our decision-making processes are inherently sensitive to even the tiniest cues from the contexts in which they are located. This is the case due to the fact that our decision-making mechanisms are intrinsically sensitive to even the most minute indications coming from the environments in which they are positioned. We can't help but impact their decision to establish surrounds, from the apps they use to locate a restaurant to the menus they order once they are there. This includes everything from the apps they use to find a restaurant to the menus they order. We are unable to stop ourselves from engaging in this activity. As a result of this, we owe it to the people to make efficient use of this influence by directing the decisions that individuals make to their own benefit as well as to the benefit of all of us collectively. This can be accomplished by guiding the decisions that individuals make to benefit both themselves and all of us collectively.

Because of this, the question that needs to be asked is, "Is nudging a form of manipulation?" This is because of the definition of manipulation that we have chosen, which is covert influence, as well as our belief that impacts are frequently concealed precisely by taking advantage of decision-making deficiencies such as cognitive biases. The question of whether "nudging" constitutes a form of "manipulation" arises in light of the fact that we have chosen to define "manipulation" as "latent influence," and we have also proposed that effects are frequently veiled precisely by exploiting decision-making deficiencies such as cognitive biases. Given these two points, the issue at hand is whether or not "nudging" In spite of the fact that a great number of people have written on this subject, there is not one single point of agreement (see e.g., Bovens , 2009; Hausman & Welch , 2010; Noggle , 2018a; Nys & Engelen , 2017; Reach, 2016; Selinger & Whyte , 2011; Sunstein , 2016). This is probably due, at the very least in part, to the fact that the term "nudge" can be used to refer to a great number and diversity of distinct shifts in the structures that are

utilized to make decisions in a wide variety of different contexts. This shifts in structure can be used to influence behavior in a variety of different ways.

The difference resides in whether or not the poke is implicit, as well as whether or not it is aiming to exploit or fix deficiencies. From our vantage point, some of the pokes are manipulative, but others are not. The many nudges mentioned by Thaler and Sunstein, in addition to those offered by other individuals, do not stay secret and seek to repair cognitive bias. For example, we do not consider nudges that strive to deliver information, such as nutrition labels, to be manipulative since all they are doing is providing information to the target audience. They encourage people to carry out activities at a more leisurely pace, to reflect on matters in more depth, and to base their choices on more reliable information. In contrast, Thaler and Sunstein's well-known "cafeteria poke" looks to be somewhat manipulative since it seeks to work independently of the conscious understanding of the individual and capitalizes on a decision-making bias. This makes the "cafeteria poke" seem to be somewhat deceptive. This may be accomplished by placing less nutritious foods below or above the eye level of more nutritious meals, with the better foods being placed at eye level. In spite of the fact that it ought to go without saying that this is dishonest and that there is no evidence to indicate that this is not a definite consequence, there is no evidence to suggest that this is not a certain outcome. One draws attention to the fact that a technique is harmful by paying focus to the fact that the method is manipulative. This is a subject that will be addressed in more depth in the next paragraphs, so stay tuned for that! Yet, if there is a greater substantial advantage that comes with it, then it is possible that the potential harm might be considered as justifiable.

After distinguishing manipulation from persuasion, coercion, deception, and nudging, it is possible to define "online manipulation" as the use of information technology to covertly influence another person's decision-making by targeting and exploiting decisions. This definition is possible after defining manipulation as covert or covert influence and differentiating it from persuasion. By defining manipulation as covert or covert influence and separating it from persuasion, coercion, deceit, and nudging, we may arrive at this definition.

By defining these definitions, it is possible to characterize "online manipulation" as the use of information technology to covertly alter the decision making of another person. This is a viable description of "online manipulation." This definition is an extension of the two definitions that came before it. Most importantly, we have removed the term "online manipulation" from the public

discourse, and we have adopted a broad perspective of what is meant by the term "online" (if any). This is because we have come to the realization that there is no longer a distinct point of separation between an individual's online existence and their life outside of the internet. The term "online manipulation," as far as our present knowledge can tell, refers to the kind of manipulation that can be carried out thanks to advancements in information technology. Instead, "automated manipulation" and "digital manipulation" are two terms that may be used in their place to refer to "internet manipulation." Both of these terms are appropriate.

We need to hold off on contact until circumstances that were once "offline" become more mediated by digital technology (for example, because the individuals there carry smartphones and the venues themselves are outfitted with internet-connected sensors).

When seen through the lens of this reasoning, it is not difficult to understand why information technology is ideally suited to play a role in the process of providing support for manipulative effects. To begin, all of our failings in terms of decision making are constantly brought to light because of the all-encompassing digital monitoring that is going place right now. Experts in the field of privacy have been aware for a very long time that everything that we do in this day and age leaves a digital imprint, and that data collectors combine these traces into fairly complete profiles based on the information that they gather. This has been the case for quite some time (Solove , 2004).

These profiles include information on our demographics, income, employment, buying activities, connections with utilities and agencies, as well as other aspects of our lives; in all, they may cover thousands of data points about each individual person.

Examining hidden patterns in this data allows those that engage in behavioral targeting, such as advertisers and others, to choose when and how to interact with us to exert the most amount of impact possible (Kaptein & Eckles , 2010). In addition to the well-known cognitive biases outlined earlier, such as anchoring and framing effects, which shape the decision-making of most individuals to some degree, each and every one of us is vulnerable to specific variables that have the potential to influence how we select. For example, we are all susceptible to specific variables that have the potential to influence how we feel about something. We are all distinct people. We discuss specific problems, anxieties, hopes, and desires, in addition to the aforementioned realities of the economic, material, and physical reality.

In addition to this, digital surveillance is becoming more capable of distinguishing between vulnerable persons and other people in general. It has been suggested that commercials could be crafted in a way that appeals to certain voter "psychometric" attributes by merging data collected from users' activity on social media platforms with personality profiles derived from online surveys (openness, extroversion, etc.). Later, in 2017, a newspaper in Australia revealed internal Facebook strategy documents that showed the company's pledge to identify young users who were feeling anxious. In particular, the records included specifics on the company's claim that it could identify when young customers were experiencing nervous feelings. These advertisements included an explanation of the alleged capabilities of the company to recognize when young clients are feeling insecure about their safety.

"Facebook is able to identify when young people are feeling 'stressed,' 'defeated,' 'overwhelmed,' 'anxious,' and 'tense' by monitoring posts, images, chats, and internet activity in real time," according to a report (Davidson, 2017). Facebook has said that it has never used the information to target adverts to teenagers; however, the corporation has not ruled out the chance that it would do so in the future.

Second, the surroundings provided by digital platforms such as websites and applications for mobile devices, such as smartphones, are excellent for transforming these discoveries into our decision-making weaknesses. Using this example as a jumping off point, it is not difficult to imagine other scenarios, such as banks targeting advertisements for subprime loans toward individuals who are in a desperate financial situation or pharmaceutical companies targeting advertisements for pharmaceuticals toward individuals who are suspected of being in a critical health crisis.

Finally, during the last several years, digital platforms such as websites and applications for digital cellphones have seen an explosion in their user base and popularity. These platforms are inherently interactive, intrusive, and adaptable dynamic decision structures due to the very nature of their design (Lanzing, 2018; Susser, 2019b; Yeung, 2017). This indicates that the digital interfaces we engage with are configured in real time using the information about us that was discussed before, and that they continue to learn about us as we continue to interact with them. This is because we ourselves are always expanding our knowledge, and hence they are always learning new things about us (2017, p. 122).

Thirdly, if manipulation is a covert effect, then the perfect instruments for manipulation are digital technology since the user will not be aware that they are being manipulated. This is mirrored in the vocabulary used in the design of technology goods; we speak about "users" and "end users," as well as "user interfaces" and "human-computer interaction." Take a computer or a smartphone, for example; when we're using them, we pay very little attention to them (Rosenberger , 2009).

Since the language of transparency might be confused with the notion of openness that is common in talks about technology policy, we might find it more beneficial to refer to it as "invisibility" (Susser, 2019b). Philosophers refer to the phenomena that occurs when we get the impression that the perceptual objects that are communicated to us by technologies such as seeing, hearing, or other means are open and transparent as technological transparency (Ihde, 1990; Van Den Eede, 2011; Verbeek, 2005).

Behavioral Advertising

In conclusion, even though we make a major focus on the example of behavioral advertising to highlight these dynamics, it is very important to bear in mind that marketers are not the only ones involved in manipulative approaches. Even though we are going to focus a significant amount of attention on this picture, it is critical that we emphasize this idea. There is a growing interest in user interface and experience, as well as design tactics that take advantage of users' decision-making deficiencies in order to coerce people into acting in a manner that is not in their own best interests. This interest comes alongside design tactics that take advantage of users' decision-making deficiencies to coerce people into acting in a manner that is not in their (or at least act in the best interests of the website or app). One example of a dark pattern is the requirement that premium memberships must automatically renew themselves commencing after the completion of the first free trial period. These design strategies are referred to as "dark models" (Brignull , 2013; Gray , Kou , Battles , Hoggatt , & Toombs , 2018; Murgia , 2019; Singer, 2016). Even though many of these tactics have been around for at least as long as the internet has, and despite the fact that not all of them rise to the level of manipulation—sometimes they can completely annoy users rather than hide their intentions—their growing prevalence has led some people to advocate for the enactment of laws that would regulate them. [Citation needed] (Bartz , 2019).

Concerns about the risk of manipulation on the internet have also been raised in connection to the services provided by companies that are a part of an economy that is demonstrating resilience,

such as Uber and Lyft (Veen , Goods , Josserand and Kaine , 2017). Even though these platforms market themselves as more flexible and liberating alternatives to conventional employment, there still needs to be some level of management over the workers who use them to guarantee a level of dependability and uniformity in the service that is provided to customers. This is necessary to guarantee a level of consistency in the quality of the product or service that is offered.

On the other hand, companies that are a part of the gig economy do not have access to the traditional management controls that are typically located in an office or on a production floor. This is because the gig economy is not a traditional business model. As a direct result of this, many companies rely on "algorithmic management" strategies such as notifications enabled through mobile apps, customer satisfaction ratings, and various other sorts of soft control (Rosenblat & Stark, 2016). For instance, rather than asking (or demanding) employees to work longer hours, Uber alerts drivers who try to leave the app with a reminder of their progress towards a specific earnings target and uses the desire to keep moving towards that target. This prevents drivers from quitting the app prematurely and ensures that they continue to make progress toward their goal. This stops drivers from closing the app too soon and guarantees that they continue to make progress toward their objective despite any potential distractions.

When an Uber driver tries to sign out of the Uber app, the business sends them a notice that informs them of how close they are to reaching certain revenue goals. Uber is a company that makes money off the fact that people desire to keep climbing to higher levels of achievement (Mason, 2018; Scheiber , 2017).

Not all these strategies are intrinsically manipulative in their current form since individuals are knowledgeable and a large proportion of them are probably already aware of the obstacles they confront. Also, the current version of these strategies has not been perfected. But, despite this, they are very important events since they illustrate the course that we are now on. Our ever-increasing reliance on digital technologies in all aspects of our lives – systems that constantly collect, aggregate, and analyze information about us – means that we are disclosing an increasing amount of information about our individual and societal vulnerabilities. This is because systems that constantly collect, aggregate, and analyze information about us. This is due to the fact that these systems are always gathering, aggregating, and evaluating information about us as individuals. It is become easier for the digital platforms that we interact with at home, at work, and in public to

make use of this data to influence and change our decision-making processes. This is happening both in public and in private settings. As more time passes, we will get more used to these routines, and as a result, we will pay less attention to each one of them in isolation.

Harms of Online Manipulation

Now that this image is before us, the question arises:

What exactly is the harm done as a result of influencing individuals in this way?

Why should we be concerned that technology mediation might make us more vulnerable to manipulation?

According to our point of view, there are a few unique types of damage, but they all come from the same underlying issue, which is that manipulation reduces the individual agency of the individuals it is targeted at. This is the root cause of all these problems. The ability of a person to make critical judgments free from the influence of other individuals is referred to as their "autonomy." Joseph Raz asserts that "the guiding notion that underpins the idea of personal autonomy is that individuals should be free to select the direction of their own lives," and this idea serves as the foundation for the concept of personal autonomy (Raz , 1986, p. 369). When you live your own life, you are free to make existential choices as well as decisions for your day-to-day life and family, such as deciding who you will spend the rest of your life with and whether you will have children. This freedom comes with the responsibility that comes with living your own life. And confronting them freely is having the chance to think about and argue about one's alternatives, to examine them in the context of one's values, goals, and commitments, and finally to make decisions for reasons that one accepts and approves as being one's own. Face them freely. And taking a direct approach to them allows one to openly confront their threats (JP Christman, 2009 ; Oshana , 2015; Veltman & Piper , 2014). The normative concept of autonomy may drive liberal democratic societies in a variety of diverse ways, depending on the society in question. We hold the concept that people may and should exercise the ability to rule themselves, thus we put a high priority on our capacity to govern ourselves in a democratic and cooperative way. This is one reason why we place such a high price on our self-governance capabilities.

In rare occasions, philosophers can make the idea of autonomy work by drawing a line of demarcation between the adequacy criteria of the concept and the conditions of originality. This allows the concept of autonomy to operate (JP Christman , 2009, p. 155f). To begin, being autonomous requires possessing the cognitive, psychological, social, and emotional skills to ponder on one's options, develop objectives about those choices, and then act on those intents. This is a prerequisite for being able to think critically about one's actions. This is something that should be kept in mind throughout a person's whole life. If you are in possession of these abilities, you will be able to act in a manner that is congruent with the choices you make. Second, it indicates that after engaging in critical reflection, one is able to connect with one's own values, interests, and passions, and that one is then able to openly assert that these things are one's own. This occurs after one is able to openly assert that one's values, interests, and passions are their own. Understandably, a great number of people have a problem with the idea of autonomy because they consider its criteria to be too logical and irrational.

They argue that people do not often make decisions in such a way, and that those who do so are acting in an illogical manner. They say that we are emotional actors and creatures of habit, that we are trained and acclimated to particular ways of decision-making that we almost never think about or approve of, and that this is due to the fact that we are creatures of habit. They also say that we are trained and acclimated to particular ways of making decisions that we almost never think about or approve of. We acknowledge that critical thinking can be counter-factual (in theory, we should be able to think critically and support our motivations to act, but in practice, we don't really need to think about every move that we make), we have a broader view of autonomy; our understanding of negotiation encompasses not only ideas and wishes, but also feelings, beliefs, and experiences; and we are aware that critical thinking can be counter-factual.

Conceptions of autonomy that are too atomistic, in addition to those that are very strict and rational, are also things that we believe should be avoided. Individuals who, on a social, cultural, historical, and political level, have the ability to be termed autonomous are, in our opinion, situated humans. To put it another way, we recognize "the intersubjective and social elements of subjectivity and identification for individual autonomy and moral and political action" (Mackenzie & Stoljar, 2000, p. 4)²². This is important because it allows us to make more informed decisions. It's possible that the circumstances of our society may mold us in a manner that will limit the choices we have. The

same social contexts that encourage us to be independent thinkers and instruct us on how to form our own opinions also inculcate in us the habits of believing and behaving in ways that are predetermined by social conventions (such as with gendered societal norms). In addition, it is essential, for the reasons that have been presented, that we emphasize our concept of autonomy as being more than just a positive thing for the individual; rather, it is an essential positive for society as a whole and for government in particular. For these reasons, it is essential that we highlight our concept of autonomy as being more than just a positive thing for the individual.

may be able to communicate their feeling of autonomy in a wide variety of social situations, including the workplace, the political arena, the family home, and a number of other settings. The free and independent political decisions made by the public are the responsibility of democratic institutions, and it is their duty to reflect and record those decisions. Because of this, interfering with the autonomy of other individuals is not just problematic from a moral sense, but it also has implications for society and politics. We are able to present a more nuanced explanation of why manipulation via the internet poses such a significant threat because of this understanding as well as the relevance of autonomy. One other interpretation of the term "manipulation" refers to the practice of covertly or overtly influencing the decision-making processes of another individual in such a way that the target is unconscious of the influence being exerted on them. When someone is subjected to this kind of influence, it is sometimes referred to as "covert manipulation." When this is done, the autonomy of the target is undermined in two different ways: first, it can lead them to act towards ends that they did not choose, and second, it can lead them to act for reasons that are not truly their own. Both of these outcomes are detrimental to the autonomy of the target. When something like this is done, both of these are instances of how the autonomy of the target might be compromised in the process. to possess.

Both of these consequences will have a detrimental effect on the capacity of the target to choose their own course of action on their own. Examine some examples of focused advertising in the business sector so that you can acquire a better grasp on the primary issue. The objective of individuals who would attempt to exert influence on customers in this setting is not very complicated: they want customers to make purchases. In contrast, marketers have the ability to design decision-making environments (also referred to as choice architectures) that either subtly or overtly encourage customers to purchase their products at the highest possible price, by

positioning their products as the only available option in the market (Calo, 2014). These settings have the potential to subtly or overtly encourage consumers to make purchases at the maximum price point for the items being offered.

The goal is to hasten, evade, or disrupt the negotiating process in order to promote more in-depth and contemplative decision-making that may or may not be consistent with an individual's more substantial, self-chosen aims and ideals. This may or may not be the case. The goal is to promote more in-depth and contemplative decision-making. This can be accomplished through the use of a variety of strategies, such as countdown clocks that put pressure on a person to indicate that their friends have purchased the item or to take action before an offer expires. Alternatively, this can be accomplished through the use of countdown clocks that indicate that their friends have purchased the item. Alternately, this may be done via the use of countdown clocks that highlight the fact that the item is now on sale. Naturally, these strategies are not new to non-digital contexts; the purpose of all commercial advertising, digital or otherwise, is to convince consumers to make a purchase, and concerns about misleading advertisements have been circulating for a very long time, long before advertisements migrated online. The goal of all commercial advertising, digital or otherwise, is to convince consumers to make a purchase. On the other hand, not all types of advertising, and maybe not even all types of targeted advertising, are safeguarded from the danger of being manipulated. There is a low probability that the targets of ads will be discreetly influenced in any way if the commercials serve just to inform and are shown to audiences who are already interested in the subject matter of the advertisements. Banner advertisements on websites that, for example, concentrate on healthcare, often contain a contact form for the company that they are marketing and are shown to visitors of such websites.

The question of manipulation will undoubtedly come up whenever advertisements are deceptive; that is, whenever they achieve their goals in a way that is not immediately obvious to the spectator. For instance, if the doctor were a psychiatrist, and his commercials were only shown to those who were supposed to be depressed, and only at specific times of the day when these people were believed to be most affected, then our argument would have some basis in logic. On the other hand, there is a possibility that manipulation is not as black and white as it first seems. This is something to keep in mind. We are the target of an infinite number of different attempts to exert influence over us, and it is perhaps important to point out that even though we comprehend some of these

attempts to a greater extent than others, they are all equally manipulative, regardless of how well we comprehend them. We are the focus of an unlimited number of different efforts to exert influence over us. When seen from this perspective, internet focused advertising, which is more often known as "behavioral" advertising, has the potential to be considered as exacerbating the false dynamics that are characteristic of other forms of advertising. This is because targeted advertising on the internet makes changes to individual decision structures more subtle, making it more difficult to resist giving in to temptations and the temptations that are a direct result of those temptations. This is because giving in to temptations makes it easier to give in to other temptations (Yeung , 2017). In addition, since online environments are so fluid and permeable, it is much simpler for marketers to confuse shopping with other types of one-of-a-kind circumstances. This makes it much more difficult for a person to determine whether or not they really wish to make any purchases. For example, a member of the target demographic could be chatting with friends on social media or looking up a restaurant when an advertising appears on their screen. This forces the target to balance multiple tasks, such as communication and information retrieval in this case, in addition to considering whether to respond to the marketing gimmick that reduces the target's ability to focus on any one of the tasks. In this case, the target's ability to focus on either communication or information retrieval. In this scenario, the target is required to juggle a number of different responsibilities, such as information gathering and communication. The phenomena that is often referred to as "native advertising" is an excellent illustration of this issue for a number of reasons (ads designed to look like user-generated, non-commercial content). This type of advertising is analogous to a Trojan horse because it knowingly combines activities that are carried out for the purpose of commercial gain with activities that are carried out for the purpose of non-commercial gain in order to hinder our ability to concentrate and engage in introspection.

In light of the philosophical framework that was just covered, these tactics pose a threat not only to the competence criteria that govern autonomy but also to the authenticity standards that must be met. Our capacity to negotiate about our options, to create intentions about them, and to act on those intentions is put in jeopardy by online manipulation, which willingly or covertly alters our settings in order to direct our decision-making. This puts our ability to negotiate about our alternatives, to create intentions about them, and to act on those intentions in jeopardy. We have to make choices in order to properly navigate the varied environments we encounter.

When we are subjected to manipulation online, we are coerced into acting in a manner that is contrary to our will and for reasons to which we have not given our assent. Since it enables us to recognize how we are being led to behave in ways to which we have not agreed, the capability to reflect on and verify the reasons why we act genuinely as if we were on our own is damaging to us. This is because it helps us to know why we are doing what we are doing. It is crucial to keep in mind that constraining individual liberty in the ways that were just described might result in additional harm, and it is important to keep this in mind. To begin, it is reasonable to assume that limiting the freedom of people will, in the majority of cases, result in a decline in the individuals' interests. This is a reasonable assumption to make. This is due to the fact that people who have autonomy have a propensity to protect (or at the very least make an attempt to protect) their own interests. In the event that we were rendered incapable of searching for ourselves, it is quite unlikely that our circumstances would improve as time went on. The people who have done studies on the issue of internet manipulation in the context of the business sector have done a good job of illustrating the harm that it causes, such as when we buy products that we don't need or pay more for them than we typically would for them (Calo , 2014; Nadler & McGuigan , 2018; Zdarsky , 2006; Zarsky , 2019). And it is a terrible damage that we need to treat seriously, especially given the fact that the law and policy surrounding information and internet activities (at least in the United States) often thinks that humans are capable of being safeguarded from harm. It is essential that we keep this in mind at all times (Solove , 2013). But, it is also important to understand that the damage done to wellbeing is a secondary effect of the more fundamental injury done to one's independence. To put it another way, the harm done to a person's wellbeing is a consequence of the autonomy loss that has been incurred. "Healing symptoms without addressing the cause" is an attempt to "protect consumers from challenges to their economic or other interests" without addressing the more fundamental threat to the consumers' autonomy. In other words, "healing symptoms without addressing the cause" is an attempt to "protect consumers from challenges to their economic or other interests." The American Medical Association is the source of the expression "healing symptoms without addressing the problem," which describes the practice of treating an illness without addressing its root cause. To put it another way, this is analogous to the practice of seeking to "protect patients" without addressing the underlying cause of the issue that they are experiencing. To have a better perspective on this topic, it is vital to bear in mind that

even the most kind and unselfish forms of manipulation may have unforeseen negative outcomes. Keeping this in mind will help put things into better perspective.

It is unethical to exert influence on another person, even if the goal is to assist that person in becoming more successful in achieving the goals that they have set for themselves in a more timely manner. In point of fact, this behavior is immoral. This is owing to the fact that the most considerable and damaging impact that manipulation has is felt not in the final conclusion, but rather in the decision-making process itself. A manipulator who is well-intentioned but paternalistic and cunning and who gently pushes his target to eat better, exercise more, and work harder makes his target in a sense better off – healthier, and possibly financially better off – but also hurts him. In other words, the manipulator's target is better off, mostly due to the fact that it stops one from seeing things in their actual form. Imagine for a moment that an unwanted pattern of behavior that a person has spent their whole life striving to break suddenly disappears one day for no apparent reason. This person has been working hard to break this pattern their entire lives. This individual has spent their whole life toiling away at attaining this objective. They will, without a doubt, have a feeling of relief after they have completely kicked the habit; but, it is likely that they will be rather confused and skeptical about the reasons for the change in behavior once they have accomplished this. TM Scanlon states, "I want to pick furniture for my own apartment, paintings for the walls, and even write my own classes," despite the fact that I may be a designer, an art enthusiast, or a bright graduate student. "I want to choose my own lessons" (Scanlon, 1988). This is despite the fact that any one of these things may accurately describe me. Having said that, all that we have proved is that manipulation, in any form, is always destructive; however, we have not established that it is always damaging in each and every scenario. All we have shown is that manipulation is always negative in any form.

One is able to think of situations in which the negative impact on one's liberty would be counterbalanced by the positive impact that the situation would have on one's health and well-being. (Imagine, for example, a scenario in which someone's life is in danger, and the only choice to save them is to convince them.) Despite this, situations such as this one are very rare, and it is quite unlikely that they will take place. The basic nature of influencing people online is what makes it so alarming; another reason why it is so disturbing is the prospect that it may become an acceptable component of the everyday activities that people engage in on a day-to-day basis. If we

do not stop this from happening, as the reasoning of Jeremy Waldron indicates, we will deprive our lives of something that is of the ultimate importance:

“What happens to the self-respect we give to our self-willed actions, even if they are self-willed, flawed, and misguided?”

How are we meant to make decisions that are in our best interests given the fact that so many of the choices we make are impacted by other people, who may or may not have our best interests in mind? As a direct result of this, manipulation not only results in damage being inflicted against people, but it also creates the potential for harm being inflicted onto organizations. This is accomplished while simultaneously working to undermine not just our independence but also our democracy in the process. The terms "democracy" and "autonomy" are often used synonymously. This is mostly due to the fact that the ability to self-govern is at the center of both of these political ideologies. Only because we think that people are truly capable of establishing their own independent judgments are we willing to accept institutions that are created to record and reflect such decisions.

The scandal that has surrounded Cambridge Analytica as well as the outrage that has been generated as a reaction to it provide evidence that the manipulation of information obtained from the internet for political purposes presents a threat to the perspectives and values that are held by the majority of the population. To recapitulate, the act of influencing people via the use of the internet is not only an ethical concern; rather, it is also a problem that pertains to society and politics.

Technology and Autonomy

If the reasons that have been offered up to this point are accepted, it is plainly clear that we need to develop laws and regulations that may lessen and prevent the repercussions of manipulative behavior that happens online. These laws and rules should be enacted as soon as possible. On this point, there is a point of agreement that may be reached by all of us. But this tactic is insufficient; the issue that decision-makers need to be asking is not how to avoid being manipulated via the use of the internet, but rather how to strengthen individual agency in an era when digital technology predominates. We are adding our voice to the voices of a growing number of academics and

activists, such as Frischmann, Selinger, and Zuboff, who are attempting to draw attention to the effect that digital technologies have on the levels of individuality that individuals possess. These individuals are concerned about the corrosive effect that digital technologies have on the levels of individuality that individuals possess. This is the assertion that we are making about the situation. To make headway against these problems, it is vital to offer the favorable conditions needed to support individual and group self-determination. This is the only way to achieve progress. This action is conducted not just because there is a need to protect consumers but also because of the desire to do so. Our brief exchange resulted in the formulation of some potential responses, even though none of us pretends to possess the expertise required to deliver a comprehensive response to these significant and difficult difficulties. It is essential to take note of the fact that these suggestions have deep roots in the realm of modern liberal political debate, with the discussion that was provided earlier acting as the motivation for them and providing the groundwork for their development. It is also essential to take note of the fact that modern liberal political debate is firmly rooted in the realm of modern liberalism. Yet, some European readers, and particularly some European readers, who believe that internet manipulation poses a major threat may be astonished by how restrained our response has been. This may be especially true for certain European readers. This is particularly relevant for a subset of readers located in Europe. We have decided to base our research on the conceptual and normative frameworks that are already prevalent in ongoing policy conversations in the hope that this will allow us to influence the debates that are taking place. This is the case even though we have no objection to more extreme interventions. In fact, we have no objection to more extreme interventions whatsoever.

Tal Data Is the "Fuel" That Drives Manipulative Online Activities, According to What Zarsky Writes in His Paper, Tal Data is the "fuel" that drives online manipulative actions (2019, p. 186). Our likes, interests, hobbies, etc. Without precise profiles chronicling them, future manipulators would have a much more tough time identifying our shortcomings and vulnerabilities. As a result, they would have a much more tough time utilizing those faults and vulnerabilities to advance their agendas. Without these precise profiles, future manipulators would have a much more tough time identifying our shortcomings and vulnerabilities. They would not even be able to compete if they did not have these comprehensive profiles at their disposal. It is plainly evident that there has been a constant need for a reduction in the amount of time spent utilizing digital surveillance, and this demand has been there for some time. At the very least since the beginning of the previous half

century, privacy advocates and experts who specialize in the study of privacy have been sounding the alarm about the potential problems that come with widespread surveillance.

Notwithstanding this, Zarsky's line of reasoning shows that arguments based on manipulation may be added to what he refers to as the "arsenal of analytical and doctrinal tools that permit legal engagement in the new digital world" (2019, p. 185). On the other hand, the disruption that has been caused by what appears to be manipulation of the internet in both the commercial and political spheres appears to be driving new government measures that are geared toward opposing such methods. This is the case because the upheaval has been generated in both spheres.

When asked why businesses collect so much data about us, data collectors almost always respond by arguing that the information is necessary to tailor their services to the needs and preferences of individual customers. This response is given in response to the question "why do businesses collect so much data about us?" This kind of thinking does, however, lead to several difficulties when it comes to customization. For example, Mark Zuckerberg recently gave an interview to the Wall Street Journal in which he attempted to explain the economic rationale behind Facebook. "People tell us all the time that if they are going to see commercials, they want it to be relevant." "That illustrates that we need to understand what their interests are." "People tell us all the time that if they are going to see advertisements, they want it to be relevant" (2019). Personalization may, at first glance, seem to be a benefit that is pure and untainted, but a closer examination reveals that this is not the case.

Who among us wouldn't want a personalized experience instead of a standard one?

Yet, the findings of research that were conducted on a wide range of personalization processes point to the fact that the process of individuating, and hence "personalizing," our experiences can be associated with significant dangers. These concerns have their roots in the persuasive argument that Eli Pariser presented, which, even though it has been criticized, is still uncontested: the growth of more unique, tailored experiences means the loss of more common, shared experiences. Bubble was the one who brought the matter to the attention of the wider public (2011). In addition to this, the book explores the unfavorable effects that change may have on the decision-making processes of individuals as well as groups. In addition to the customization of information environments

(focus), advances in technology have made it possible for individuals to more easily filter out information that is not relevant to them. This enables individuals to concentrate on the information that is most important to them (De Stefano, 2015). Due to the difficulties that we have recently encountered, it is conceivable that many of these answers will include the use of manipulative tactics. We are left questioning whether the positives of personalization really outweigh its drawbacks because of targeting and exploiting the one-of-a-kind decision-making gaps made accessible by digital technology. This has caused us to target and exploit these gaps. One of the numerous advantages that come along with the development of current technology is the capacity to edit material found on the internet. We shouldn't, at the very least, endorse customization wholeheartedly as the foundation for gathering more data, and we should approach the promise of a more tailored digital world with suspicion (if not cynicism).

If the main problem that is caused by changing information online is one of secrecy, then any remedy that is proposed must contain an incentive to achieve a better degree of awareness. The question that logically follows is, "How should this consciousness manifest itself?" The most common method of informing individuals of information flows and data practices is to provide them with a privacy statement, which is also sometimes referred to as "notice and consent" in common parlance. The question that naturally follows is, "How should this consciousness manifest itself?" Yeung is of the opinion that this tactic, which is the one that is used most of the time, is insufficient (2017). It is not enough to only educate a person that they are the target of manipulation in order to get rid of the effects of manipulation. To get rid of the consequences of manipulation, it is necessary to act. To achieve this objective, one must not only be aware of the person who is the target of manipulation, but one must also have knowledge about the manipulator, including who the manipulator is, the methods they use, and the reasons they use these strategies. Using standard notification formats alone is not a sufficient means to equip customers to deal with the challenges posed by online manipulation. There is no rational basis for this expectation. This is because of the well-known "transparency paradox," which states that we are compelled to keep customers from obtaining access to information that is relevant to their requirements. As a result, we must restrict consumers from gaining access to information.

Manipulation in Online Spaces

In addition, the issue of manipulation in online contexts is a problem that is far more fundamental than any one specific kind of manipulation. In a manner analogous to this, machine learning and

artificial intelligence technologies have swiftly and stealthily been given extensive decision-making capabilities across a wide range of current situations and organizations. Academics and activists have made calls for more open decision-making as a reaction to this issue, which is something that concerns many people, such as targeted advertising. Reason for this is that dishonest practices have become integral parts of the digital world. Because of this, individuals either do not notice them or prefer not to mention them since they have become so commonplace.

Two Different Workflows

It is possible to make a distinction between the many phases of the management process, which involve storing, monitoring, matching, and changing information. These steps are all included (e.g., reordering and updating information). While it has been shown by a few studies that becoming older is associated with a deterioration, the processes that are at the core of this decline still need to be researched in more depth.

The early attempt to make this distinction (Smith et al., 1998; Veltman et al., 2003) was based on comparing brain activity between normal item identification tests and manipulation activities. This comparison was done by looking at the similarities and differences between the two (eg, the Sternberg WM task). Using the Sternberg WM task, we may see one of these norms put into effect (characterized more as a manipulation task involving rendering and updating). In accordance with the explanation that Smith et al (1998). provided for these findings, the dlPFC becomes active anytime there is a need for the processing of a WM task. On the other hand, conventional item identification tests, which are also susceptible of being viewed as storage activities, did not discover any evidence of dlPFC activity. These tests are also capable of being regarded as storing activities. On the other hand, Veltman et al. (2003) pointed to a functional rather than a neuroanatomical distinction between maintenance (increased primarily in the Sternberg task) and manipulation (increased in the n-back task) processes. This was due to the evidence that both tasks result in a remarkably similar task pattern. Maintenance was increased in the Sternberg task, while manipulation was increased in the n-back task. Since both activities enhance activity in the same regions of the brain, a differentiation has been drawn between the two. It is possible to see significant activations in the cerebellum and the superior longitudinal fasciculus (SMA), in addition to the bilateral dorsolateral prefrontal cortex, left ventral prefrontal cortex, and bilateral parietal cortex. These evaluations have been used extensively as continuous recognition measures that involve the presentation of sequences of stimuli for a respectable number of years at this point.

The basis for the second way to explicate is provided by the research that was done on N-back tasks as well as the neuroanatomy that supports WM functions. These sequences may be made up of anything from letters and pictures to syllables and a whole host of other potential components as well (eg, Miller et al., 2009; Jaeggi et al., 2010).

The objective of this activity for the participants is to determine whether each item in the series is equivalent to the item for which n components were presented before. It is expected of the participants that they would respond simultaneously to each item while simultaneously keeping and updating a dynamic set of practices. According to the information that was obtained via the use of the n-back task, the "2-back" condition was much more challenging than the "1-back" condition. The reason for this was that both circumstances engaged different processes that are associated with WM. This was the case because both conditions engaged separate processes. To clarify a little more, the "1-back" activity focuses mostly on maintenance, but the "2-back" job utilizes manipulation resources.

Recent neuroimaging studies (D'Esposito et al., 1999; Rypma and D'Esposito, 1999; Tsukiura et al., 2001; Ragland et al., 2002) have shown that different regions of the brain participate in both disorders. These studies were conducted by D'Esposito et al., 1999; Tsukiura et al., 2001; Ragland et al. . The n-back task has the potential to generate various contrasts, which might point to shifts in activation that are indicative of care versus manipulation requirements (Ragland et al., 2002). To be more specific, the "1 vs 0-back" comparison indicates modifications connected with working memory maintenance (managing sensory and motor components) while concurrently constraining the contribution and updating (manipulation) resources of the central executive system. The comparison of "2-and 0-back," on the other hand, shows activation adjustments that are representative of the inclusion of central execution components (monitoring and manipulation) to the conditions for online maintenance. The comparison of "2-back to 1-back," on the other hand, mitigates the impact of the maintenance demands that are associated with both 1-back and 2-back activities and enables one to determine the resources that are necessary for WM manipulation.

It is possible, via the use of these three contrasts, to localize specific regions of the brain that participate in several different WM processes. Comparisons have been made between the specific functions that require central executive components, such as the maintenance and manipulation of sensory information (Petrides, 1994; D'Esposito et al. 1998). These comparisons have been made

to examine the similarities and differences between these functions. The similarities and differences between the functions that need central executive components have been analyzed and compared. These comparisons were accomplished by using the findings of neuroimaging research in combination with previous theoretical frameworks. This allowed for the most accurate results possible.

Even though the prefrontal cortex participated in early ventromedial WM processes (BA 44, 45, and 47), the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex is involved in the most recent ventromedial WM processes (BA 9 and 46). On the other hand, it seems more plausible than not that this divergence between functions is relative rather than absolute. [Citation needed] (Ragland et al., 2002). The objective of this study was to establish whether or whether individual variations in brain activity during the maintenance and manipulation of information in working memory (WM) in normal, healthy older individuals relate to the success of TIP as evidenced by psychophysical markers. According to our working theory, which claims that these two cognitive processes are related to one another, millisecond timing and working memory may share the same neuroanatomical substrate. This is one of the hypotheses that we are now testing. Despite this, there may be a difference in the amount of mental effort required to accomplish more challenging WM tasks, which has the potential to alter this link. WM stands for working memory.

Study of Observed Behavior Using Statistics and Psychological TOJ Indices

The ATOT values and mean activation that were derived from the ROIs are reported here to investigate the links that exist between the efficacy of TIP and the brain activity that participates in the processes of working memory (maintenance/manipulation). This was done to determine whether there is a connection between the two. Researchers found that when participants were asked to manipulate processes, additional frontal brain regions, in addition to the insula, were somewhat connected with negative correlations. This was demonstrated when the participants were given the task of manipulating processes (2 versus 1-back). In the bilateral medial frontal gyrus (BA 6, 9, and 46), the left medial frontal gyrus (BA 8), the left insula (BA 13), and the left complementary frontal gyrus (SFG), we identified connections (BA 6). In addition to this, we discovered connections in the region of the right medial frontal gyrus (BA 13). . This leads one to believe that the more effective TIP (which was shown at lower ATOTs) is due to increased activations occurring solely in the regions outlined above during the process of WM manipulation.

On the other hand, neither the one-back state nor the zero-back state nor the maintenance operations had any statistically significant relevance for these associations. This demonstrates that the temporal resolution makes a far less significant contribution to the maintenance of the system. Because of these connections, many regions of the brain that were similarly and strongly related with temporal resolution were able to be discovered within the WM network. Brain Network Involved in WM Care The brain network that participates in care and that is detailed here (Figure 4A) is comparable to those that have been documented in other types of study (Tsukiura et al., 2001; Ragland et al., 2002; Crottaz-Herbette et al., 2004; Narayanan et al., 2005). (Tsukiura et al., 2001; Ragland et al., 2002; Crottaz-Herbette et al., 2004; Narayanan et al., 2005). The research that was described above did not base its findings on the participants' ages (which were maintained throughout the subjects' lifespan, which ranged from 18 to 53 years), the target modality (visual, auditory), or the method that was used. The premotor cortex of the left hemisphere (BA 6), the superior fronto-temporal gyrus (BA 8), and the precentral network of the gyrus (BA 44) have all been defined in the past using a variety of methodologies. For instance, Narayanan et al. (2005) used an item recognition test and discovered that an increase in memory load (task difficulty) was detected in the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex and ventromedial They found that it was associated to increased activity in the prefrontal cortex. This study was conducted using an item recognition test. In addition, the activations that we found in the inferior parietal lobe (IPL) and the superior parietal lobe (BA 7) include the storage of knowledge, which is something that is discussed rather often in research. (Awh et al. et al . , 1996; Jonides et al., 1998). These findings, which are consistent with the findings of Owen (1997) and D'Esposito et al., reveal that the vIPFC contributes to maintenance, and this contribution is also reflected in the activations of BA 44. Additionally, these findings show that this contribution is reflected in the activations of BA 44. (1998). On the other hand, several studies have shown that there is activity in the dlPFC during maintenance, particularly in the right MFG (BA 9, 46; Tsukiura et al., 2001). (BA 9, 46; Tsukiura et al., 2001). The findings of Tsukiura et al. (2001) may have something to do with the more complex care methods and concomitantly more sophisticated techniques that have been employed, both of which cause a delay in patient response. The exceedingly sophisticated work that was used in the study by Tsukiura et al. is predicted to be less involved in this endeavor, which will include a smaller network of structures (2001). (2001).

The brain networks that were engaged in grooming and manipulation activities were almost identical; however, the network connected to manipulation had larger and more diffuse activity than the network associated to grooming. This is most likely a result of the more intricate processes that are required for manipulation, which requires constant rearrangement and updating of the material that is being investigated.

These findings provide further evidence in favor of the concept that a sizeable portion of the core WM system is, at any one-time during manipulation, actively involved in the frontoparietal network (Tsukiura et al., 2001; Ragland et al., 2002; Veltman et al., 2003; Schmidt et al. , 2009; Barbey et al. others, 2013). (Tsukiura et al., 2001; Ragland et al., 2002; Veltman et al., 2003; Schmidt et al. , 2009; Barbey et al. others, 2013). This is consistent with the fundamental functional distinction between manipulation and manipulation. In a more recent research (Luis et al., 2015), activations in the cerebellum were also shown to occur during WM tasks.

Cooper et al. (2012) brought attention to the significance of these integrative processes in executive functions and other cognitive tasks. They predicted that the cerebellum plays an integrative role in the processing of motor information. In addition, they advanced the hypothesis that the cerebellum performs an integrative role during the processing of sensory data. It has been shown that the cerebellum is involved not just in working memory but also in a variety of tasks related to the temporal lobe (Ben- Yehudah et al., 2007). (Ben- Yehudah et al., 2007). The activations in the cerebellar cortex of senior patients that were revealed in our experiment may be attributed to the engagement of compensatory mechanisms that permit more sophisticated processing while manipulation is taking place. Given the natural decline that comes with advancing age, it's possible that processing of this kind may be more difficult for those who are older.

In conclusion, our findings are, for the most part, consistent with those of earlier studies that made use of the n-back task in older participants and provide evidence for the involvement of the vast fronto-parieto-cerebellar network in working memory (WM) processes (Owen et al., 2005; Luis et al., 2015). These studies were conducted in younger adults.

Asymmetrical development of verbal working memory across the hemispheres in older brains

Previous research (Hart et al., 2005) suggested that the kind of material (syllables) used in the n-back task in this study may preferentially excite regions located in the left hemisphere of the brain.

This judgment was supported by the findings of the recent inquiry that was conducted. In most people, the hemisphere of the brain that is responsible for language has a circuit that is more extensive for the processing of linguistic content in memory (Bradshaw and Nettleton , 1981; Gazzaniga , 2000; Weber et al., 2007; Hellige , 2008). (Bradshaw and Nettleton , 1981; Gazzaniga , 2000; Weber et al., 2007; Hellige , 2008). It is quite likely that the electrical neuroimaging studies will back up the auditory evoked potentials that were acquired from the participants when they were doing the TOJ task (Bernasconi et al., 2010, 2011). (Bernasconi et al., 2010, 2011). They found that activity in the left posterior perisylvian areas, as opposed to the right, acts as a signal of early encoding phases of paired stimuli. These phases are necessary for the perception of the sequence of the stimuli, as well as the accurate behavioral execution of the auditory TOJ task. They found that this activity acts as a signal of early encoding phases.

An indicator of decreased structural, neuromodulatory, and hemodynamic reactivity is insufficient activation. On the other hand, one kind of increased activation that is common in the elderly population is called overactivation. Those who are older tend to digest information less well, which might lead to compensatory behaviors. These are the reactions that occur in response to processing faults that have been identified. The loss of white matter (WM) that occurs naturally with aging means that the activation of other parts of the brain may be necessary to maintain WM (and maybe other cognitive processes) (Park and Reuter -Lorenz, 2009). (Park and Reuter -Lorenz, 2009). Considering these findings, we have conclude that TIP has the potential to make WM processes more efficient, in particular during the manipulation phase, which makes use of more complex resources than the maintenance phase does. It is possible that the increased activity in manipulation is the consequence of delivering more effective TIP to WM to delay the effects of age-related WM impairments. To investigate these difficulties in more depth, further research is necessary.

A female body with a low body mass index (BMI) is associated with ideas of better health, more prestige, and higher socioeconomic position, while a female body with a high BMI is typically associated with negative connotations. This is since undernourishment is an extremely rare occurrence in Western countries. Experts are of the opinion that the delicate ideal is beginning to take on a more global character, and they believe that this may be explained, at least in part, because of the globalization of Western media. It's possible that this also explains why, for instance, South Africans who moved to Britain began to favor Western body standards for their

appearance as they became older. In addition, muscularity may relate to the same traits, analogous to the way that Western society associates thinness with health and high status. For instance, participants' ratings of muscular male bodies as physically healthy, clean, and attractive were shown to be biased in their favor, indicating that people had positive biases toward muscular male bodies. In a similar vein, research has shown that thin female bodies are associated with negative stereotypes among the general population. They have an unfavorable preconception about non-muscular endomorphs and see them as physically ill, filthy, and unattractive. Moreover, they have negative preconceptions about endomorphs in general. Instead, individuals have these adverse attitudes toward muscular endomorphs in their minds. It is not unusual for fictional Western characters to have a high socioeconomic position and be associated with positive qualities when they appear in the media. For instance, in the highest-grossing films produced between 1980 and 2006, muscular individuals had a greater chance of playing major roles. These characters are also more likely to be romantically associated with other people, have more sexual activity, and experience more successful conclusions. Because muscular male figures now dominate a significant portion of Western media, where they are frequently given a positive value and where digital manipulation is frequently used to further enhance muscular body features, such media exposure is likely to increase preferences for idealized body types and 'normality' in female bodies, just as such media exposure is likely to increase preferences for idealized body types and 'normality' in male bodies. Since it influences "perception," it is especially important. Actually, it is essential to focus further research on this under-studied area of male muscularity preferences in order to determine whether or not seeing idealized male media photographs influences what such men afterwards believe to be 'ideal' or 'normal' standards.

Studies have, for the most part, neglected to consider male preferences for muscularity. If we want to be successful in our efforts to devise strategies for promoting male body image in Western countries, it is equally important that we investigate the factors that lie behind the changes in preferences that have taken place. A recent research aimed to analyze whether changes in muscularity preferences are the outcome of our "visual diet." This is the premise that only exposure to certain body types may vary our preferences. The methodology of Boothroyd et al. were used for this investigation (the idea that only exposure to certain body shapes can change our preferences). It is essential either because of processes known as "associative learning" (the Western assumption that muscularity is associated with positive attributes of health and status) or

as a mix of the two of these factors. It is critical that research be conducted to determine whether male and female audiences' tastes for a muscular physique in men have changed over time. We argue that it is reasonable to expect that the choices of both men and women will be affected because both men and women are exposed to media messages about what is attractive, normative, and high-status in a male body. Because of this, it is important to include female respondents in our sample because we are exposed to media messages about what is attractive, normative, and high-status in a male body. Actually, earlier studies on adaptation to muscularity have discovered impacts for both men and women when they are exposed to male and female stimuli. These findings pertain to adaptation to muscularity. This other study, on the other hand, made use of neutral stimuli (such as images of men posing in a standard anatomical position while wearing standardized tight gray tank tops and shorts), but it did not investigate whether there was sensitivity to visual adaptation as a result of this choice. When the stimuli employed have a positive value (like males clothed in high-status apparel or guys standing in a high-status posture with different muscle mass, for example), the likelihood of it occurring increases (such as men dressed in high-status clothing, high-status stance of different muscle mass).

This is a question that is being investigated in the work that is currently being done. In the first study's manipulation conditions, the participants saw photographs of either desired male bodies with high muscle mass, desirable male bodies with low muscle mass, neutral male bodies with high muscle mass, or neutral male bodies.

It is important to assume, in accordance with the visual diet theory, that a change in preference for muscular (or non-muscled) male bodies will result from exposure to images of muscular (or non-muscled) male bodies, regardless of whether they are a feature of the image. This is the case even if the muscles do not appear in the image. However, according to the associative learning hypothesis, it is important to assume that preferences for a more muscular (or non-muscled) male body type will only move in the direction of positive male bodies, regardless of whether they are muscular or not. This is the case even though it is important to assume that preferences for a more muscular male body type will move in the direction of positive male bodies. If the data indicates to a visual dieting mechanism, then this suggests that the media's overemphasis on muscular male bodies is likely influencing both our preferences towards what a normal male body should look like as well as our views of what a muscular male body should look like. This reveals that the

mechanism responsible for the visual diet oversees the visual diet itself. On the other hand, if the evidence points to associative learning mechanisms, then it means that changes in muscularity preferences between men and women can be explained by the internalization of the positive connotations that are attributed to muscularity in Western culture. This is the case if the evidence points to associative learning mechanisms (such as health and higher intelligence). (such as improved health and a more developed intellect). condition) and it's possible that this is because of how the media depicts males who have a lot of muscle mass. A similar study was mentioned earlier, and it is important to assume that viewing pictures of people with high (or low) muscle mass may also increase (or decrease) preferences for muscularity, and that this shift is likely to be more pronounced. This assumption is based on the previous research.

Muscular Preferences in a Western Population

Many different manipulation settings were constructed to evaluate the degree to which visual diet or associative learning processes offer the best explanation for such variations in body preferences. The notion of a visual diet is supported by the data when examined as a whole, particularly regarding images displaying minimal quantities of muscle mass. This is especially the case when the data are evaluated in the context of the photographs. According to the visual diet theory, the act of gazing at a picture of a male body that has a high muscle mass as opposed to an image of a male body that has a low muscular mass should produce a preference shift toward male bodies that have a greater muscle mass. The image in question has a positive or neutral value. After being exposed to guys who had a low muscle mass, the participants' preference for following muscularity decreased. This effect was seen regardless of whether the value of male bodies was positive or neutral. The conclusion that was reached based on the prediction is given some credibility by these pieces of evidence. This effect was not observed in other circumstances (i.e., by including neutral males, according to the associative learning hypothesis, high muscle mass males should have little or no effect on one's later muscularity preference). Exposure to large muscle mass increased men's preference for muscularity in some circumstances (i.e., where these images have a positive value as in Case 1), but this effect was not observed in other circumstances (i.e., where these images have a negative value as in Case 1). These results may be interpreted in terms of the associative learning processes that are at play here (preferably a larger change than any observed change in aspiration conditions).

Since we did not find any evidence to suggest that there was a substantial three-way interaction between phase, muscularity, and valence, we are able to draw the conclusion that the interaction between aspirational and neutral imagery was consistent about phase and muscularity. There was still a significant interaction between phase and muscularity once gender was included as an extra marker; however, there were no higher order interactions, which shows that people were equally susceptible to the effects of visual diet. In addition, exploratory analyses show that a participant's Muscularity score does not affect the likelihood of changing muscularity preferences after being exposed to men with either high or low muscle mass. This is the case even though the participants were shown men with either high or low levels of muscle mass. The results of this study disprove the notion that the participant's Muscularity score would have an influence of this kind. This result is consistent with the findings of other research, which found that dissatisfaction with one's physique had little influence on the outcomes of weight adaptation in women. This conclusion is in accordance with the findings of past studies. This contradicts the results of a few investigations that were conducted in the past and published in academic journals. Those people who had previous anxieties were demonstrated to be more vulnerable to the visual adaptation effects in body size, as revealed by the results of these researchers.

Based on these results, associative learning processes may be, to some extent, be the driving force behind changes in people's wishes for masculine muscles to be present in their bodies. The findings of Condition 6 cannot be explained by the visual diet theory; rather, it must be the consequence of individuals responding positively to muscleless masculine bodies and adjusting their preferences because of this response. The visual diet hypothesis has been shown to be incorrect (a process known as associative learning). According to the associative learning theory, if you followed examples of aspirational high muscular mass in men with examples of neutral low muscular mass in men (Condition 5), it would likely reinforce their preferences for the aspirational high muscular mass in men. It is important to take note of the fact that these findings are remarkably like those that were presented in an earlier study that was published. According to the findings of this study, the researchers found that subjects' preferences for thinness decreased after being shown photos of fine detail that did not induce aspiration, in addition to images of huge objects that did induce aspiration. On the other hand, seeing aspirationally thin pictures alongside larger images that did not induce aspirational thinness did not result in a discernible shift in the participants' preferences regarding thinness. The findings of this investigation are remarkably like those of the most current

study, which was conducted not long ago. Despite this, we feel that further research in this area need to make use of stimuli that are more suited for muscularity. While lean muscle mass and fat mass are inextricably linked, it is known that the proportion of lean muscle mass to fat mass in men is tied to health in several different ways. Even though the two are connected, they cannot be separated (because larger people have more fat and muscle). The genetic instructions for coding an individual's fat mass and their muscle mass are not the same, according to research that was conducted on adaptability. This is because the participants' subjective normality points migrate in the direction of the alteration photos along the axis that corresponds to fat versus muscle. This was shown to be the case.

According to the findings, the only groups that were able to reach similar levels of growth were those that were either given structured input or processing instructions; however, the group that was given explicit information did not yet make comparable headway. The understanding that the progression of the learners could be related to the organized input activities in which they engaged was the most important and significant lesson from this inquiry. Students who participated in structured input activities before to receiving explicit information about the target form performed at the same level as students who participated in structured input activities after the receipt of explicit information about the target form. Since that time, a similar primary finding has been discovered in the Italian future tense (Benati, 2004a), the Italian noun-adjective agreement (Benati, 2004b), the French negative plus indefinite article (Wong, 2004), the Spanish object pronoun (Sanz, 2004), the Japanese past forms, and positive versus negative present forms (Lee & Benati, 2007a), in addition to the Russian case mark, the German case mark, and the Spanish direct object pronoun. In addition to this major finding, we found that. (VanPatten Collopy , Price , Borst and Qualin , 2013). After doing an analysis of the data that measures the component that plays a causal role in processing, one can arrive at the following conclusion:

The variable that functions as the underlying cause of the processing instruction is the one that involves the execution of structured input activities.

in traditional sciences such as archeology (for example, Morrison 2006), and in multidisciplinary subjects such as resilience (for example, Gunderson and Holling 2002), reveals that adaptability to changing social- ecological systems, including climatic factors, is not a novel aspect of human civilizations. This thesis is supported by the fact that human civilizations have persisted for a

substantial length of time and constitute an important piece of evidence. Yet, what is new is people's understanding of how "dangerous" climate change is, as well as the scale and intensity of the effects that have already been experienced and those that are expected, which offers more impetus to concentrate on adaptation measures. This can be seen as a positive development (Adger et al. 2007). In addition, Adger et al. (2007) highlight the fact that there is not a great deal of multisectoral studies of the costs and benefits of global adaptation that are now accessible.

So how should adaptation efforts be evaluated in a world that is becoming more international?

What criteria should be based on for our approaches?

The ideas that form the basis of adaptation may be traced back to a wide variety of academic fields. Each of these fields has its own special focus as well as repercussions for how society operates and what it achieves. For example, Smit et al. (1999) draw attention to the many distinct origins of adaptation that may be found in fields such as ecology, natural disasters, and risk management. The well-established occurrence of the phenomena in cultural ecology is used by Head (2010) as an example to illustrate this point. Orlove (2009) conducts research into the evolution of the term's use and finds that English definitions of adaptation from the 17th century relate to a process of transformation and contain the meanings of "adapt" or "fit" in reference to an external occurrence. This information is included in the article. This conclusion lends credence to Orlove's notion that the phrase was initially conceived of to express a reaction to a shifting natural setting. component to consider. He began to see more tangible applications in the sphere of scientific study towards the middle of the 19th century. For instance, Charles Darwin used the term "natural selection" in the year 1859 to describe the process by which organisms and species gradually become more adapted to their respective environments. He did so to explain evolution. He used this expression to speak about "evolution," and he was the one who named this process "evolution." John Dewey (1916) relied on Charles Darwin's account of adaptation to explain how people and societies can respond to or transform environments to achieve social change and reach their full potential. Dewey's explanation was based on the idea that people and societies can reach their full potential. The argument that Dewey offered was predicated on the notion that individuals and society can realize their full potential only when they are given the opportunity to do so. Orlove (2009) draws attention to the fact that Dewey's notion is primarily responsible for the widespread usage of the

word to define a person's ability to adapt to a variety of different changing dynamic settings. Adaptability can be defined as the capacity of an individual to adjust well to new and different circumstances. In a manner that is analogous, Nelson et al. (2007) highlights the fact that adaptation is tied to the conceptual decision-making processes and the following actions that are taken to address the implications of change. However, although most of the focus in discussions about public policy has been on taking action, very little emphasis has been placed on fair decision-making methods or the nature and severity of the ramifications of complying with the policy. This is even though the majority of the attention has been centered on taking action.

It is very unlikely that we will be able to accurately foresee all the repercussions that our actions will have over a wide range of spatial, chronological, and cultural dimensions. This is because of the complexity of these factors. This is since the whole repercussions will be dependent on the particular setting in which they are put into effect. Yet, in the case of human systems, it is necessary to either make internal changes, also known as adaptations, or external adjustments, such as manipulations, to respond to social-ecological dynamics. This is due to the nature of human systems, which is that they are complex adaptive systems (either on an individual or societal scale, depending on circumstances). The emphasis of adaptation is on the outside environment, but the focus of manipulation is on who or what has been affected. This focus on who or what has been transformed is a key difference between adaptation and manipulation. We argue that internal changes to social-ecological systems that consider both social and ecological aspects provide significantly greater learning opportunities and possibilities for building adaptive capacity and securing a sustainable future. This is because these changes consider both social and ecological aspects. This is since the modifications in question take into account both social and environmental factors. Over the course of history, the only persons who have investigated the prospect that data collectors may utilize information about individuals to impose control over those individuals have been academics who are concerned in privacy and surveillance. Concern over this issue is rising among the general community, as seen by their expressions (e.g., Abramowitz , 2017; Doubek , 2017; Vayena , 2018). If a person knows (or can reasonably assume) a person's preferences, hobbies, and habits, in addition to friends and acquaintances, education and work, physical health, and financial circumstances, that person is able to have a significant impact on the person who is known to them. This is because friends and acquaintances, education and work, physical health, and financial circumstances are all interconnected (Richards, 2013).).1 As a consequence of this,

the individual who is most familiar with them is in a better position to comprehend what motivates their aspirations, what their limitations and vulnerabilities are, when they are most receptive to being influenced, and how to most successfully construct calls and pitches for them. Although the majority of these technologies were developed by corporations such as Google and Facebook — which discovered advertising as a way to monetize the treasure trove of personal information they collect about internet users — at first, this meant that researchers investigating the issue were at the mercy of the whims of advertisers. However, in recent years, this has changed (Zuboff, 2015).). Because of this, for a period of time, academic concerns were (appropriately) focused on commercial advertising practices, and policy solutions were focused on modernizing privacy and consumer protection regulations to account for the new capabilities of data-driven advertising technologies. Both focuses have been appropriate. Hence (e.g. , Calo , 2014). (e.g. , Calo , 2014). (For more reading, see Turow (2012) as well as Nadler and McGuigan (2018)). In his article, "The Digitalization of Commerce Is Dramatically Affecting the Power of Corporations to Influence Customers on a Personal Level," Ryan Calo sees that "The digitalization of commerce is dramatically affecting the power of corporations to influence customers on a personal level." Businesses will have the ability to discover and capitalize on the boundaries of their capability to pursue the interests of each individual customer. On the other hand, the breadth of these concerns has greatly expanded in the more recent times (2014, page 999).

Conclusion

Many individuals are coming to face the reality that the risk of targeted advertising is not limited to the realm of commercialism because of recent concerns voiced on the use of information technology to influence elections throughout the world in 2016 and 2017. If other social media services make use of the ad targeting tools that are made available by websites like YouTube and Facebook, they have the potential to have a substantial impact not just on political campaigns but also on the choices and actions of voters (Vaidhyanathan , 2018; Yeung , 2017; Zuiderveen Borgesius et al., 2018). Concerns have been raised because of the event involving Cambridge Analytica ("Cambridge Analytica and Facebook: The Scandal so Far", 2018; see also Abramowitz , 2017; Doubek , 2017; Vayena , 2018).

The data analytics company involved in this scandal created profiles of voters in the United States, the United Kingdom, France, Germany, and other countries, and then identified those voters with

"evidence of the pendulum swinging further in the other direction." The scientists focused their attention on the specific harms caused by internet influencing tactics in certain situations. They are making a conscious effort to move away from passing judgment and toward looking at the bigger picture. *Re-Engineering* was newly published, and it was written by Frischmann and Evan Selinger. They examine a wide range of interconnected phenomena in their book *Humanity*, which they refer to collectively as "Techno-social engineering." These phenomena influence the ways in which humans think, perceive, and act (2018, p. 4). Frischmann and Selinger, who operate on a large scale reminiscent of the criticism of technology from the middle of the 20th century (such as that of Lewis Mumford or Jacques Ellul), from the "micro-level" to the "meso-level" and refers to the "macro level", technologies that are changing the way in which we conduct and understand our lives, viral media. [Citation needed] (2018, p. 270). A similar point of view is presented in Shoshana Zuboff's book "The Age of Monitoring," which was released in 2019. He raises the alarm in his book *Capitalism* about the use of information technology to bring about what he refers to as "behavior change." Zuboff argues that because this practice has become so pervasive and so central to the workings of the modern knowledge economy, we have entered a new era in the history of political economy. Zuboff's book *Capitalism* raises the alarm about the use of information technology to bring about "behavior change." These events help call attention to the idea that unethical corporate practices are only one of many issues that are at risk here. There are many other things that are at stake here. When information about us is used to try to influence our decision making, not only does this make it more difficult for us to safeguard our own interests, but it also constitutes a violation of our independence.

On the other hand, putting certain boundaries on the conclusions of the research can out to be extremely beneficial. The concepts of "techno-social engineering" and "surveillance capitalism" are too expansive to be applied in a surgical manner; the first seeks to unearth a fundamental truth about the nature of our human relationship to technology, and the second identifies the broad set of economic imperatives that currently structure technology development and the technology industry. Neither concept can be applied in a surgical manner because they seek to unearth a fundamental truth about the nature of our human relationship to technology. None of these concepts can be implemented surgically in any meaningful way. Our intervention needs to concentrate on more attainable targets to be effective. During the previous few years, there has been an increasing public outrage against a particular collection of abuses that make use of

information technology. These types of wrongdoings are what many people mean when they speak about "manipulation online" (for example, Abramowitz (2017), Doubek (2017), and Vayena (2018)). In the coming lines, we shall guess and justify this complaint.

In the first part of this essay, we defined manipulation by separating it from similar concepts such as persuasion, coercion, dishonesty, and nudging. We also explored why information technology is so well-suited for the facilitation of manipulation. The second section of this debate centered on theorizing and rationalizing this problem. In the second part, we discussed about the harmful effects of influencing people online, which is also known as utilizing information technology to influence people, and we focused our attention first on the danger that it presents to people's individual autonomy. In conclusion, we presented some proposals on how future policy efforts should be focused to decrease incidences of online manipulation and raise degrees of autonomy in human-technology relationships. These proposals were provided in the context of a debate on how to decrease instances of internet manipulation.

References

- A. Lipsitz, K. Kallmeyer, M. Ferguson, and A. Abas. "Counting on blood donors: Increasing the impact of social reminder calls." *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 19, (1989). 1057 – 1067.
- Akerlof, George A. and Robert J. Shiller, 2015, *Phishing for Phools : The Economics of Manipulation and Deception*, Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Aristotle *Rhetoric*, (W. Rhys Roberts, Translator). (Mineola, New York: Dover Publications, Inc., 2004). 1355a20.
- Arneson, Richard J., 2015, "Nudge and Shove", *Social Theory and Practice*, 41(4): 668–691. doi:10.5840/soctheorpract201541436
- Arrington, Robert L., 1982, "Advertising and Behavior Control", *Journal of Business Ethics*, 1(1): 3–12. doi:10.1007/BF00382800
- Australian Psychological Society *Stress & wellbeing: How Australians are coping with life: The findings of the Australian Psychological Society Stress and Wellbeing in Australia Survey 2015*

- Barbey , AK, Koenigs , M., and Grafman, J. (2013). Dorsolateral prefrontal contributions to human working memory. *Cortex* 49, 1195–1205. doi: 10.1016/j.cortex.2012.05.022
- Barnhill, Anne, 2014, “What Is Manipulation?” in Coons & Weber 2014: 51–72. doi:10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199338207.003.0003
- Baron, Marcia, 2003, “Manipulativeness”, *Proceedings and Addresses of the American Philosophical Association*, 77(2): 37–54. doi:10.2307/3219740
- Baron-Cohen, S., & Wheelwright, S. (2003). The Friendship Questionnaire: An investigation of adults with Asperger Syndrome or high functioning Autism, and normal sex differences. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 33, 509-517.
- Beauchamp, Tom L., 1984, “Manipulative Advertising”, *Business and Professional Ethics Journal*, 3(3/4): 1–22. doi:10.5840/bpej198433/426
- Belohrad , Radim , 2019, “The Nature and Moral Status of Manipulation”, *Acta Analytica*, 34(4): 447–62. doi:10.1007/s12136-019-00407-y
- Benenson , JF, & Christakos, A. (2003). The greater fragility of females versus males' closest same-sex friendships. *Child Development*, 74, 1123-1129.
- Benn, Stanley I., 1967, “Freedom and Persuasion”, *Australasian Journal of Philosophy*, 45(3): 259–275. doi:10.1080/00048406712341211
- Ben- Yehudah , G., Guediche , S., and Fiez , JA (2007). Cerebellar contributions to verbal working memory: beyond cognitive theory. *Cerebellum* 6, 193–201. doi: 10.1080/14734220701286195
- Bernasconi , F., Grivel , J., Murray, MM, and Spierer, L. (2010). Interhemispheric coupling between the posterior sylvian regions impacts successful auditory temporal order judgment. *Neuropsychology* 48, 2579–2585. doi: 10.1016/j.neuropsychologia.2010.05.004
- Bernasconi , F., Manuel, AL, Murray, MM, and Spierer, L. (2011). Pre-stimulus beta oscillations within left posterior sylvian regions impact auditory temporal order judgment accuracy. *int. J. Psychophys* . 79, 244–248. doi: 10.1016/j.ijpsycho.2010.10.017

- Binder, M. (2015). Neural correlates of audiovisual temporal processing-comparison of temporal order and simultaneity judgments. *Neuroscience* 300, 432–447. doi: 10.1016/j.neuroscience.2015.05.011
- Black, PJ, Woodworth, M., & Porter, S. (2014). The Big Bad Wolf? The relation between the Dark Triad and the interpersonal assessment of vulnerability. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 67, 52-56.
- Bland, JM, and Altman, DG (1995). Multiple significance tests: the Bonferroni method. *br. Med. J.* 310:170. doi: 10.1136/bmj.310.6973.170
- Blieszner , R., & Adams, RG (1992). *Adult Friendship*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Blumenthal- Barby , JS, and Hadley Burroughs, 2012, “Seeking Better Health Outcomes: The Ethics of Using the 'Nudge'”, *American Journal of Bioethics*, 12(2): 1–10. doi:10.1080/15265161.2011.634481
- Blumenthal- Barby , JS, 2012, “Between Reason and Coercion: Ethically Permissible Influence in Health Care and Health Policy Contexts”, *Kennedy Institute of Ethics Journal*, 22(4): 345–366.
- Booth- Kewley , S., Larson, GE, & Miyoshi, SK (2007). Social desirability effects on computerized and paper-and-pencil questionnaires. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 23, 463-477.
- Boothroyd LG, et al., Television exposure predicts body size ideals in rural Nicaragua. *British Journal of Psychology*, 2016. 107(4): p. 752–767. pmid:26910312
- Boothroyd LG, Tovée MJ, and Pollet TV, Visual diet versus associative learning as mechanisms of change in body size preferences. *PLoS One*, 2012. 7(11): p. e48691. pmid:23144929
- Bowers, L., 2003, “Manipulation: Searching for an Understanding”, *Journal of Psychiatric and Mental Health Nursing*, 10(3): 329–334. doi:10.1046/j.1365-2850.2003.00603.x
- Bradshaw, J., and Nettleton, N. (1981). The nature of hemispheric specialization in man. *behav . BrainSci.* 4.51–63. doi: 10.1017/s0140525x00007548

- Braiker , Harriet, 2004, *Who's Pulling Your Strings? How to Break the Cycle of Manipulation and Regain Control of Your Life*, first edition, Maidenhead: McGraw-Hill Education.
- Buhusi , CV, and Meck , WH (2005). What makes us tick? Functional and neural mechanisms of interval timing. *Nat. Rev. neurosci.* 6, 755–765. doi: 10.1038/nrn1764
- Buss, David M., 1992, “Manipulation in Close Relationships: Five Personality Factors in Interactional Context”, *Journal of Personality*, 60(2): 477–499. doi:10.1111/j.1467-6494.1992.tb00981.x
- Buss, David M., Mary Gomes, Dolly S. Higgins, and Karen Lauterbach, 1987, “Tactics of Manipulation”, *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology: Personality Processes and Individual Differences*, 52(6): 1219–1229.
- Buss, Sarah, 2005, “Valuing Autonomy and Respecting Persons: Manipulation, Seduction, and the Basis of Moral Constraints”, *Ethics*, 115(2): 195–235. doi:10.1086/426304
- Cabeza, R. (2002). Hemispheric asymmetry reduction in older adults: the HAROLD model. *Psychol. Aging* 17, 85–100. doi: 10.1037//0882-7974.17.1.85
- Campbell, A. (1999). Staying alive: Evolution, culture, and women's intrasexual aggression. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 22, 203-252.
- Carhart, R. (1971). Observations on relations between thresholds for pure tones and for speech. *J. Speech Hear. Discord.* 36, 476–483. doi: 10.1044/jshd.3604.476
- Cave, Eric M., 2007, “What's Wrong with Motivational Manipulation?” *Ethical Theory and Moral Practice*, 10(2): 129–144. doi:10.1007/s10677-006-9052-4
- Challinor KL, et al., Body size and shape misperception and visual adaptation: An overview of an emerging research paradigm. *Journal of International Medical Research*, 2017. 45(6): p. 2001–2008. pmid:29076380
- Christie, R., & Geis, FL (1970). *Studies in Machiavellianism*. London: Academic Press.

- Conway, AR, Kane, MJ, Bunting, MF, Hambrick, DZ, Wilhelm, O., and Engle, RW (2005). Working memory span tasks: a methodological review and user's guide. *psycho _ bull. Rev.* 12, 769–786. doi: 10.3758/bf03196772
- Cooper, FE, Grube, M., Von Kriegstein , K., Kumar, S., English, P., Kelly, TP, et al. (2012). Distinct critical cerebellar subregions for components of verbal working memory. *Neuropsychologia* 50, 189–197. doi: 10.1016/j.neuropsychologia.2011.11.017
- Coull , JT, and Nobel , AC (2008). Dissociating explicit timing from temporal expectation with fMRI. *Curr. opin . neurobiol .* 18, 137–144. doi: 10.1016/j.conb.2008.07.011
- Coull , JT, Cheng, RK, and Meck , WH (2011). Neuroanatomical and neurochemical substrates of timing. *Neuropsychopharmacology* 36, 3–25. doi: 10.1038/npp.2010.113
- Cowan, N. (2008). What are the differences between long-term, short-term, and working memory? *prog. Brain Res.* 169, 323–338. doi: 10.1016/s0079-6123(07)00020-9
- Craig, AD (2002). How do you feel? Interoception : the sense of the physiological condition of the body. *Nat. Rev. neurosci.* 3,655–666. doi: 10.1038/nrn894
- Craig, AD (2009). Emotional moments across time: a possible neural basis for time perception in the anterior insula. *Philos. Trance. R. Soc. london _ B Biol. sci.* 364, 1933–1942. doi: 10.1098/rstb.2009.0008
- Crottaz-Herbette , S., Anagnoson , RT, and Menon, V. (2004). Modality effects in verbal working memory: differential prefrontal and parietal responses to auditory and visual stimuli. *NeuroImage* 21, 340–351. doi: 10.1016/j.neuroimage.2003.09.019
- D'Esposito , M., Aguirre, GK, Zarahn , E., Ballard, D., Shin, RK, and Lease, J. (1998). Functional MRI studies of spatial and nonspatial working memory. *Cognit. Brain Res.* 7, 1–13. doi: 10.1016/s0926-6410(98)00004-4
- David-Barrett T., Rotkirch A., Carney J., Behncke Izquierdo I., Kreams JA, et al. (2015). Women favor dyadic relationships, but men prefer clubs: Cross-cultural evidence from social

- networking. PLoS ONE, 10, e0118329.
- Dennis, NA, and Cabeza, R. (2008). “Neuroimaging of healthy cognitive aging,” in *The Handbook of Aging and Cognition*, 3rd Edn. eds F. Craik and T. Salthouse (New York, NY: Psychology Press), 10–63.
- Duffy PJ, Shiflett , S., & Downey, RG (1977). Locus of control: Dimensionality and predictability using Likert scales. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 62, 214-219.
- EJ Austin et al. Associations of the managing the emotions of others (MEOS) scale with personality, the Dark Triad and trait EI *Personality and Individual Differences* (2014)
- EJ Austin et al. Development and preliminary validation of a scale to assess the emotions of others *Personality and Individual Differences* (2013)
- American Psychological Association & Harris Interactive Work and well-being survey (2016)
- EJ Austin et al. Emotional intelligence, Machiavellianism and emotional manipulation: Does EI have a dark side? *Personality and Individual Differences* (2007)
- Fischer, Alexander, and Christian Illies . 2018. “Modulated Feelings: The Pleasurable-Ends-Model of Manipulation.” *Philosophical Inquiries IV* (2): 25–44.
- Fisher, Alexander. 2017. *Manipulation. Zur Theorie und Ethik einer Form der Beeinflussung* . Berlin: Suhrkamp .
- Fisher, Alexander. 2021. “Das Handwerk der Verführung : Manipulation, Sexualität und Glaube .” In *Sexualisierte Gewalt in kirchlichen Kontexten [Sexual Violence in the Context of the Church]. Neue interdisziplinäre Perspektive [New Interdisciplinary Perspectives]*, edited by Mathias Wirth, Isabelle Noth , and Silvia Schroer , 189–214. Berlin: De Gruyter.
- Fradkin C., et al., Associations between socioeconomic status and obesity in diverse, young adolescents: Variation across race/ethnicity and gender. *Health Psychology*, 2015. 34(1): p. 1. pmid:25133824
- G. Breen and J. Matusitz . “Preventing yours from join gangs: How to apply

- inoculation theory.” *Journal of Applied Security Research*, 4, 2009. p. 109 – 128.
- Galbraith, John Kenneth, 1958, *The Affluent Society*, New York: Houghton Mifflin.
- Gigerenzer, Gerd. 2014. “Rationalität.” In *Dorsch . Psychologisches Wörterbuch*, edited by H. Häcker and KH Stapf, 1380. Bern: Hans Huber.
- Glauert R., et al., Body dissatisfaction and the effects of perceptual exposure on body norms and ideals. *International Journal of Eating Disorders*, 2009. 42(5): p. 443–452. pmid:19115365
- Goodin , Robert E. 1980. *Manipulatory Politics*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- Goodin , Robert E., 1980, *Manipulatory Politics*, New Haven: Yale University Press.
- Gorin , Moti, 2014a, “Do Manipulators Always Threaten Rationality?” *American Philosophical Quarterly*, 51(1).
- Gorin , Moti. 2014a. “Do Manipulators Always Threaten Rationality?” *American Philosophical Quarterly* 51 (1): 51–61.
- Gorin , Moti. 2014b. “Towards a Theory of Interpersonal Manipulation.” In *Manipulation. Theory and Practice*, edited by Christian Coons and Michael Weber, 73–97. Oxford: Oxford University Press
- Gorton, William A., 2016, “Manipulating Citizens: How Political Campaigns’ Use of Behavioral Social Science Harms Democracy”, *New Political Science*, 38 (January): 61–80.
- Green, Ronald K., and Edward J. Pawlak. 1983. “Ethics and Manipulation in Organizations.” *Social Service Review* 57 (1): 35–43.
- Greenspan, Patricia, 2003, “The Problem with Manipulation”, *American Philosophical Quarterly*, 40(2): 155–164.
- Grotle , L., Haugen, AJ, Keller, A., Natvig , B., Brox , J. & Grotle , M. (2012). Poor agreement found between self-report and a public registry on duration of sickness absence. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 65, 212-218

- H. W. Simons. *Persuasion: Understand, practice, analysis* (2nd ed.). (New York: McGraw-Hill, 1986). p. 4.
- Handelman, Sapir, 2009, *Thought Manipulation: The Use and Abuse of Psychological Trickery*, Santa Barbara: Praeger Publishers.
- Hanna, Jason, 2015, “Libertarian Paternalism, Manipulation, and the Shaping of Preferences”, *Social Theory and Practice*, 41(4): 618–643. doi:10.5840/soctheorpract201541434
- Hannah, Jason. 2015. “Libertarian Paternalism, Manipulation, and the Shaping of Preferences.” *Social Theory and Practice* 41 (4): 618–643.
- Hill, Thomas E. Jr., 1980, “Humanity as an End in Itself”, *Ethics*, 91(1): 84–99. doi:10.1086/292205
- James McCroskey. *An introduction to rhetorical communication*. (Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall, 1972). p. 269.
- James, William. 1890. *Principles of Psychology*. New York: Henry Holt.
- Jay Conger. “The Necessary Art of Persuasion.” *Harvard Business Review Onpoint*, Fall 2010. p. 46.
- Jucker J.-L., et al., Nutritional status and the influence of TV consumption on female body size ideals in populations recently exposed to the media. *Scientific Reports*, 2017. 7(1): p. 1–9. pmid:28127051
- Kahneman, Daniel, 2013, *Thinking, Fast and Slow*, 1st edition, New York: Farrar, Straus and Giroux.
- Kasten, Vance, 1980, “Manipulation and Teaching”, *Philosophy of Education*, 14(1): 53–62. doi:10.1111/j.1467-9752.1980.tb00539.x
- Kasten, Vance, 1980, “Manipulation and Teaching”, *Philosophy of Education*, 14(1): 53–62. doi:10.1111/j.1467-9752.1980.tb00539.x
- Klenk, Michael, 2022, “(Online) Manipulation: Sometimes Hidden, Always Careless”, *Review of Social Economy*, 80(1): 85–105. doi:10.1080/00346764.2021.1894350
- Klenk, Michael, 2022, “(Online) Manipulation: Sometimes Hidden, Always Careless”, *Review of Social Economy*, 80(1): 85–105. doi:10.1080/00346764.2021.1894350

- Kligman , M., & Culver, CM (1992). An Analysis of Interpersonal Manipulation. *Journal of Medicine and Philosophy*, 17(2), 173–197. doi:10.1093/ jmp /17.2.173
- Kligman , Michael and Charles M. Culver, 1992, “An Analysis of Interpersonal Manipulation”, *Journal of Medicine and Philosophy*, 17(2): 173–197. doi:10.1093/ jmp /17.2.173
- Kole, Pamela, 2016, *Mind Games: Emotionally Manipulative Tactics Partners Use to Control Relationships*, CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform.
- Lanzing , M. (2018). “Strongly Recommended” Revisiting Decisional Privacy to Judge Hypernudging in Self-Tracking Technologies. *Philosophy & Technology*. doi:10.1007/s13347-018-0316-4
- Law C. and Labre MP, Cultural standards of attractiveness: A thirty-year look at changes in male images in magazines. *Journalism & Mass Communication Quarterly*, 2002. 79(3): p. 697–711.
- Leit RA, Pope HG Jr, and Gray JJ, Cultural expectations of muscularity in men: The evolution of Playgirl centerfolds. *International Journal of eating disorders*, 2001. 29(1): p. 90–93. pmid:11135340
- Levinson, JD, & Peng, K. (2007). Valuing Cultural Differences in Behavioral Economics. *ICFAI Journal of Behavioral Finance*, 4(1).
- Long, Todd R., 2014, “Information Manipulation and Moral Responsibility”, in Coons & Weber 2014: 151–175. doi:10.1093/acprof:oso /9780199338207.003,0008
- Mackenzie, C., & Stoljar , N. (Eds.). (2000). *Relational Autonomy: Feminist Perspectives on Automony , Agency, and the Social Self*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Mandava , Amulya and Joseph Millum , 2013, “Manipulation in the Enrollment of Research Participants”, *Hastings Center Report*, 43(2): 38–47. doi:10.1002/hast.144
- Manne, Kate, 2014, “Non-Machiavellian Manipulation and the Opacity of Motive”, in Coons & Weber 2014: 221–245. doi:10.1093/ acprof:oso /9780199338207.003.0011

- Marcuse, Herbert. 1969. "Aggressivität in der gegenwärtigen Industriegesellschaft." In *Aggression und Anpassung in der Industriegesellschaft*, edited by Herbert Marcuse and Alexander Mitscherlich, 7–29. Frankfurt: Suhrkamp.
- Mason, S. (2018, November 20). High score, low share: Why the gig economy loves gamification. *The Guardian*. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/business/2018/nov/20/high-score-low-pay-gamification-lyft-uber-drivers-ride-hailing-gig-economy>
- Matz, SC, Kosinski, M., Nave, G., & Stillwell, DJ (2017). Psychological Targeting as an Effective Approach to Digital Mass Persuasion. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 114(48), 12714–12719. doi:10.1073/pnas.1710966114
- McCreary DR, The Drive for Muscularity Scale: Description, Psychometrics, and Research Findings. 2007.
- McMahan, J. (2009). *Killing in war*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Mele, AR (1995). *Autonomous agents*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Merken, S. (2019, February 6). States Follow EU, California in Push for Consumer Privacy Laws. Retrieved March 25, 2019, from Bloomberg Law website: <https://news.bloomberglaw.com/privacy-and-data-security/states-follow-eu-california-in-push-for-consumer-privacy-laws-1>
- Mills, C. (1995). Politics and manipulation. *Social Theory and Practice*, 21(1), 99–130.
- Mills, Claudia, 1995, "Politics and Manipulation", *Social Theory and Practice*, 21(1): 97–112. doi:10.5840/soctheorpract199521120
- Mills, Claudia. 1995. "Politics and Manipulation." *Social Theory and Practice* 21 (1): 97–112. ,
- Moles, Andrés, 2015, "Nudging for Liberals", *Social Theory and Practice*, 41(4): 644–667. doi:10.5840/soctheorpract201541435
- Morgan-Short, K., & Bowden, HW (2006). Processing instruction and meaningful output-based instruction. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 28, 31-65.

- Morrison D., et al., Predicting the reward value of faces and bodies from social perception. *PloS one*, 2017. 12(9): p. e0185093. pmid:28926615
- Morrison TG and Halton M., Buff, tough, and rough: Representations of muscularity in action motion pictures. *The Journal of Men's Studies*, 2009. 17(1): p. 57–74.
- Murgia , M. (2019, May 4). When manipulation is the business model. *Financial Times*.
- Nadler, A., & McGuigan, L. (2018). An Impulse to Exploit: The Behavioral Turn in Data-Driven Marketing. *Critical Studies in Media Communication*, 35(2), 151–165. doi:10.1080/15295036.2017.1387279
- Nissenbaum , H. (2011). A Contextual Approach to Privacy Online. *Daedalus*, 140(4), 32–48. doi:10.1162/DAED_a_00113
- Noggle , R. (1996). Manipulative actions: A conceptual and moral analysis. *American Philosophical Quarterly*, 33(1), 43–55.
- Noggle , R. (2018a). Manipulation, Saliency, and Nudges. *Bioethics*, 32(3), 164–170. doi:10.1111/bioe.12421
- Noggle , R. (2018b). The Ethics of Manipulation. In EN Zalta (Ed.), *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (p. 24). Retrieved from <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/ethics-manipulation/>
- Noggle , Robert, 1996, “Manipulative Actions: A Conceptual and Moral Analysis”, *American Philosophical Quarterly*, 33(1): 43–55.
- Nys , TR, & Engelen , B. (2017). Judging Nudging: Answering the Manipulation Objection. *Political Studies*, 65(1), 199–214. doi:10.1177/0032321716629487
- Oshana, M. (Ed.). (2015). *Personal Autonomy and Social Oppression: Philosophical Perspectives* (First edition). New York: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Otsuka, M. (1994). Killing the innocent in self-defense. *Philosophy and Public Affairs*, 23(1), 74–94.
- Overstreet, M. (1998). Text enhancement and content familiarity: The focus of

- learner attention. *Spanish Applied Linguistics*, 2, 229-258.
- Palmer, N. (ed.) (2003) *Terrorism, War, and the Press*. Teddington, Middlesex: Hollis.
- Parfit, D. (2011). *On what matters* (Vol. 1). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Pariser, E. (2011). *The Filter Bubble: What the Internet Is Hiding from You*. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&scope=site&db=nlabk&db=nlabk&AN=1118322>
- Pereboom, D. (2014). *Free will, agency, and meaning in life*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Pienemann, M., & Lenzing, A. (2015). Processability theory. In B. VanPatten & J. Williams, J. (Eds.), *Theories in second language acquisition* (2nd ed.) (pp. 159-179). New York: Routledge.
- R. Evans, R. Rozelle, M. Mittelmark, W. Hansen, A. Bane and J. Havis. "Deterring the onset of smoking in children: Knowledge of immediate physiological effects and coping with peer pressure, media pressure, and parent modeling." *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 8, 1977. p. 126 – 135.
- RL Badawy et al. When do Machs feel threatened? An investigation into fair situations *Journal of Research in Personality* (2018)
- Rachlinski, JJ (R). *Cognitive Errors, Individual Differences, and Paternalism*. *University of Chicago Law Review*, 73(1), 207–229. Available at <https://chicagounbound.uchicago.edu/uclrev/vol73/iss1/11/>
- Raymond S Ross. *Understanding Persuasion*, 4th Edition. (Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Simon & Schuster, 1994). p. 2
- Raz, J. (1986). *The Morality of Freedom* (Reprinted). Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- Raz, J. (1999). *Practical reason and norms*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Raz, J. (2011). *From normativity to responsibility*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Reaves S., et al., *If looks could kill: Digital manipulation of fashion models*. *Journal of Mass Media Ethics*, 2004. 19(1): p. 56–71.

- Reinders, H., & Ellis, R. (2009). The effects of two types of input on intake and the acquisition of implicit and explicit knowledge. In R. Ellis, S. Loewen, C. Elder, R. Erlam, J. Philp, & R. Reinders (Eds.), *Implicit and explicit knowledge in second language learning, testing and teaching* (pp. 282-302). Bristol: Multilingual Matters.
- Ripstein, A. (2020). Kant and the law of war. Manuscript on file with the author.
- Rosen, G. (2003). Culpability and ignorance. *Proceedings of the Aristotelian Society*, 103, 61–84.
- Ryckman RM, et al., Male and female raters' stereotyping of male and female physiques. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 1989. 15(2): p. 244–251.
- Sanz, C. (1997). Experimental tasks in SLA research: Amount of production, modality, memory, and production processes. In A. Pérez-Leroux & W. Glass (Eds.), *Contemporary perspectives on the acquisition of Spanish: Vol. 2 production, processing and comprehension* (pp. 41-56). Somerville, MA: Cascadilla.
- Sanz, C. (2004). Computer delivered implicit versus explicit feedback in processing instruction. In B. VanPatten (Ed.), *Processing instruction: Theory, research, and commentary* (pp. 241-255). Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Sanz, C., & Morgan-Short, C. (2004). Positive evidence versus explicit rule presentation and explicit negative feedback: A computer-assisted study. *Language Learning*, 54, 35-78.
- Sharwood Smith, M. (1993). Input enhancement instructed SLA: Theoretical bases. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 15, 165-179.
- Shook, DJ (1994). What foreign language reading recalls reveal about the input-to-intake phenomenon. *Applied Language Learning*, 10, 39-76.
- Shore, B. (1996) *Culture in Mind: Cognition, Culture, and the Problem of Meaning*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Sidel, M. (2004) *More Secure, Less Free? Antiterrorism Policy & Civil Liberties after September 11*. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press.
- Silverman, I., & Choi, J. (2005). Locating places. In D. Buss (Ed.), *The Handbook of Evolutionary*

- Psychology (pp.177-199). Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons.
- Simard, D. (2009). Differential effects of textual enhancement formats on intake. *System*, 37, 124-135.
- Spellman, BA, & Kincannon , A. (2001). The relation between counterfactual (“but for”) and causal reasoning: Experimental findings and implications for jurors' decisions. *Law and Contemporary Problems: Causation in Law and Science*, 64, 241–264.
- Sripada , C. (2012). What makes a manipulated agent unfree? *Philosophy and Phenomenological Research*, 85, 563–593.
- Sripada , C., & Konrath, S. (2011). Telling more than we can know about intentional action. *Mind & Language*, 26, 353–380.
- Stephen ID, et al., Visual attention mediates the relationship between body satisfaction and susceptibility to the body size adaptation effect. *PloS one*, 2018. 13(1): p. e0189855. pmid:29385137
- Sturman D., et al., Independent Aftereffects of Fat and Muscle: Implications for neural encoding, body space representation, and body image disturbance. *Scientific reports*, 2017. 7(1): p. 1–8. pmid:28127051
- Water , R., Rounds, J., & Armstrong, PI (2009). Men and things, women and people: A meta-analysis of sex differences in interests. *Psychological Bulletin*, 135, 859-884.
- Sunstein, C., & Thaler, R. (2008). *nudge* New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- Swami V. and Tovée MJ, Male physical attractiveness in Britain and Malaysia: A cross-cultural study. *Body Image*, 2005. 2(4): p. 383–93. pmid:18089203
- Swami V., et al., The attractive female body weight and female body dissatisfaction in 26 countries across 10 world regions: Results of the International Body Project I. *Personality and social psychology bulletin*, 2010. 36(3): p. 309–325. pmid:20179313
- Tadros , V. (2013). *The ends of harm*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Tadros , V. (2020a). Secondary duties. In Miller PB and & Oberdiek J. (Eds.). (2020) *Civil wrongs and justice in*

- private law. New York: Oxford University Press (pp. 185-207).
- Tadros , V. (2020b). Two grounds of liability. *Philosophical Studies*, this issue.
- The emotional manipulation-psychopathy nexus: Relationships with emotional intelligence, alexithymia and ethical position *Personality and Individual Differences* (2010)
- Trahey , M., & White, L. (1993). Positive evidence and preemption in the second language classroom. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 15, 181-204.
- Tulving, E. (1983) *Elements of Episodic Memory*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Uludag , O., & VanPatten, B. (2012). The comparative effects of processing instruction and dictogloss on the acquisition of the English passive by speakers of Turkish. *International Review of Applied Linguistics*, 50, 189-212.
- Uttich , K., & Lombrozo , T. (2010). Norms inform mental state ascriptions: A rational explanation for the side-effect effect. *Cognition*, 116, 87–100.
- Van Dijk, TA (1989) 'Structures of Discourse and Structures of Power', in JA Anderson (ed.) *Communication Yearbook*12, pp. 18–59. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Van Dijk, TA (1991) *Racism and the Press*. London: Routledge.
- Van Dijk, TA (1993) *Elite Discourse and Racism*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Van Dijk, TA (1996) 'Discourse, Power and Access', in CR Caldas- Coulthard and M. Coulthard (eds) *Texts and Practices: Readings in Critical Discourse Analysis*, pp. 84–104. London: Routledge.
- Van Dijk, TA (1998) *Ideology: A Multidisciplinary Approach*. London: Sage.
- Van Dijk, TA (1999) 'Context Models in Discourse Processing', in H. van Oostendorp and SR Goldman (eds) *The Construction of Mental Representations during Reading*, pp. 123–148. Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Van Dijk, TA (2001) 'Multidisciplinary CDA: A Plea for Diversity', in Ruth Wodak and Michael Meyer (eds) *Methods of Critical Discourse Analysis*, pp. 95–120. London: Sage.

- Van Dijk, TA (2003) *Ideología y discurso* .
Barcelona: Ariel.
- Van Dijk, TA and Kintsch , W. (1983)
*Strategies of Discourse
Comprehension*. New York:
Academic Press.
- Van Leeuwen, T. (2005) *Introducing Social
Semiotics*. London: Routledge.
- VanPatten, B. (1996). *Input processing and
grammar instruction in second
language acquisition: Theory and
research*. Norwood, NJ: Ablex .
- VanPatten, B. (2004). *Input processing in
second language acquisition*. In B.
VanPatten (Ed.), *Processing
instruction: Theory, research, and
commentary* (pp. 5-32). Mahwah, NJ:
Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Wai, M., & Tiliopoulos , N. (2012). *The
affective and cognitive empathic
nature of the dark triad of personality*.
*Personality and Individual
Differences*, 52, 794,799.
- Waldmann , M., Nagel, J., & Weigmann , A.
(2012). *moral judgment*. In KJ
Holyoak & RG Morrison (Eds.), *The
Oxford handbook of thinking and
reasoning* (pp. 364–389). Oxford,
England: Oxford University Press.
- Want SC, *Three questions regarding the
ecological validity of experimental
research on the impact of viewing
thin-ideal media images*. *Basic and
Applied Social Psychology*, 2014.
36(1): p.
- Wastell , C., & Booth, A. (2003).
*Machiavellianism: An Alexithymic
Perspective*. *Journal of Social and
Clinical Psychology*, 22, 730-744.
- Wilson, DS, Near, D., & Miller, RR (1996).
*Machiavellianism: A Synthesis of the
Evolutionary and Psychological
Literatures*. *Psychological Bulletin*,
119, 285-299
- Winkler C. and Rhodes G., *Perceptual
adaptation affects attractiveness of
female bodies*. *British Journal of
Psychology*, 2005. 96(2): p. 141–154.
pmid:15969827
- Wood, AW (2014). *Coercion, manipulation,
exploitation*. In *Manipulation: Theory
and practice* (pp. 17–50).
- Woodward, J. (2006). *Sensitive and
insensitive causation*. *Philosophical
Review*, 115, 1–50.
- Woodward, J. (2010). *Causation in biology:
Stability, specificity, and the choice*

- of levels of explanation. *Biology and Philosophy*, 25, 287–318.
- Woolfolk, RL, Doris, JM, & Darley, JM (2006). Identification, situational constraint, and social cognition: Studies in the attribution of moral responsibility. *Cognition*, 100, 283–301.
- Yaffe , G. (2003). Indoctrination, coercion and freedom of will. *Philosophy and Phenomenological Research*, 67(2), 335–356.
- Young, L., & Phillips, J. (2011). The paradox of moral focus. *Cognition*, 119, 166–178.
- Young, L., & Tsoi, L. (2013). When mental states matter, when they don't , and what that means for morality. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 7, 585–604.
- Young, L., Camprodon , J., Hauser, M., Pascual-Leone, A., & Saxe, R. (2010). Disruption of the right temporoparietal junction with transcranial magnetic stimulation reduces the role of beliefs in moral judgments. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 107, 6753–6758.
- Young, L., Cushman, F., Hauser, M., & Saxe, R. (2007). The neural basis of the interaction between theory of mind and moral judgment. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 104, 8235–8240.